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D2.1 ENTRUST Reference Architecture – Initial Release

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Abstract	<p>Deliverable D2.1 provides a detailed description of the conceptual architecture of ENTRUST, which will provide the basis for the design, implementation, and integration activities of all ENTRUST components to be performed throughout the lifecycle of the project. To this end, we first provide an analysis of the status in the medical device domain, and we define the motivation of ENTRUST considering the most recent developments in the field of medical device cybersecurity. In addition, we provide details on existing standardization and regulatory efforts related to the use of medical devices by medical organizations and identify gaps in the existing standards. The aforementioned analysis provides the basis for the identification of the core research pillars considered in the context of ENTRUST, and the formulation of the research agenda to be followed. Next, for each of these pillars, we provide a state-of-the-art analysis, as well as the positioning of ENTRUST within the corresponding research domain. In addition, the</p>		

analysis on existing standards yielded an exhaustive list of functional, security, operational, legal, and ethical requirements, which has been refined and adapted to the specific needs of ENTRUST. Based on all the above, the conceptual architecture of ENTRUST is defined, including all components and their interconnectivity. The action workflow is split into three core phases, namely manufacturing, pre-deployment, and runtime, and we provide sequence diagrams depicting the action workflows for the processes to be performed in the context of the framework. Finally, we provide detailed description of the four envisioned use case demonstrators where the validation of the ENTRUST framework will be performed, and we define preliminary versions of the User Stories and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) based on which the experimental activities will be performed.

Keywords

Connected Medical Devices, Threat Modelling, Trust Assessment, Formal Verification, Runtime Attestation, Digital Twins, Physical Unclonable Functions, Misbehaviour Detection, Conformity Certificates, Secure Enrolment

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Dissemination Level		
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- * R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.
- DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-based Signatures
ACL	Access Control List
AK	Attestation Key
AOO	Actions on Objectives
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, techniques & Common Knowledge
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
C2	Command and Control
CA	Certification Authority
CEGAR	Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement
CFA	Control-Flow Attestation
CIV	Code Integrity Validation
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPSs	Cyber-Physical Systems
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service attacks
DDRV	Distributed and Decentralized Runtime Verification
DFG	Data Flow Diagram
DID	Domain Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoS	Denial of Service
DT	Digital Twin
EMTs	Emergency Medical Technicians
ENISA	European Network and Information Security Agency
FES	Feel Emotion Sensor
FL	Federated Learning
FV	Formal Verification
FW	Firmware
HDOs	Healthcare Delivery Organizations
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HRV	Hardware-supported Runtime Verification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology

IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LTL	Linear Temporal Logic
MD	Medical Device
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
MDSW	Medical Device Software
mHealth	Mobile health
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform
MITM	Man-In-The-Middle
ML	Machine Learning
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Descriptions
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OSN	Online Social Networks
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
PHG	Tellu Personal Health Gateway
PMS	Patient Monitoring Systems
PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
QMS	Quality Management System
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Risk Assessment
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RoT	Root-of-Trust
RPMS	Remote Patient Monitoring Systems
RTL	Required Level of Trustworthiness
SA	Static Analysis
SBOM	Software Bill of Material
SDL	Secure Development Lifecycle
SL	Subjective Logic
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theories
SoS	System of Systems
SPLC	Secure Product Life Cycle
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
STRIDE	Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Denial of Service and Elevation of Privilege
SUT	System Under Test
SW	Software

SWaP	Size, Weight, and Power
TAR	Trust Assessment Request
TARA	Threat Agent Risk Assessment
TC	Trusted Component
TDE	Trust Decision Engine
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TI	Threat Intelligence
TLEE	Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine
TM	Threat Modelling
TMM	Trust Model Manager
TOE	Target of Evaluation
TSM	Trust Sources Manager
TTP	Tactics, Techniques and Procedures
UID	Unique Initial Identification
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	13
List of Tables.....	15
Executive Summary	16
1 Introduction	18
1.1 Purpose and Scope.....	18
1.2 Structure of the Document.....	20
2 Motivation and Gap Analysis	21
2.1 Current Status in the Medical Device Domain	23
2.2 Cybersecurity Needs and Challenges.....	25
2.3 Analysis of the Current Standards and Identification of Gaps	27
2.3.1 Cyber Security Risk Management	32
2.3.2 Secure Product Life Cycle (SPLC)	35
2.4 Proposal by ENTRUST for Revision of the Current Guidance (MDCG 2019–16).....	38
2.5 Ethical and Legal Dimension of Trust Management in Next Generation of CMDs.....	40
2.5.1 Introduction and methodology	40
2.5.2 Problem Setting.....	40
2.5.3 International Framework.....	42
2.5.4 European Framework.....	43
2.5.5 Ethics	43
3 Research Agenda and Vision of ENTRUST.....	45
3.1 ENTRUST Vision	45
3.2 Research Pillars and Current State-of-the-Art	46
3.2.1 Formal Verification Models to Capture the Secure Device Lifecycle	46
3.2.2 Software Verification Through Code Analysis Techniques and Discussion on the Expansion of Verification Capabilities During Runtime Operation	49
3.2.3 Threat Modelling for Modelling Device Context	55
3.2.4 Trust Assessment Based on Subjective Logic and Properties to be Used as Runtime Trust Indicators to Construct Modular Protection Profiles for CMDs	65

3.2.5	Digital Twins for Simulating Various Attack Vectors and Evaluating the Defined Security Policies and Mitigation Actions.....	67
3.2.6	Runtime Attestation to Monitor and Assess the Secure State of the CMD During Runtime	72
3.2.7	Self-Certification of CMDs Based on Runtime Evidence and the use of Verifiable Presentations to Expand the MUDs.....	73
3.2.8	Use of PUFs as a Trusted Component for Enabling Attestation.....	74
3.2.9	CMD Evidence Monitoring Collection and Dynamic Tracing Functionalities for In-Depth Investigation of the CMDs Behaviour	80
3.2.10	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection on Blockchain Data	81
3.2.11	MUDs and Certificates of Conformity.....	81
4	Technical Requirements.....	88
4.1	Methodology	88
4.2	Framework Specifications	89
4.3	Security requirements	96
4.4	Operational Requirements (Pre-Deployment).....	100
4.5	Legal and Ethical Requirements.....	103
5	ENTRUST Conceptual Architecture.....	106
5.1	High-level Conceptual Architecture	107
5.1.1	Design Phase.....	109
5.1.2	Pre-deployment in the Domain	112
5.1.3	Runtime.....	112
5.2	Process view and High-level Sequence of Actions	114
5.2.1	Design-time and Pre-deployment in the Domain.....	114
5.2.2	Secure Enrolment	117
5.2.3	Runtime (Attestation & Conformity Certificate).....	119
5.2.4	Runtime (Misbehaviour Detection)	124
5.3	Functional Components	126
5.3.1	Design-time.....	127

5.3.2	Pre-deployment phase	131
5.3.3	Runtime phase	132
6	Use Cases.....	142
6.1	Overview of the Use Cases	142
6.2	Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting.....	142
6.2.1	Current Status	142
6.2.2	Scenario’s Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST	143
6.2.3	Threat landscape	143
6.2.4	“To-be” Scenario and User Stories	144
6.2.5	Metrics of success.....	149
6.3	Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living 151	
6.3.1	Current Status.....	151
6.3.2	Scenario’s Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST	153
6.3.3	Threat Landscape	155
6.3.4	“To-be” Scenario and User Stories	156
6.3.5	Metrics of Success	159
6.4	Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers.....	160
6.4.1	Current Status.....	161
6.4.2	Scenario’s Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST	162
6.4.3	Threat Landscape	163
6.4.4	“To-be” Scenario and User Stories	166
6.4.5	Metrics of Success	170
6.5	Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data.....	171
6.5.1	Current Status.....	171
6.5.2	Scenario’s Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST	172

6.5.3	Threat Landscape	172
6.5.4	“To-be” Scenario and User Stories	174
6.5.5	Metrics of Success	177
7	Conclusions.....	179
	References.....	181
	APPENDIX	193

List of Figures

Figure 1: Pert Chart highlighting the inter-dependencies of WP2 with the technical WPs as well as with the experimentation and validation WP, namely WP6.....	20
Figure 2: Formulation of Regulatory Requirements based on IEC 81001 5-1 and IEC 62304 standards	37
Figure 3: High-level overview of the cybersecurity requirements in the MDR document [11].....	39
Figure 4: Generic model of IoT device lifecycle (from [12])	47
Figure 5: Comparison of tools for symbolic security analysis (from [15]).....	48
Figure 6: Derivation rules for the abstract simplex algorithm (from [29]).....	51
Figure 7: Static analysis using machine learning (from [31])	53
Figure 8: DeepHunter workflow (from [32])	53
Figure 9: Data Flow Diagram (from [36]).....	57
Figure 10: STRIDE model for a basic web architecture [34].....	58
Figure 11: Attack tree model for SQLi attack [34].....	59
Figure 12: Priced Timed Automata using trees [39]	60
Figure 13: Markov chain with countermeasures [40].....	61
Figure 14: Kill chain of a ransomware [41].....	62
Figure 15: Ukraine cyber-attack simulation [42].....	63
Figure 16: Subjective Logic Framework.....	66
Figure 17 Part of the conceptual model for digital twin, physical twin, and their relations [53] ...	67
Figure 18: Part of the conceptual model characterizing digital twins [53]	68
Figure 19: Digital twins and security for cyber-physical systems [57].....	71
Figure 20: PUF taxonomy based on fabrication process [77] and the district PUF implementations considered in the context of ENTRUST.....	75
Figure 21: (a) A simple implementation of the weak PUF. The response of any attempted counterfeit would detectably differ compared to the response recorded of the genuine PUF. (b) A simple implementation of the strong PUF. Here, even if the PUF is compromised an attacker would not know the relevant challenges to record, and an eavesdropper could never hear a usable challenge response pair	76
Figure 22: Memory-based PUFs: (a) S-PUF, (b) B-PUF, (c) SR-L-PUF, (d) FF-PUF, (e) BR-PUF, (f) MECCA PUF (M-PUF)	77
Figure 23: Operation principle of an optical-PUF and its main building blocks	79
Figure 24: Tree representation of YANG MUD model in [113]	83
Figure 25: MUD architecture defined in [113].....	84
Figure 26: Certification Authority MUD sequence proposal.....	85
Figure 27: High-level generic lifecycle of medical products.....	89

Figure 28: Mapping of ENTRUST requirements. 89

Figure 29: Sequence diagram of the design and pre-deployment phases of a device..... 114

Figure 30: Pre-deployment phase 116

Figure 31: Manufacturer Bootstrapping and Domain Bootstrapping..... 117

Figure 32: Runtime attestation and creation of Conformity Certificate..... 120

Figure 33: Actions taken in case $ATL < RTL$ 122

Figure 34: ATL calculation 123

Figure 35: AI-based Misbehaviour Detection 125

List of Tables

Table 1: Medical needs and challenges to be addressed by the ENTRUST framework.....	25
Table 2: Pre-market activities	31
Table 3: Post-market activities.....	31
Table 4: Risk Management Plan Requirements.....	33
Table 5: Risk analysis / Risk Control Measures Requirement.....	33
Table 6: Risk analysis / Risk Control Measures Requirement.....	34
Table 7: Risk management report.....	35
Table 8: IEC 62304 Standard and IEC 81001-5-1 Standard Chapter Titles	38
Table 9: Research pillars of ENTRUST.	45
Table 10: Threat modelling methodologies weaknesses and advantages [33].....	63
Table 11: Threat modelling methodologies weaknesses.....	64
Table 12: ENTRUST framework specifications	90
Table 13: ENTRUST security requirements.....	96
Table 14: ENTRUST operational requirements.....	100
Table 15: ENTRUST legal and ethical requirements.....	103
Table 16: Functional Components of ENTRUST	126
Table 17: Tested functionalities and components for Secure Enrolment of ECG Monitoring Portable Devices use case	147
Table 18: Tested functionalities and components for Compositional Security and Cooperative Execution of Safety-Critical Operations in Hospital Settings use case	149
Table 19: KPIs for Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Use Case.....	150
Table 20: Tested functionalities for Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System Use Case.	158
Table 21: KPIs for Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System Use Case.....	159
Table 22: Use Case 3 Scenario 1: Smart Ambulance	165
Table 23: Tested functionalities and components for Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers Use Case.....	168
Table 24: KPIs for Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers Use Case.....	170
Table 25: Tested functionalities and components for Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring Use Case	176
Table 26: KPIs for Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring Use Case.....	177
Table 27: Comprehensive list of requirements for the medical domain	193

Executive Summary

Modern medical organizations, such as hospitals and healthcare providers, are increasingly adopting network infrastructures consisting of multiple medical devices originating from different manufacturers, with varying computational capabilities and hardware specifications, and subject to different security, privacy, and trustworthiness requirements. In this context, ENTRUST envisions the design and development of a **holistic framework for the provision of runtime operational assurance of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)**, as well as **the network infrastructure of the organization as a whole**. While there have been significant advancements in the literature in the domain of medical device cybersecurity, as well as **regulatory and standardization efforts** guiding medical organizations towards the adoption of effective solutions, there is not yet a comprehensive solution that is able to encompass all underlying requirements in a manner that is able to adapt to various types of medical organizations.

Therefore, ENTRUST envisions a detailed work plan towards the design and development of a set of **components and methodologies formulating the overall security framework**, which also aims to **push forward the state-of-the-art in various research areas adjacent to the domain of medical device cybersecurity**. Deliverable D2.1 is dedicated to the documentation of the approach followed in ENTRUST with regard to the design and implementation of such as solution and encloses the conceptual ENTRUST architecture and the technical requirements. In addition, ENTRUST envisions the validation of the provided framework through **four use case demonstrators**, capturing a wide gamut of requirements and practical scenarios pertaining to modern medical organization infrastructures, specifically (i) **Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring of Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting**, (ii) **Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living**, (iii) **Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carriers**, and (iv) **Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data**. In this context, this deliverable provides a comprehensive view of ENTRUST's use cases and scenarios and describes the user stories to be employed for showcasing of core ENTRUST pillars. In addition, an initial set of KPIs per use case has been devised (to be revised under D6.1), hinting at business and technical indicators that will be tested in the frame of WP6.

In addition, D2.1 aims to provide a reference document for the ENTRUST project to be used as input for the technical WPs, namely WP3, WP4, WP5. One core activity performed to this end is the **definition of the list of requirements to be fulfilled by the ENTRUST solution**. Specifically, the consortium has worked towards defining these requirements, considering not only existing standards but also EU Regulations on medical devices, needed for fulfilling the project's vision of providing a holistic trust management framework that can safeguard Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) during the whole spectrum of their lifecycle, strengthening trust and privacy in the entire medical ecosystem. These requirements, with a holistic view on a security solution in today's healthcare ecosystems, have been categorised as describe functional requirements, security requirements and operational requirements. Following these activities, considering also the guidance provided by the ENTRUST Advisory Board (AB), a mapping between the project's technical requirements and the use case requirements has been conducted, identifying the exact needs of each use case and the specific ENTRUST functionality that will be tested in each scenario.

Another core aspect of this deliverable is the provision of a **high-level overview of the conceptual architecture of ENTRUST**. This includes not only the definition of the **technical components** and their **positioning within the overall ENTRUST framework**, but also the

definition of the entire **action workflow of the framework**, starting with the activities carried out during the manufacturing of the device, followed by the activities needed in order to deploy the device into the network infrastructure of the target medical organization, and including the activities carried out during the operation of the device for the provision of **runtime operational assurance** and the **real-time mitigation of identified threats and vulnerabilities**. In addition, we provide high-level sequence diagrams depicting the action workflows for several operations to be performed in the context of the ENTRUST framework, such as **Manufacturer and Domain Bootstrapping, Remote Attestation, and Misbehaviour Detection** (i.e., anomaly detection in network traffic data). These sequence diagrams will provide the basis for the design and implementation activities to be carried out throughout the lifecycle of the project, which will be documented in subsequent deliverables throughout all technical WPs.

Overall, D2.1 aims to provide a comprehensive document, outlining not only the approach to be followed by ENTRUST with regard to the design and implementation of all envisioned core artefacts, but also technical details on the methodologies and components to be developed as part of the project, as well as the activities to be carried out for their validation in practical scenarios defined by the four use case demonstrators.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

In recent years, there have been significant advancements in the domain of medical devices, which are increasingly being used in the context of large-scale medical organizations in an interconnected manner, in order to perform operations related to various healthcare aspects, including the **collection of patient data**, the **continuous monitoring of patient status**, and the **use of such data for diagnostic purposes**, either on-site or remotely. Therefore, in order to ensure the uninhibited provision of such medical services in a manner that fulfils all underlying security, privacy, and trustworthiness requirements, it is of paramount importance for such medical organizations to implement security measures that are able to provide operational assurance to medical devices, as well as the system as a whole, throughout their operational lifecycle. Such networks typically comprise multiple heterogeneous Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) originating from different manufacturers, subject to different requirements, and with varying levels of available hardware and computational capabilities.

In this regard, the vision of ENTRUST is *to design and implement an end-to-end trust assessment framework to dynamically manage the lifecycle of connected medical devices (CMDs), starting from the design phase (including formal verified trust models, risk assessment process security policies) to the runtime monitoring, strengthening trust and privacy in the entire medical ecosystem, offering enhanced operational assurance without limiting the applicability of such devices*. The deliverable at hand introduces the scope and vision of ENTRUST, denoting the technical requirements that have been identified by the partners, and the use cases for the implementation of the envisaged ENTRUST multifunctional cybersecurity platform. The deliverable provides in detail the ENTRUST conceptual architecture, the technical requirements of the project, some representative reference scenarios, and a number of user stories to be investigated within these scenarios.

Specifically, in order to provide the basis for the research and development activities to be carried out throughout the lifetime of the ENTRUST project, in Chapter 2 we first outline the existing regulations set forth by the EU with regard to medical device security, specifically **Regulation (EU) 2017/745** [1] on medical devices, and **Regulation (EU) 2017/746** [2] on *in vitro* diagnostic medical devices. In this context, in order to provide the required cybersecurity guarantees, medical device manufacturers need to adhere to the **Medical Device Regulation (MDR)** regarding the implementation of robust risk management system addressing both security and cybersecurity risks. Considering these regulations, as well as the needs of actual medical organizations set forth by the use case demonstrators of ENTRUST, we identified the core medical needs and challenges to be addressed by the ENTRUST framework. These include the need to design and implement a **security and privacy solution that is applicable throughout the entire lifecycle of a medical device**, while also providing devices with the capability to **verifiably prove that they in a correct configuration and operational state during runtime**, while achieving the appropriate balance between **security, safety, and performance**, considering the resource-constrained nature of the examined medical devices. In addition, the implemented security enablers should achieve the **certifiability and auditability** of their outcomes.

Considering this approach, in Chapter 3, we identify the core **research pillars** to be focused on in the context of ENTRUST, and we define the appropriate **research agenda and vision** in order to construct the required components and methodologies in order to formulate the ENTRUST framework. We also perform a state-of-the-art analysis in each of the identified research pillars and we outline the approach to be followed by ENTRUST to provide significant contributions to the research landscape in those areas. In addition, based on the aforementioned standards and

regulations, in Chapter 4 we focus on the formulation of the **list of requirements to be fulfilled by the ENTRUST framework**, covering a wide range of aspects including **framework specifications, security requirements, operational requirements, and legal/ethical requirements**.

Having laid the groundwork for the research and development work plan to be carried out in the context of ENTRUST, in Chapter 5 we provide a detailed overview of the ENTRUST framework, including the set of components to be designed and implemented, their positioning within the overall framework, and the overall action workflow. Note that this is split into three core phases, the **manufacturing phase**, the **pre-deployment phase**, and the **runtime phase**. We also provide high-level action workflows for various processes to be performed as part of the ENTRUST framework, such as **Manufacturer and Domain Bootstrapping, Remote Attestation, AI-Based Misbehavior Detection** (i.e., anomaly detection in network traffic data). Throughout the lifecycle of the project, the ENTRUST framework will be evaluated in the context of the envisioned use case demonstrators. Specifically, in Chapter 6, we define a **preliminary set of user stories and KPIs**, which will provide the basis for the experimental activities to be carried out in the context of WP6 in order to evaluate the efficiency and performance of the project artefacts.

As the reference architecture and technical requirements deliverable, this deliverable serves as the basis for all later WPs and deliverables. This initial version of the deliverable includes a comprehensive background and gap analysis (T2.1) of the current standards regarding security, privacy and trust in the context of CMDs, the functional and non-functional requirements (T2.2) of the framework per se along with the first version of the ENTRUST Architecture (T2.3) accompanied with the first version of the ethical analysis (T2.4) on the measures of evidence to be considered and the type of secure elements to be used (T2.5). The final version of this deliverable will be provided by the end of M24 and will include the complete developments of T2.3-T2.5 and potential updates on the reference architecture. In addition, D2.1 constitutes the baseline for Milestone MS1 - Reference Architecture and Operational Landscape to be met by the ENTRUST framework, as it delivers the architectural specification of the ENTRUST architecture. The inter-dependencies of WP2 with the ENTRUST technical WPs as well as with the experimentation and validation WP (WP6) are depicted in the figure below (Figure 1), in the form of a pert chart.

Figure 1: Pert Chart highlighting the inter-dependencies of WP2 with the technical WPs as well as with the experimentation and validation WP, namely WP6

1.2 Structure of the Document

In **Chapter 2**, the current regulations and standards in the medical device domain are presented, along with the cybersecurity needs and challenges faced by a modern healthcare ecosystem. Then, a thorough analysis of the current standards and the gaps identified are provided, accompanied by an ethical and legal dimension of trust management in next generation of CMDs. The research pillars of ENTRUST and the current state of the art are presented in **Chapter 3**, whereas in **Chapter 4** the methodology and the technical requirements of the envisioned framework are outlined. **Chapter 5** serves for presenting the ENTRUST reference architecture in detail, whereas **Chapter 6** comprehensively describes the four use cases, including the reference scenarios adopted by each demonstrator. The user stories from which the requirements will be drawn as part of the scenarios are described in detail and will govern the industrial demonstrations of the ENTRUST. Finally, **Chapter 7** concludes the deliverable.

2 Motivation and Gap Analysis

In recent years, organizations operating within the healthcare industry, referred to as **Healthcare Delivery Organizations (HDOs)**, employ various types of **heterogeneous medical devices** operating in cloud network topologies in an interconnected manner. Therefore, they are increasingly exposed to an **expanded attack surface** comprising a wide variety of types of threats and vulnerabilities, technology issues, software risks, and human factors. These may lead to issues such as **compromising the operations of HDOs**, as well as the **integrity of patient data**. Existing solutions for such organizations typically consider the notion of security in a fragmented manner, through the application of specific policies targeting individual devices. Considering the above, *ENTRUST aims to address the issues affecting HDOs in a holistic manner, through the design, implementation, and deployment of a security framework that can address all types of security, privacy, and trustworthiness requirements of HDOs.*

As aforementioned, in the healthcare sector, one core issue that needs to be addressed is the **safeguarding of property and personal data**. This is especially pertinent in the case of medical devices and mobile applications used for health purposes. These products are used to exchange data, remotely monitor patients, predict risks, and even pilot medical devices. Some of these applications and software are qualified as medical devices or diagnostic medical devices, and are CE marked under the new European regulations. As a result, they fall under the scope of ANSM surveillance [3]. In this regard, while the marketing of medical devices is well-regulated in terms of **standardization and regulatory** efforts, the culture of cybersecurity among manufacturers is still at a low level of maturity. Specifically, some manufacturers may lack the knowledge or resources to conduct specific risk analyses or are unaware of cybersecurity requirements. Others may fail to take cybersecurity into account during the design and development process of the medical device. Furthermore, there are no specific texts or recommendations dedicated to IT cybersecurity in the medical device industry. Therefore, *one of the core targets of ENTRUST is the ability to provide a security solution for medical organizations that not only follows the existing standards but is also efficiently applicable to a wide range of organizations belonging to the healthcare sector.*

One core tenet of the security solution offered by ENTRUST is the **secure and trustworthy verification of the identity of Connected Medical Devices (CMD)** belonging to an HDO. Traditional notions of security for healthcare organizations consider a perimeter approach, based on which a strong outer security perimeter is built, while network traffic within the perimeter is considered trusted. However, this approach is increasingly outdated, as the definition of such a perimeter is often not realistic and does not consider the existence of external and internal threats on the network itself, thus rendering network locality as insufficient for determining trust in a network. To this end, ENTRUST employs a **Zero Trust** approach, based on which **no device is considered trusted by default**, but should be able to provide **strong (hardware-based) guarantees on the correctness of its own identity**. Based on this approach, all devices and users need to be authenticated and authorized, and policies must be dynamic and calculated from as many sources of data as possible. In other words, *Zero Trust removes the assumption of trust and requires entities to provide strong guarantees on the correctness of their identity and configuration state regardless of network location, subject, or asset.*

In [4], a **Zero Trust Maturity Model** is defined, according to which Zero Trust for medical devices in HDOs is achieved based on five core zero trust maturity pillars:

- **Identity:** This refers to an attribute or set of attributes that uniquely describe a user or entity, and entails the implementation of measures that serve to securely validate the identity of the CMD. In this regard, HDOs should ensure and enforce that the right users and devices have access to the correct resources at the appropriate time. HDOs need a

reliable method to discover, classify, and inventory all medical devices, including a detailed insight into the type of device, its capabilities, location, and behaviours. Based on these, the security of CMDs depends on authenticating and ensuring that each device can be trusted to do what is expected. Considering all the above, the ENTRUST framework needs to establish a method to collect all pertinent information about each medical device, including information used to determine what policies should be applied to each device.

- **Device:** A device is a hardware asset that can connect to the network infrastructure of the target medical organization. While CMDs have significantly enhanced the capability of HDOs to deliver quality healthcare, there is a number of challenges that need to be faced by HDOs in order to ensure the integrity of their devices for ensuring secure access to services and data. Specifically, these include the **identification of unseen vulnerabilities** that may create exponential risk, the **identification of threats**, the **safeguarding of CMDs against access by unauthorised individuals** who may tamper with the device or attempt to extract sensitive data, the implementation of **secure update and patching mechanisms** against the identified vulnerabilities, and the **integration of modern authentication methods**.
- **Network:** This refers to open communication mediums, including internal network, wireless, and the Internet. In this regard, HDOs need to align network segmentations and protections according to the needs of application workflows instead of the implicit trust inherent in traditional network segmentation. As aforementioned, the fact that CMDs are part of a network is a factor that leads to the creation of security risks. Therefore, when considering the Risk Assessment approach of ENTRUST, we need to consider the interdependencies between CMDs in order to generate the risk graph of the entire topology. In addition, it is necessary to **monitor network traffic** so that the **AI-based Misbehaviour Detection** component can detect any unexpected network traffic behaviour, which is an indication of risk that may require further investigation for the identification of malicious activity.
- **Application:** This includes medical applications that are executed on-premise and in the cloud. In this regard, HDOs need to integrate protections closely with application workflows to ensure that they have the visibility and understanding required to provide adequate security. In the context of Zero Trust, since no device is trusted by default, verification of a CMD is required before it gets access to the applications. This aims to ensure the security of medical device applications and to prevent device and data breaches. In addition, data encryption in motion and at rest is essential for application security.
- **Data:** This refers to data handled by CMDs in the context of their normal operation, or the execution of a security enabler. Specifically, medical devices produce a large volume of electronically protected health information that serves many purposes, such as **diagnostics, monitoring, and treatment of patients**, in order to provide safe and effective healthcare. In addition, large volumes of data can be used for population health and preventive analytics. In the context of the security enablers, devices need to exchange data between them, such as raw traces used as attestation evidence during the execution of an attestation enabler. The notion of Zero Trust allows the use of data through **access control enforcement granularity** and focuses on a foundational, data-centric approach to cybersecurity rooted in the tenets of zero trust, based on which data is protected regardless of where it resides. Specifically, ENTRUST aims to implement dynamic policies to protect enterprise processes by controlling access to data, for example through the implementation of **Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE)** and **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** mechanisms that ensure identity-centric data security.

From all the above, it follows that with the increasing connectivity of medical devices to networks such as Wi-Fi, radiofrequency, and Bluetooth, they are exposed to new threats generated by technological progress, including malicious acts such as hacking and cyber-attacks, which are not adequately addressed by state-of-the-art solutions. The consequences of these threats could be devastating, as they could directly impact the safety of care and the health of patients. Therefore, **it is becoming essential for medical device manufacturers to integrate basic cybersecurity requirements into the design of their products.** This will help to guarantee the achievement of the **required level of security against malicious activity.** To ensure that medical devices are adequately protected against these threats, it is possible to conduct a gap analysis based on cybersecurity standards related to MDR and IVDR regulations. This analysis will provide insight into any gaps that exist in current cybersecurity practices and highlight areas where improvements can be made.

In the remainder of this Chapter, we will provide a detailed analysis of the state-of-the-art of existing cybersecurity solutions in the medical device domain, identifying the gaps in these solutions and outlining how the approach followed by ENTRUST will address issues and gaps in the existing methods. Throughout this deliverable, we will provide a detailed overview of the ENTRUST framework, which is designed in a manner that is able to address the specific needs of the medical domain in a holistic, efficient, and trustworthy manner.

2.1 Current Status in the Medical Device Domain

The European Union has put in place several regulations and standards to ensure cybersecurity in the medical device industry. The regulations concerning medical devices were reviewed in depth, leading to the publication of two new ones in 2017. One of them is the Regulation (EU) 2017/745 concerning medical devices, and the other is the Regulation (EU) 2017/746 concerning diagnostic medical devices in vitro. These two regulations have been in force since May 26, 2020, and May 26, 2022, respectively. Before their invalidation, certificates issued by notified bodies under the directives will remain valid until the end of their period of validity.

To combat cyber threats, medical device manufacturers are required by the Medical Device Regulation (MDR) to implement robust risk management systems addressing both security and cybersecurity risks. Annex I, paragraphs 14.2d, 17.1, 2, and 4 outline requirements for the IT environment to ensure that medical devices are secure by design and can operate securely. The MDR mandates that medical devices are secure by design and address cyber threats by default and outlines the requirements for the IT environment to ensure that devices can operate securely. Manufacturers must establish, implement, document, and maintain a continuous iterative process of risk management throughout the lifecycle of a device, which includes controlling risks related to the IT environment and single fault conditions, as well as mitigating the impact of security vulnerabilities in the host platform, operating system, or network.

Implementing risk management throughout the lifecycle of a medical device involves a comprehensive and multi-faceted approach. This process begins at the design and development stage, where manufacturers must incorporate cybersecurity principles into the initial design of the device. This includes selecting secure components, using encryption for data transmission and storage, and designing interfaces that are resilient to unauthorized access. During the manufacturing process, quality control measures must be employed to ensure that cybersecurity standards are met. This involves regular testing and validation of security features and updating protocols to address any identified vulnerabilities.

Once the device is in use, continuous monitoring is essential. Manufacturers are required to establish a system for ongoing surveillance and reporting of any cybersecurity incidents. This system should include regular software updates and patches to address emerging threats.

Additionally, manufacturers are expected to provide training and support to users to ensure they understand the security features and best practices for operating the device safely.

In the post-market phase, manufacturers must actively engage in monitoring the cybersecurity landscape for new threats and vulnerabilities that could impact their devices. This involves participating in information sharing forums and collaborating with cybersecurity experts to stay informed about the latest threats. In the event of a security breach, manufacturers must have a response plan in place that includes timely notification to users and regulatory bodies, and rapid deployment of fixes to mitigate the impact.

Throughout this entire process, compliance with regulatory requirements must be maintained. This includes documenting all steps taken to ensure cybersecurity and submitting necessary reports to regulatory bodies. By adopting such a proactive and comprehensive approach to risk management, manufacturers can significantly reduce the cybersecurity risks associated with medical devices throughout their entire lifecycle.

The IEC 60601-1 Appendix H.7 describes possible causes of hazardous situations for medical devices in IT networks, while UL 2900-1 and UL 2900-2-1 provide guidance on verifying and validating security risk control measures against design requirements for vulnerabilities, exploits, and software weaknesses.

According to the MDR, a "medical device" means any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes: diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease, diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability, investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state, providing information by means of in vitro examination of specimens derived from the human body, including organ, blood and tissue donations, and which does not achieve its principal intended action by pharmacological, immunological or metabolic means, in or on the human body, but which may be assisted in its function by such means. The following products shall also be deemed to be medical devices: devices for the control or support of conception; products specifically intended for the cleaning, disinfection or sterilization of devices as referred to in Article 1(4) and of those referred to in the first paragraph of this point.

Furthermore, several standards are specific to mobile and wireless medical devices, such as the Diabetes Technology Society's "Guidance for Use of Mobile Devices in Diabetes Control Contexts" and the DTSec standard for wireless diabetes devices. The IEC 80001-1 and related standards are designed for asset owners of healthcare IT networks, while the ISO/IEC 27000 series covers a broad range of information security topics. The IEC 62443 Standard Series is particularly helpful for defining cybersecurity requirements for critical infrastructures and is also highly applicable for system integrators. In addition to the EU standardization efforts outlined throughout this section, several additional efforts have been outlined in the literature towards the guidance and standardization of securing CMDs [5], such as the Medical Device Interoperability Reference Architecture (MDIRA) created by the JP-APL for the US Army [6]. Another interesting report is the Medical Device and Health IT 4 Joint Security Plan [7] by the Healthcare and Public Health Sector Coordinating Council (HCSS) 2019. The Health Level Seven International (HL7) [8] is a standards developing organization dedicated to providing a comprehensive framework and related standards for the exchange, integration, sharing, and retrieval of electronic health information. This organization offers several standards and resources, including the HL7 Reference Information Model [9]. In addition, the National Telecommunications and Information

Administration (NTIA) and the Cybersecurity Infrastructure and Security Agency (CISA) both advise the adoption of the Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) [10].

Compliance with these regulations requires cooperation between hospital asset owners, system integrators, and medical device manufacturers. The medical device industry has been evolving rapidly, and the implementation of the new regulations and standards is essential to secure medical devices and IT networks. Cybersecurity in the medical device industry is complex and requires cooperation between a wide range of stakeholders, including hospital asset owners, system integrators, and medical device manufacturers.

2.2 Cybersecurity Needs and Challenges

As outlined throughout this deliverable, the core target of ENTRUST is the design, implementation, and deployment of a holistic security framework that can ensure the secure, reliable, and uninterrupted operation of CMDs within the network infrastructure of a medical organization. The end goal is to ensure the **unimpeded provision of healthcare services** to patients, while also safeguarding the **integrity and privacy of sensitive patient data**. Compounding all the above, in Table 1 we provide an overview of the identified medical needs and challenges, as well as some insight on how they will be addressed by the services to be integrated into the ENTRUST framework.

Table 1: Medical needs and challenges to be addressed by the ENTRUST framework

Medical Need or Challenge	Description
How can we build a security and privacy solution that is applicable throughout the entire lifecycle of a medical device?	The approach followed by ENTRUST entails the design and implementation of security enablers that can monitor the correctness of CMDs during runtime, throughout their operational lifecycle. For instance, the Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) scheme attests to the correctness of a set of device properties in order to ensure that is in a desired configuration state. In addition, following a failed attestation, simulations can be executed on the Digital Twin of the device to determine the source of the failure with the help of the SW Verification module. Afterwards, the Protection Profile Composition Engine is able to update the Protection Profile of the device accordingly. Note that the policies specifying the security and attestation enablers that need to be executed by each device are contained in its Protection Profile, which is initially constructed during manufacturing and dictates the properties that need to be attested in order to address the specific threats and vulnerabilities identified.
How can we build trustworthy devices capable of providing self-issued certificates (evidence) that they are in a trusted state and their configuration, and specifications are as expected during runtime?	As aforementioned, the CIV scheme is able to ensure that the device is in a trusted state based on the Protection Profile that has been provided by the device Manufacturer (and may have been updated during the operation of the device following the identification of new threats or vulnerabilities), and its configuration and specifications are as expected during runtime. In addition, following a successful attestation, the Certification and Auditing component is able to construct a Conformity Certificate for the CMD, demonstrating the correctness of the configuration state of the device to certification bodies, auditors, and external third parties with the appropriate permissions. Note that in case a device is found to be compromised after the issuance of the certificate, ENTRUST enables the revocation of the deprecated certificate.
How can we effectively create design-time	ENTRUST implements a variety of tools designed to achieve the Required Trust Level (RTL) of a CMD before its deployment to the network infrastructure of a

<p>tools to achieve the required level of trust for each specific application?</p>	<p>medical organization. Specifically, the SW/FW Verification module is able to verify the correctness of the SW and FW of the device prior to its deployment. In addition, the Risk Assessment module can calculate the risk profile of the device based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities. Based on these, the Digital Twin of the device can be used to simulate identified types of attacks that may target the CMD and to identify the appropriate mitigation measures. The Formal Models provide methods for the mathematical verification of the security enablers provided by ENTRUST, and the Protection Profiles Composer creates the Protection Profile of the device compounding all the above into a set of policies to be applied for ensuring the runtime correctness of the CMD.</p>
<p>How can we enhance operational assurance without limiting the applicability of connected medical devices?</p>	<p>ENTRUST employs a hybrid HW-based Trusted Component (TC) that consists of a Physically-Unclonable Function (PUF) and a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) that are able to handle the creation of the required cryptographic material for the execution of the security enablers of ENTRUST, as well as the execution of cryptographic functions. In addition, the attestation schemes and the Runtime Tracer are designed in a lightweight manner, that aims to operate in a non-intrusive way that does not impede the normal operation of the device.</p>
<p>What optimization strategies should be used to balance the trade-off between security, safety, and performance?</p>	<p>Throughout the lifecycle of ENTRUST, experimentation activities will be carried out on all implemented methods and schemes in the context of the envisioned use case demonstrators to evaluate their security, safety, and performance. Based on the results of these experiments, the appropriate strategies will be determined in order to optimize the operation of the implemented schemes and the required adjustments will be made.</p>
<p>How does trust assessment affect or work in tandem with safety assessment mechanisms?</p>	<p>As aforementioned, the remote attestation enablers of ENTRUST will be used in order to evaluate the correctness of the configuration and operational state of a CMD during runtime, by evaluating the correctness of a set of device parameters, determined by the Protection Profile of the device. These parameters are traced as needed by the Tracer, who is responsible for collecting the attestation evidence for the execution of the attestation scheme. After the attestation process is complete, the Trust Controls module can calculate the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the measured parameters compared to the Required Trust Level (RTL). In case the ATL is lower than the RTL, mitigation measures need to be taken to increase the trust level of the device, such as the deployment of a patch or software update.</p>
<p>How can we verify the correct execution of system updates after a security incident?</p>	<p>As aforementioned, in case of a failed attestation, the Conformity Certificate of the device is revoked so that it can no longer be considered as trustworthy. Afterwards, it is possible to utilize the Digital Twin of the device to emulate the attack and identify the cause of the failed attestation. Based on this, it may be needed to deploy a secure software update to the device in order to patch any identified vulnerabilities. In addition, the Protection Profile Composition Engine of the device updates the Protection Profile of the CMD accordingly, to reflect the new attestation actions that need to be taken for verifying the correctness of the device. The execution of these actions leads to the verification that the system update was successful, and that the device can be considered trustworthy again.</p>
<p>How can we deploy the solution even to resource-constrained devices (e.g., BLE)?</p>	<p>Medical devices are typically resource-constrained and do not possess the necessary hardware to execute complex mathematical operations. Therefore, the methods implemented by ENTRUST will consider the limitations of these devices in order to provide runtime operational assurance in a fast and efficient manner.</p>
<p>Gaps in the existing guidance (security by</p>	<p>ENTRUST will provide significant contributions to the field of cybersecurity for medical applications, since the state-of-the-art does not yet consider the security issues that arise from the interconnectivity of CMDs in the context of large-scale</p>

design, post market surveillance, etc.) medical organizations and the types of attacks that may be performed on such systems (e.g., attacks that aim to gain illicit access to a device by compromising a different device and using it as an entry point). In addition, a market analysis will be performed in order to identify the **positioning of ENTRUST in the market**, the targeted **market segment**, possible **exploitation paths** for each core artefact of ENTRUST, and the appropriate **business strategy** to be applied not only per individual artefact, but also for the ENTRUST framework as a whole.

2.3 Analysis of the Current Standards and Identification of Gaps

This section delves into the current standards set forth by the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) for ensuring the cybersecurity of medical devices and software. As these systems become increasingly integrated with digital technology, they inherit vulnerabilities akin to other cyber-physical systems. Thus, adopting a comprehensive approach to security is essential. We will analyse the eight (8) key practices recommended by the MDCG, which encompass a holistic "Defence-in-Depth" strategy throughout the product lifecycle. These practices range from security management to the provision of detailed security guidelines, forming a foundational framework for securing medical devices against a myriad of cyber risks. This analysis not only highlights the current standards but also aims to identify potential gaps and areas for improvement, ensuring that the security measures remain effective and resilient in the face of evolving cyber threats.

Figure 2- Defence in depth strategy for Product Life Cycle

According to the MDCG, the general approach to managing security for medical devices and software is similar to that of other cyber-physical systems. To establish a "Defence-in-Depth" strategy throughout the product lifecycle, the following eight common practices must be in place:

Practice 1 – Security management: The security management practice ensures that security-related activities are adequately planned, documented, and executed throughout the product's lifecycle.

Practice 2 – Security requirements specification: This practice is used to identify the security capabilities required to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data, function, and services of the medical device in the specified product security context. Security capabilities may include authentication, authorization, encryption, auditing, and other security features that a product requires. The product security context may include physical security levels, external interface protection via a firewall, and other items. Security requirements can be defined at the product level or may supplement product-level requirements.

Practice 3 – Secure design: The processes specified by this practice ensure that the product is secure by design, including defence in depth.

Practice 4 – Secure implementation: The processes specified by this practice ensure that product features are implemented securely. The requirements in this practice apply to all hardware and software components in the product, except for externally provided components, for which the requirements of Practice 1 (Security Management) apply instead.

Practice 5 – Security verification and validation testing: This practice documents the security testing required to ensure that all the security requirements have been met for the product and that security is maintained when the product is used as intended. Security testing should align

with other product test activities and can be performed at various times by different personnel during the security lifecycle based on the type of testing and the vendor's development model.

Practice 6 – Security-related issue management: This practice is used to handle security-related issues of a product.

Practice 7 – Security update management: This practice ensures that security updates and patches associated with the product are tested for regressions and made available to product users in a timely manner.

Practice 8 – Security guidelines: This practice provides and maintains user documentation that describes how to integrate, configure, and maintain the defence in depth strategy of the product in accordance with its product security context.

Figure 3: NIST CSF

Figure 4: MD Lifecycle (MDCG 2019-16)

In this section, we delve into a comprehensive analysis of the current standards in pre-market and post-market activities, with a particular focus on the European Union's Medical Device Regulation (EU MDR), UL 2900-2-1, and the IEC 62443 series (IEC 62443-4-1 and IEC 62443-4-2). These standards are pivotal in ensuring the security and reliability of medical devices throughout their lifecycle. Our analysis is structured into two primary tables: one for Pre-Market activities and another for Post-Market activities. Each table is further divided to detail the specific activities and requirements under these standards, providing an in-depth view of the regulatory landscape.

For the Pre-Market section, we explore areas such as Secure Design, Risk Management, Validation and Verification processes, Technical Documentation, and Post-Market Surveillance Planning. We compare and contrast the requirements laid out in the EU MDR with those in UL 2900-2-1 and IEC 62443-4 standards. This comparison highlights the degree of coverage, including areas of partial coverage and gaps, within each standard.

In the Post-Market section, the focus shifts to ongoing obligations after the medical device has been released to the market. This includes continual Risk Management, updating Risk Control Measures, maintaining a vigilant Post-Market Surveillance System, and reporting on safety and incidents. Again, we assess the alignment and discrepancies between the EU MDR and the other mentioned standards.

This structured approach not only provides clarity on the current standards but also aids in identifying the gaps where additional measures or revisions may be required to enhance the safety, security, and compliance of medical devices. The goal of this analysis is to offer a detailed and comparative perspective that can serve as a foundation for developing more robust regulatory strategies and practices in the field of medical device security and surveillance.

Table 2: Pre-market activities

EU MDR	UL 2900-2-1	IEC 62443-4-1 and IEC62443-4-2
Pre-market activities		
Secure Design (Annex I)	Requirements 7.1, 8.1, 9.1 Security Controls	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 3 - Secure by Design IEC62443-4-2 FR1 - FR-7
Risk Management (Annex I)	Requirement 12.1 Risk Analysis and Risk Management Process	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 2 - Specification of security requirements -> Partial coverage
Establish Risk Control Measures (Annex I)	Requirement 12.4.3 Design and Development Process-related Risk Controls	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 2 - Specification of security requirements -> Partial coverage
Validation, Verification, Risk Assessment, Benefit Risk Analysis (Annex I)	Requirement 12.2 Risk Evaluation Process Requirement 12-19 Functional and Penetration Testing Requirements	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 5 - Security Verification and Validation Testing
Technical Documentation (Annex II and III)	Requirements 4-1, 5-1, 6-1 Product Documentation and Documentation for Product	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 8 - Security Guidelines
Establish a Post-market Surveillance Plan and Post-Market Surveillance System (Article 83 and 84)	Requirements 12.3 Risk Management Plan & File -> Partial Coverage	Not Covered
Clinical Evaluation Process (Chapter VI)	Requirements 12-19 Functional and penetration testing requirements	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 5 - Security Verification and Validation Testing

Table 3: Post-market activities

EU MDR	UL 2900-2-1	IEC 62443-4-1 and IEC62443-4-2
Post-market activities		

Risk Management (Annex I)	Requirement 12.1 Risk Analysis and Risk Management Process	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 2 - Specification of security requirements -> Partial coverage
Modify Risk Control Measures / Corrective Actions / Patches (Annex I)	Requirement 20.4 Product update release and patch management process	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 7 - Security Update management
Validation, Verification, Risk Assessment, Benefit Risk Analysis (Annex I)	Requirement 12.2 Risk Evaluation Process Requirement 12-19 Functional and Penetration Testing Requirements	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 5 - Security Verification and Validation Testing
Maintain and update a Post-Market Surveillance Plan and Post-Market Surveillance System (Article 83 and 84)	Requirements 12.3 Risk Management Plan & File -> Partial Coverage	Not Covered
Trend Reporting (Article 88)	Requirement 12.1 Risk Analysis and Risk Management Process	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 6 - Management Security related issues
Analysis of Serious Incidents (Article 89)	Requirement 12.1 Risk Analysis and Risk Management Process	IEC62443-4-1 Practice 6 - Management Security related issues
Post-Market Surveillance Report (Article 85)	Not covered	Not covered
Periodic Safety Update Report (Article 86)	Not covered	Not covered
Inform the Electronic System on Vigilance (Article 92)	Not covered	Not covered

2.3.1 Cyber Security Risk Management

Medical device security is a critical component of the healthcare industry. While compliance with ISO 14971 for risk management is essential, it is no longer sufficient to ensure device safety. Cybersecurity risk management is equally important as it has the potential to directly impact the safety of the device. Consider a scenario where a ventilator on an ICU unit is password protected for security reasons. While this may seem like a reasonable measure, the lack of access to the password during an emergency situation renders the "secure" feature a safety hazard.

Therefore, when it comes to cybersecurity risk management, it is vital to assess the trade-off between safety and performance. One possible approach is to use AAMI TIR 57, which complements the safety risk management activities of ISO 14971. Alternatively, the risk management method of ISO/IEC 15408 standards can also be employed for a more in-depth evaluation of device security.

Table 4: Risk Management Plan Requirements

Risk Management Plan Requirements	Description
<i>Scope of Risk Management Activities</i>	<i>Clearly define the scope of risk management activities</i>
Devices and Accessories	Identify all devices and accessories in question
Life Cycle Phases of Device	Describe the life cycle phases of the device
Assignment of Responsibilities and Authorities	Clearly define responsibilities and authorities for risk management
Identification of Requirements for Review	Identify the requirements for review of risk management activities
System for Categorizing Risk	Define a system for qualitative or quantitative categorization of probability of occurrence of harm and severity of harm
Criteria for Acceptable Risk Levels	Define the criteria for acceptable risk levels
Evaluation of Residual Risk Acceptability	Evaluate the acceptability of residual risk, including overall residual risk
Criteria for Acceptability of Overall Residual Risk	Define criteria for acceptability of overall residual risk
Verification of Risk Control Measures	Verify implementation of risk control measures
Verification of Effectiveness of Risk Control Measures	Verify the effectiveness of risk control measures
Activities for Collection and Review of Production and Post-Production Information	Identify activities for collection and review of production and post-production information

Table 5: Risk analysis / Risk Control Measures Requirement

Risk analysis / Risk Control Measures Requirement	Content Descriptions
The documentation shall contain information on:	The benefit-risk analysis referred to in section 1 and 8 of MDR Annex I
	The solutions adopted and the results of the risk management referred to in section 3 of MDR Annex I
	Evidence given that a safety concept in accordance with section 4 of MDR Annex I is applied, including information to users of any residual risk(s)
The documentation shall include	Design risk assessment: documented risk assessment for the design aspects of the device.

Production/process risk assessment: documented risk assessment for the production / manufacturing process aspects of the device.
Clinical/Application/Product risk assessment: documented risk assessment for the clinical usage / application aspects of the device.
For design risk assessment, an assessment shall be provided whether any design changes add new hazards or reduce the likelihood of occurrence of existing hazards, irrespective of whether the risk assessment has changed.

Reduction of the risks related to use error shall cover the requirements set out in section 5 of MDR Annex I. For usability evaluation please refer to the MDR requirements stated in Annex I, clauses 14.6,21.3, 22.1, 22.2, 23.1a, as well as to EN 62366-1.

Table 6: Risk analysis / Risk Control Measures Requirement

Risk analysis / Risk Control Measures Requirement	Content Descriptions
Risk analysis shall demonstrate	All known and foreseeable hazards associated with each device are identified and analyzed (i.e., estimation and evaluation of risks for each hazardous situation)
	All known and foreseeable risks, and any undesirable side-effects, are minimized and acceptable when weighed against the evaluated benefits to the patient and/or user arising from the achieved performance of the device during normal conditions of use.
	Estimation and evaluation of risks associated with and occurring during intended use and during reasonably foreseeable misuse are estimated and evaluated, including eliminating or controlling these risks
The documentation shall include	Appropriate controls (i.e., process validations, biocompatibility, sterilization, clinical, shelf-life or other key verification/validation tests) have reduced all risks as low as possible to acceptable levels considering state-of-the-art for the product(s) under assessment.
	Risk control measures are implemented for each hazard (with references to the documentation where these measures are implemented).
	The effectiveness of risk control measures is verified (with references to the documentation where effectiveness of risk control measures is demonstrated).
	Residual risks and their processing operations are identified, and the acceptability of any residual risk(s) is assessed
	A statement is given that the medical benefits outweigh all the residual risks.
	Production and post-production information are evaluated regarding hazards and their associated risks, as well as on the overall risk, benefit-risk ratio and risk acceptability; and the control measures are amended if necessary
Hazards related to all device components	

Risk analysis shall cover (not limited to)	Hazards related to clinical use.
	Hazards related to ergonomic features of the device and the environment in which the device is intended to be used.
	Hazards related to technical knowledge, experience, education, training and use environment of users
	Hazards related to the medical and physical conditions of intended users (lay, professional, disabled, etc.).
	Hazards related to reuse.
	Hazards related to the manufacturing process.
	Hazards related to cybersecurity.

Additionally, it should be noted that in addition to the hazards identified in the Risk Management Plan, there may be additional hazards to consider as outlined in EN ISO 14971.

Table 7: Risk management report

Risk management report	Content Descriptions
Provide the risk management report associated with the device, including	The evaluation of any residual risk(s) acceptability
	The evaluation of the overall residual risk acceptability
	The evaluation of the benefit risk ratio

2.3.2 Secure Product Life Cycle (SPLC)

Risk management is an essential and ongoing activity that must be carefully considered, controlled, and documented throughout all phases of a medical device's life cycle. This encompasses everything from the device's initial conception and development, through testing, market authorization, post-market use, and ultimately its end-of-life and obsolescence. The most effective way to meet these expectations is by adopting a Secure Product Life Cycle (SPLC) approach to risk and quality management.

In support of this, it is recommended that manufacturers consult relevant standards, such as the International Electrotechnical Commission's (IEC) 62304. This standard provides guidance on the software development life cycle for medical device software and can assist in achieving effective risk management.

It is crucial to recognize that cyber security risk, like all other risks, must be effectively minimized and managed throughout the device's life cycle. Failure to do so can lead to serious issues, including the device's failure to deliver its therapeutic benefits, breaches in the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of medical device data, or unauthorized access to the device and its network.

Critical to the SPLC approach is the ongoing application and updating of quality management systems, including **risk management procedures, change management procedures, design procedures, and complaint management procedures**. As clinical use of a medical device often

exceeds the expected lifespan of the technology that supports its operation, manufacturers and sponsors must work closely with users to effectively minimize risk and ensure the device's safe and reliable use.

2.3.2.1 Compliance Throughout MDSW Lifecycle

To ensure regulatory compliance, medical devices that incorporate software must meet certain criteria. In particular, Annex I of the new regulations defines general safety and performance requirements, some of which are specifically aimed at medical device software (MDSW).

According to Section 14.2 of the MDR, MDSW must be designed and manufactured in such a way as to "eliminate or reduce as far as possible (...) any risk associated with a possible negative interaction between the software and the computing environment in which they operate and with which they interact". This is particularly important for MDSW that interacts with other systems, such as software linked to a Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS), as any adverse interactions can have serious consequences for patient safety.

Similarly, Section 14.5 of the MDR specifies that "devices intended to be implemented with other devices or products must be designed and manufactured in such a way that their interoperability and compatibility are reliable and safe". This is especially important for MDSW, as they are often designed to work in conjunction with other devices or software. Therefore, it is critical that MDSW is designed to be fully interoperable and compatible with any other medical device or software it is intended to work alongside.

Section 17 of the MDR is dedicated specifically to Medical Device Software (MDSW), which includes programmable electronic systems and software that are devices in their own right. It emphasizes that the design of MDSW must guarantee repeatability, reliability, and performance in accordance with their intended use. Measures must be taken to eliminate or reduce all risks or degradation of their performance. The following items are detailed:

- **Section 17.1:** "Devices incorporating programmable electronic systems, including software, or software that are devices in their own right are designed to ensure repeatability, reliability and performance with respect to their intended use. In the first fault condition, adequate means are adopted to eliminate or reduce as much as possible the resulting risks or performance degradation" (MDR, Annex I, 17.1).
- **Section 17.2:** "For devices that include software or for software that are devices in their own right, this software is developed and manufactured in accordance with the state of the art, taking into account the principles of the development cycle, risk management, including information security, verification and validation" (MDR, Annex I, 17.2).
- **Section 17.3:** "Software covered by this section that is intended to be used in conjunction with mobile computing platforms shall be designed and manufactured taking into account the specific characteristics of the mobile platform (e.g. screen size and contrast ratio) and the external factors related to their use (variation of noise level or brightness in the environment)" (MDR, Annex I, 17.3).
- **Section 17.4:** "Manufacturers state the minimum requirements for computer hardware, computer network characteristics, and computer security measures, including protection against unauthorized access, that are necessary to operate the software as intended" (MDR, Annex I, 17.4).

The regulations also require the generation of substantial documentation around the software.

Section 6.1 of Annex II of the MDR covers software verification, validation, description of the software design and development process, and evidence of software validation as used in the finished device. This information typically includes a summary of the results of all verification,

validation, and testing performed internally and in a simulated or real-world use environment prior to final release. In addition, as stated in Section 6.1 of the MDR, " software verification and validation (describing the software design and development process and evidence of the validation of the software, as used in the finished device. This information shall typically include the summary results of all verification, validation and testing performed both in-house and in a simulated or actual user environment prior to final release. It shall also address all of the different hardware configurations and, where applicable, operating systems identified in the information supplied by the manufacturer)."

Additionally, the IEC 81001-5-1 (Health software and health IT system safety, effectiveness and security - Part 5-1: Security - Activities in the product life cycle) standard supplements the IEC 62304 standard (Medical device software – Software life cycle processes) to meet the regulatory requirements applicable to the design and development of software (of) medical devices.

Indeed, the activities that these two standards provide for the processes of the software life cycle (of) medical devices are intended to meet requirements of distinct types:

- On the one hand the security requirements of the software and
- On the other hand, the cybersecurity (or safety) requirements of the software.

Figure 2: Formulation of Regulatory Requirements based on IEC 81001-5-1 and IEC 62304 standards

In addition, the requirements of IEC 81001-5-1 and IEC 62304 standards impact the same software life cycle processes:

- Software risk management,
- Software design and development,
- Software maintenance,
- Software configuration management and
- Software problem solving.

This is particularly visible when comparing both standards chapters titles:

Table 8: IEC 62304 Standard and IEC 81001-5-1 Standard Chapter Titles

IEC 62304 Standard Chapter	IEC 81001-5-1 Standard Chapter
1. Scope	1. Scope
2. Normative references	2. Normative references
3. Terms and definitions	3. Terms and definitions
4. General Requirements	4. General Requirements
5. Software development process	5. Software development process
6. Software maintenance process	6. Software maintenance process
7. Security Software risk management process	7. Safety Software risk management process
8. Software configuration management	8. Software configuration management
9. Software problem resolution process	9. Software problem resolution process

2.4 Proposal by ENTRUST for Revision of the Current Guidance (MDCG 2019–16)

In order to ensure that the devices placed on the EU market are fit for the new and emerging technological challenges linked to cybersecurity risks, two new regulations on medical devices have been adopted and entered into force on 25 May 2017, namely **745/2017 (MDR)** and **746/2017 (IVDR)**. These regulations, aiming to replace three existing EU Directives, have been applied for medical devices and for in vitro diagnostic medical devices. These texts lay down new essential safety requirements for all medical devices that incorporate electronic programmable systems and software and require manufacturers to develop and manufacture their products in accordance with the state-of-the-art, considering principles of risk management and information security, as well as to set out minimum requirements regarding IT security measures, such as protection against unauthorised access.

In order to provide guidance to manufacturers on the fulfilment of all essential security requirements outlined in the two aforementioned documents, the **Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG)** compiled a document [11] that aims to incorporate mechanisms tailored to modern complex medical device supply chains, as well as additional considerations concerning expectations from actors other than manufacturers. It also provides a description of other EU and global pieces of legislation and guidance relevant to the domain of cybersecurity for medical devices. Note that the MDCG was established by Article 103 of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 and consists of representatives of all EU Member States and is chaired by a representative of the European Commission.

In Figure 3, we provide a high-level overview of the general safety and security requirements of the Medical Device Regulations (MDR) document with focus on cybersecurity, which deal with both pre-market and post-market aspects. These requirements provide the basis for the development of recommendations and guidance for medical device manufacturers specified in [11]. These requirements are also applicable to those included in the regulation on In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices (IVDR), between which correspondence can be identified.

Figure 3: High-level overview of the cybersecurity requirements in the MDR document [11]

Following a detailed examination of the aforementioned documents by the ENTRUST consortium, some gaps were identified regarding the standardization of IT Security in the domain of secure device design and trustworthiness in medical devices. To this end, *ENTRUST is in the process of publishing a White Paper outlining a proposal to amend the current MDCG guidance with a harmonized canonical catalog of requirements for the medical device domain.* Specifically, the approach proposed by ENTRUST is characterized by the following observations:

1. **There is a need for the definition of a set of essential requirements needed for device design.** This refers to the definition of software and firmware specifications, cryptographic protocols, communication of internal system components, and secure-by-design environments.
2. **There is a need for formally verifying device design,** which is a challenging topic. Therefore, there needs to be a minimum set of requirements to be followed, as well as the support and provision of Trusted Components (TCs).
3. **Manufacturers must perform risk-benefit analysis** in order to establish balance between safety, performance, and security.
4. **There must be a consolidation between trust requirements** in order to create an overall model of trustworthiness comprising safety, security, privacy, resilience, and reliability. Note that the establishment of trustworthiness is quite challenging, and there need to be assumptions without risking the normal operation of medical devices.

Considering the above, ENTRUST will propose a revision of MDCG 2019-16 around the following core tenets:

- Expansion of the current notion of **Conformity Certificates**, which are limited to the design and manufacturing of a device, by also including runtime and verifiable evidence.
- Harmonization of the **Conformity Assessment framework during runtime** based on claims provided by the devices.
- Further enhancement of the MUDs with Conformity Certificates, referred to as **Protection Profiles**, as verifiable evidence on the security posture of each CMD.

- Enabling device manufacturers to **prove compliance** with existing standards and regulations.
- Definition of the **minimum-security requirements** to be followed by manufacturers, such as required set of device capabilities related to trusted/secure boot.

Overall, through the provision of a harmonized approach regarding the management of all relevant cybersecurity aspects in the domain of medical devices, ENTRUST aims to provide a methodology that will enable both manufacturers and medical organizations to ensure the secure operation of devices, considering the need of large-scale interconnected systems consisting of multiple heterogeneous devices.

2.5 Ethical and Legal Dimension of Trust Management in Next Generation of CMDs

2.5.1 Introduction and methodology

The goal of this subsection is to define the legal framework for e-health at International and European levels.

First, a definition of e-health along with an explanation of the risks involved is presented. After the introduction of e-health and its risks, the appropriate International and European legal frameworks are identified.

For the International framework, the conventions considered are the Convention on the Protection of Individuals regarding Automatic Processing of Personal Data (Convention 108); the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention); the International Medical Informatics Association (IMIA) Code of Ethics for Health Information Professionals; World Health Organization (WHO) Resolution on e-Health; International Standardization Organization (ISO) Standards for Electronic Health Records (EHRs). The presentation of the conventions follows a chronological order, starting from the least to the most recent.

Subsequently, the European legal framework is addressed. The Regulations and Directives that are considered are: Regulation 2016/679/EU (GDPR)[1]; Directive 2002/58/EC (Directive on privacy and electronic communications or ePrivacy Directive)[2]; Proposal for a regulation laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act)[3]; Regulation 2017/745/EU European medical devices regulation (MDR)[4]; Directive 2022/2555/EU on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS 2)[5].

In tandem with this legal analysis, ethical considerations are presented, offering a comprehensive view of the ethical landscape surrounding e-health initiatives.

Regarding the application of the aforementioned frameworks to the ENTRUST project, the corresponding requirements (see Chapter 4) that make it abide by them are identified and presented in a later section.

2.5.2 Problem Setting

Providing a concise definition of electronic health proves to be a challenging endeavour due to its expansive nature, encapsulating a diverse range of applications and services. E-Health seems a comprehensive umbrella term, encompassing various concepts and technologies within the realm of healthcare. Electronic health records (EHRs), telemedicine, mobile health (mHealth), health information exchange (HIE), wearable devices, and health applications are well-known applications of e-health. Through the deployment of these applications, e-health ensures a myriad of functionalities, such as instantaneous access to medical information, facilitation of remote monitoring, and provision of real-time communication [7].

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines e-health, alternatively known as the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), as the utilisation of information and communication technology (ICT) in the domain of health [8]. A widely accepted definition, articulated by the German-Canadian researcher Gunther Eysenbach, characterises e-health as "[...] referring to health services and information delivered or enhanced through the Internet and related technologies. In a broader sense, [...] to improve health care locally, regionally, and worldwide by using information and communication technology" [9].

In summary, e-health is an HTI, therefore capable of improving people's quality of life, which arises from the union of the health service with the Internet and other technologies, and which is at the centre of a paradigm shift in healthcare.

However, despite the manifold applications and advantages presented by this emerging intersection of public health and ICT, inherent cybersecurity risks pose significant challenges to the integrity of digitised healthcare systems. Healthcare institutions confront elevated financial risks associated with data theft, stemming from their liability profiles and the vast volume and diversity of data collected and stored. More and more healthcare institutions face particularly high financial risk from data theft, owing to both their liability profile and the volume and variety of data they collect and store.

While healthcare is embracing technological advancements, attention and measures must be increased to counter cyber risks in this interconnected environment, particularly in the context of maintaining ongoing patient safety [10]. There is a strong need for further regulatory guidance, acknowledging the importance of addressing and mitigating risks associated with Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) devices. Indeed, it is essential to recognize that "any device leveraging a network or information system is inherently susceptible to hacking" [11].

In Europe, a recent study by ENISA revealed that healthcare organisations reported the highest number of security incidents related to vulnerabilities in software or hardware [12].

The same trend is recognizable also in other countries.

In the US, a whopping 94% of healthcare institutions reported having been victims of cyberattacks (Filkins B. SANS healthcare cyber threat report: widespread compromises detected, compliance nightmare on the horizon. Norse. February 2014 [13]).

In India, cyberattacks in the healthcare sector are rising. In 2023 60% of health organisations have been hit by cyber-attacks and only 24% of healthcare organisations were able to disrupt a ransomware attack before the attackers encrypted their data [14].

Finally, in Australia it was reported that between 2019 and 2020 there was an 84% rise in cyber-attacks in the healthcare sector [15].

The implications and risks connected to e-health are extremely relevant, and even if its role should be to improve the quality of life of people and patients, these embedded risks can represent a threat to patient well-being.

Considering the case of a patient with high blood pressure and chronic heart failure who relies on a smart pillbox to ensure they take their medications correctly; a malicious actor could exploit vulnerabilities in the pillbox's software to manipulate the device's data. For instance, they could double the dose of the patient's diuretic medication or deceive the device into marking the pill as dispensed, leading the patient to believe they have already taken it [16]. These alterations may result in significant repercussions for the patient's well-being, potentially posing the risk of organ damage or, in extreme cases, fatal outcomes.

Since e-health can increase the well-being of patients, and at the same time make the same patients more exposed to risks to their safety, it seems to have the nature of *pharmaka*, (a drug that can provide patients benefic or malefic depending on the dose administered), having simultaneously curative and noxious effects [17]. Consequently, a risk-based approach is needed, capable of adopting the benefits of e-health, while reducing its harmful and noxious effects.

To do this, in this chapter the legal reference framework for e-health and specifically for medical devices, clarifying its legal and ethical limits is defined.

2.5.3 International Framework

- **Convention on the Protection of Individuals regards Automatic Processing of Personal Data (Convention 108)**
 - The Convention, commonly known as Convention 108, was established in 1981 and currently, 55 countries ratified it. This agreement addresses crucial aspects of data protection, including principles governing the safeguarding of personal data, the lawfulness of data processing, the rights of data subjects, and transborder data flows. Convention 108 sets standards for responsible and lawful handling of personal data in the context of automatic processing, promoting a harmonised approach to privacy protection across its member states.
- **Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention)**
 - The Budapest Convention, adopted in 2001 and ratified by 65 states, is a significant step forward to fight cybercrime. It is the first international treaty to address this issue comprehensively, and it has already had a positive impact on the way nations cooperate to combat cybercrime. (For the interest of this section, the offences related to child pornography are excluded). S
- **International Medical Informatics Association (IMIA) Code of Ethics for Health Information Professionals**
 - The Code of Ethics for Health Information Professionals, adopted in 2002, serves as a guiding framework for ethical conduct and professional responsibilities among health information professionals. The Code incorporates the principles of bioethics (Autonomy, Justice, Beneficence, Non-Maleficence) into the institutional framework of health information management, thereby emphasising the ethical imperatives associated with the use and management of health information.
- **World Health Organization (WHO) Resolution on e-Health**
 - The most recent WHO resolution on e-health, WHA71.7, was adopted in 2018. The resolution focused on the role of e-health in improving health systems and promoting health equity. It also called for the development of global standards for patient health information and the strengthening of international cooperation in e-health.
- **ISO 13606-1:2019 - International Standardization Organization (ISO) Standards for Electronic Health Records (EHRs)**
 - The International Standardization Organization (ISO) Standards for Electronic Health Records (EHRs) ensure interoperability, security, and quality in the domain of healthcare informatics. Specifically, ISO 13606-1:2019 provides a comprehensive set of guidelines that delineate the technical specifications and requirements for the development, implementation, and management of Electronic Health Records. ISO standards in this context address fundamental aspects such as data exchange formats, terminologies, and security protocols to facilitate seamless communication and integration of health information systems across diverse healthcare settings. By establishing a common language and structure for

electronic health data, these standards promote the continuity of care, while improving patient safety, and facilitating collaborative research initiatives.

2.5.4 European Framework

- **Directive 2002/58/EC (Directive on privacy and electronic communications or ePrivacy Directive)**
 - The ePrivacy Directive (EU) 2002/58/EC is designed to complement and enhance the protection of individuals' privacy in the context of electronic communications, including the use of cookies and similar technologies. The ePrivacy Directive sets rules and requirements aimed at ensuring the confidentiality of communications, protecting personal data, and promoting user consent for certain online tracking activities.
- **Regulation 2016/679/EU (GDPR)**
 - GDPR applies to the processing of personal data by a data controller or processor in the EU. Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. GDPR extends its application to all foreign companies processing data of EU residents.
- **REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 European medical devices regulation (MDR)**
 - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 is the European Union's Medical Device Regulation, which entered into force on May 26, 2021. It replaces the Medical Devices Directive (MDD) and sets out a new legal framework for medical devices in the EU. The MDR aims to lay down harmonized requirements for medical devices placed on the market within the European Union (EU).
- **Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA**
 - Since Regulation (EU) 2019/881 established the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) and strengthened its role in ensuring the cybersecurity of the European Union (EU), it has placed itself in a central position for the analysis of the European legal framework
- **Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union NIS 2**
 - Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, also known as NIS 2, is a significant update to the Network and Information Security (NIS) Directive, which was first adopted in 2016. The NIS 2 Directive aims to strengthen cybersecurity across the European Union (EU) by introducing several new requirements for operators of essential services (OESs) and digital service providers (DSPs).

2.5.5 Ethics

Further to the legal dimension, the ethical dimension of connected medical devices is also crucial. Having in mind that these devices can collect and transmit sensitive personal health information, we should assure patients that their data will be kept secure and used only for their benefit.

Based on the analysis the ethical issues to consider are the following:

1. **Informed consent to use data:** Users must be fully informed about how the data will be collected, stored, and used before they consent to the use of connected medical devices
2. **Safety and transparency:** Users need to be assured that the devices they are using are safe and reliable, and they should be informed of any potential risks associated with the device's use.

3. **Ensuring that devices remain safe and effective after every update or when integrated into different clinical situations:** It is essential to ensure that the device's functionality remains safe and effective after every update and when integrated into different clinical situations, any potential risks should be communicated transparently to the users.
4. **Consent of research use of this data:** The consent of research use of this data needs to be obtained explicitly, and users should have the right to access and control their data.
5. **Informational privacy:** Users have a right to expect that their data will be kept private and confidential, and that it will not be shared or sold without their explicit consent.
6. **Ownership and data access:** Users need to be informed about where their data is stored and who has access to it.

3 Research Agenda and Vision of ENTRUST

As aforementioned, the core vision of ENTRUST entails the design, implementation, and integration of a holistic framework in order to provide runtime operational assurance to medical devices throughout their operational lifecycle and their integration into a medical organization, while ensuring the security and integrity of the devices and related data, as well as the medical organization as a whole. In order to achieve this, ENTRUST aims to develop a number of components as part of the overall framework architecture, each one of which will play a specific role in the provision of operational assurance. In this regard, ENTRUST aims to provide innovative solutions in a wide range of research domains, covering various facets of operational assurance in the medical domain.

Here, we first provide details on the core vision of ASSURED with regard to the research agenda and vision of ENTRUST, in the context of all targeted research domains. Throughout the remainder of this Chapter, we elaborate on the motivation of ENTRUST for the research activities in each identified research domain, we provide a state-of-the-art analysis on the literature for each of these domains, and we outline the research approach to be followed in ENTRUST.

3.1 ENTRUST Vision

As aforementioned, the research activities of ENTRUST can be categorized into a number of core pillars, corresponding to each innovative technology and component to be integrated into the overall ENTRUST framework. In Table 9 we provide a high-level overview of those research pillars, as well as their significance as part of the ENTRUST framework.

Table 9: Research pillars of ENTRUST

Research pillars of ENTRUST	Description
Formal Verification Models	ENTRUST envisions following a mathematically rigorous approach to systematically identify any vulnerabilities and flaws within the software and hardware components used for the ENTRUST framework.
Software Verification through code analysis techniques	Verification protocols and mechanisms (Code integrity Validation techniques such as memory fuzzing, concolic testing etc.) are used in the context of ENTRUST towards enhancing the automated orchestration of CMD security enablers.
Threat modelling	This includes methodologies and tools to identify the exact type of SW-based attacks (e.g., code injection, data-oriented attacks, etc.) that need to be taken into consideration.
Trust assessment	The scope of this pillar is the compilation of a library of data harmonization and trust management techniques for extracting (during runtime) the types of security claims that need to be produced by devices as measures of evidence on their trustworthiness.
Digital Twins for simulation of attack vectors	ENTRUST envisions the utilization of a testbed offering the capabilities to launch virtualized representations of the medical devices capturing all of their operational profiles and interconnections for enabling (real-time) device monitoring SW-based attack simulation and validation.
Runtime attestation	This includes techniques to measure the integrity of all executables and libraries before loading them to the volatile memory, providing trustworthy and privacy-aware support for CMDs. Specifically, the Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) scheme aims to attest to the correctness of a set of device attributes through the collection of the required evidence, and the Swarm Attestation (SA) scheme aims to attest to the correctness of multiple devices simultaneously, in a manner that is more computationally efficient than attesting to each device individually.

Self-certification of CMDs based on runtime evidence	Since healthcare systems typically employ physical credentials in order to identify patient attributes, such as insurance details, employee badges, and patient cards, ENTRUST envisions the issuance of Verifiable Credentials (VCs) containing the totality of user attributes that can be verifiably demonstrated, as well as the construction of Verifiable Presentations (VPs) containing the subset of those attributes that is needed in order to prove their possession, following the principle of selective disclosure.
Use of PUFs as a trusted component for enabling attestation	Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) are an attractive approach for providing digital keys for secure cryptographic protocols in IoT devices, in a physically controlled, unclonable, non-reproducible mechanism, based on parameters generated during the manufacturing process. ENTRUST envisions the use of PUFs in order to provide strong hardware-based guarantees to the keys used in the context of various cryptographic operations.
CMD evidence monitoring collection and dynamic tracing	In the context of the attestation schemes of ENTRUST, the CMD needs to be able to collect data to be used as attestation evidence. Therefore, we need to construct dynamic tracing mechanisms that are able to address challenges specific to the CMD domain, while also leveraging advancements in data analytics, Machine Learning, and AI algorithms.
AI-based Misbehavior Detection	In the context of ENTRUST, Misbehavior Detection refers to anomaly detection based on collected network traffic data. Since CMDs may operate within the network infrastructure of large-scale medical organizations, we are able to utilize network data in order to identify deviations from the expected network traffic behavior, which may constitute an indication of risk. In this regard, ENTRUST envisions the use of AI-based techniques to identify abnormalities such as spikes or prolonged increased network traffic loads, which may indicate activity by a malicious party.
MUDs and Certificates of Conformity	The Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) has been standardized within the scope of the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) and enables manufacturers to establish network behavior profiles for their devices, built around a set of policies. ENTRUST builds upon this construct in order to dictate the actions that need to be taken for providing operational assurance during runtime, and envisions the dynamic updating of the Protection Profiles of the CMDs for the mitigation of newly identified threats and vulnerabilities.

3.2 Research Pillars and Current State-of-the-Art

Having identified the core research pillars to be targeted by ENTRUST, in the following Sections, we provide a state-of-the-art analysis for each of these pillars, and we identify the positioning of ENTRUST within the research landscape. These are essentially the areas where ENTRUST aims to provide significant contributions in the context of securing CMDs operating within large-scale medical organizations and will provide the basis for the research activities to be carried out throughout the lifecycle of the project.

3.2.1 Formal Verification Models to Capture the Secure Device Lifecycle

Formal verification for securing the lifecycle of the CMD is paramount to ensuring robust security for the ENTRUST framework with regard to the enrolment phase and the key derivation process. Formal verification provides a mathematically rigorous approach to systematically identify any vulnerabilities and flaws within the software and hardware components used for the ENTRUST framework. Using this verification model, manufacturers not only comply with stringent regulatory standards, but also increase the reliance against cyber security threats and enhance the long-term reliability of CMD. Furthermore, this approach follows the security by design principle. The advantages of this verification model can also be seen in practice, where well-established protocols have been formally modelled and verified which revealed vulnerabilities.

In the context of ENTRUST, formally verified trust models are defined for the services that a CMD will provide (or use) throughout its lifecycle for achieving the security, privacy, and trust requirements. Relevant concepts in these models are the security material that will be created and used (e.g., keys, crypto functions) and the security protocols that will support secure onboarding, communication, and update of devices.

Rahman et al. [12] define a generic model of an IoT device lifecycle (Figure 4:).

Figure 4: Generic model of IoT device lifecycle (from [12])

In this model, the installation and commissioning stage prepares the device for operation and secure communication in a network. The bootstrapping activity is a process in which the device joins a network and includes steps for device authentication and authorization. During this stage, crypto keys may be created, and an agreement about the used security algorithms and protocols is established. They are used in the later stages, such as operation and update. During operation, the device executes its main services and applications. It is important that communication with other devices is secure and satisfies the formulated security requirements. In the update stage, the device can be reconfigured and can receive software and firmware updates. Again, it is important that this process is secure and guarantees that the updates come from a trusted source and their integrity is preserved during the process. Usually the activities of bootstrapping, communication during operation, and update follow dedicated protocols. These protocols will be subject to modelling and verification as part of task T3.1. More broadly, the design and analysis of the security-related aspects of an IoT device/service is part of the construction stage in Figure 4:.

In general, formal verification is the process of checking if a model of the behaviour of a given system satisfies certain properties. The model and the properties are specified in languages with clear formal semantics. Tools are used to perform the verification in an (semi-)automated way. The two main forms of verification are model checking and theorem proving. In model checking, the space of possible system executions is generated (possibly up to a certain bound) and then the properties are checked. In theorem proving the property is treated as a mathematical statement (theorem) that must be proven based on the available knowledge (system specification). Both approaches usually use formal notations that require specialized training for the users.

In recent years, significant research has been performed on the verification of security protocols resulting in several dedicated tools, ProVerif [13] and Tamarin [14] being the most prominent ones. In these tools, protocols are usually defined in applied pi-calculus where messages carry terms that represent cryptographic operations (hashing, random number generation, encryption, and decryption). Some of the commonly checked properties are confidentiality of certain data and guarantees for the order of certain events that result, for example, in proper authentication. Both model checking and theorem proving have been used for analysing security protocols. Figure 5: (originally given in [15]) shows a comparison among several popular protocol verification tools.

Tool	Unbound	Eq-thy	State	Equiv	Link
CPSA [45]	●	○	●	○	○
DEEPSPEC [31]	○	◐	●	●	○
F7 [13]	●	◐	●	○	●
Maude-NPA [49]	●	●	○	●	○
ProVerif [30]	●	◐	○	●	○
Scyther [41]	●	○	○	○	○
Tamarin [72]	●	●	●	●	○
Verifpal	●	◐	●	◐	◐

Figure 5: Comparison of tools for symbolic security analysis (from [15])

We observe that the tools perform differently on several commonly used criteria (unbounded execution incl. interleaving of protocol sessions, support of equational theory, mutable states, among others) and it may be necessary to use more than one tool to achieve high degree of confidence in the protocol definition.

Protocol verification tools use specialized tool-specific languages that may have a significant learning curve. Two recent works from the software modelling community address this problem. In [16], protocols are specified as scenarios expressed in UML sequence diagrams extended with variables and assignments. This style of specification follows the customary in the field ‘Alice-Bob’ notation. The model is then automatically transformed to ProVerif specification. This enables engineers to use a more friendly notation that can possibly be translated to the languages of more than one protocol verifier. The authors of [17] take a similar approach: a protocol for software update of IoT devices is expressed as a UML sequence diagram and then translated to a Verifpal model. Both works use a single protocol verifier in the background although multiple translations are technically feasible. These works do not define a language for specifying the properties to be checked, some commonly encountered properties are assumed instead. Furthermore, there is no translation from the protocol verifier’s feedback (in case of property violation) back to the source model.

Beaulaton et al. [18] focus on modeling the interactions among the participants in an IoT system (devices, users, attacker) by explicitly defining the data they exchange and the possibility for data leaks. The models are then used to analyze if a certain attack scenario can succeed by checking, for example, if a password or ID can leak and become known to an attacker. The checks are performed by simulation or by using automated probabilistic reasoning. This work also allows an explicit specification of an attack.

It has to be stated that even if it is shown by means of formal verification that a model satisfies certain properties, there is still no guarantee that these properties are preserved in the actual software implementation. Techniques like model-based testing and runtime verification are applicable in this case. The models created at design time can be used for automatically deriving

test cases. In the area of security testing, fuzz testing is of particular interest for checking how an implementation handles malformed or unexpected inputs. These techniques, they are tightly bonded with threat modelling and SW verification, which will be discussed in the following subsection.

Runtime verification (or monitoring) is a dynamic analysis technique in which a property is checked over observations collected during system execution (in contrast to model checking where all possible executions are explored). The observations can be a series of inputs and outputs of the system (e.g., sent and received messages, service requests) or information collected and logged from the system internal state (e.g., data values, dataflow, and control flow information). Runtime verification is applicable in cases where design time formal verification is computationally infeasible (due to state space explosion), in highly dynamic and unpredictable environments, and in situations where there is lack of information to perform sound design time analysis.

In an early work, Bauer and Jurjens [19] show how runtime verification can be applied to check Java implementation of the SSL protocol. Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) is used to specify the properties to be monitored. The implementation is instrumented in order to provide for the observations used to evaluate the properties. Vella et al. [20] outline a general approach for runtime verification in the context of TEE (Trusted Execution Environment). In this approach state machines are used to specify the expected behavior of the protocol implementation.

Apart from verifying the behavior of the security aspects of an IoT device, the regular services and applications can also be a subject of modeling and verification. In [21], Bonfanti et al. present a literature review of the formal methods used for medical software systems. A multitude of approaches, languages and tools are identified. We observe that the ways in which the model of the system is defined revolves around state-based notations. The choice of the verification approach and tool depends on the properties to be verified.

Several languages are proposed to model different aspects of an IoT device or IoT system. ThingML [22] is a domain-specific language for modeling IoT devices accompanied by code generators for multiple target implementation platforms. This language, however, does not consider security aspects explicitly. ASTo [23] is a tool (based on a DSL) that allows security analysis of IoT systems. Still, it misses behavior specification constructs that are present in ThingML.

We are currently not aware of a language/approach that considers explicitly the concept of trust and can depict all trust-related aspects in an IoT device (spanning the software and hardware layers). In the context of ENTRUST, we need a comprehensive way to depict trust in IoT device services that include models of the behavior, specification of the security requirements and models of threats/attacks. Using notations that reflect the concepts in the domain and are friendly to the engineers is a promising direction instead of directly using the languages of the verification tools.

3.2.2 Software Verification Through Code Analysis Techniques and Discussion on the Expansion of Verification Capabilities During Runtime Operation

Software verification is an essential aspect of the software development process, tasked with ensuring that software systems not only fulfil their specified functions, but also maintain high standards of reliability, security, and freedom from vulnerabilities. This verification becomes increasingly significant in an era where digital systems play a critical role in essential operations across various industries and sectors. The reliability and security of software are not just a matter of functionality, but also a matter of trust and safety for users and stakeholders.

By employing a combination of these code analysis techniques, developers and testers can achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the software's quality. This multifaceted approach allows for the early identification and rectification of issues, making it a more cost-effective and time-efficient practice. The goal is to enhance the overall quality of the software product, ensuring it is robust, secure, and reliable, thereby boosting user trust and satisfaction.

Furthermore, in a landscape where software is often subject to regulatory compliance, these verification methods play a crucial role in ensuring that software products adhere to industry standards and legal requirements. This is particularly important in sectors like finance, healthcare, and telecommunications, where software failure can have significant legal and financial repercussions.

By using multiple code analysis techniques, we aim provide results that are more comprehensive, thus providing a way of increasing the quality to of the software product.

3.2.2.1 Definitions for Key Terms

This section is dedicated to the definition of key terms that will be used in the following in the context of the state-of-the-art analysis in the domain of software verification:

- **Formal methods** are mathematical techniques that are used to verify, in a rigorous way, the correctness of computer software [24].
- **Symbolic execution** is a technique to check if a propriety, such as an exception, e.g., null pointer, or security issues, e.g., the nonexistence of a backdoor, can be violated by exploring all execution paths [25].
- **Static analysis** is a technique of checking the source code or the binary, without the execution of the software, to check for security issues [26].
- **Fuzz testing** is a technique to test software applications by providing random, malformed, or unexpected inputs to trigger crashes and discover security issues [27].
- **Runtime verification** is a paradigm that is based on the process of monitoring a system and comparing the real input with the desired one [28].

3.2.2.2 Formal Methods

In the following, we provide further information on the state-of-the-art in various formal verification methods available in the literature.

3.2.2.2.1 Deductive Verification

Deductive verification is a method that analyses the program using symbolic execution or weakest preconditions. Its strength is that it can handle complex specifications and perform modular verification, but at the downside of being limited in automation area, by needing interactive proofs [24]. Examples of platforms that are using deductive verification include Frama-C, an open-source platform designed for the verification of C applications.

3.2.2.2.2 Design by Refinement

Design by refinement is a method of developing formally verified software by using successive refinements of a sequence of state machines [24]. This technique is well-suited for developing verified software from scratch but requires a significant effort in specification.

3.2.2.2.3 Proof Assistants

Proof assistants are interactive tools used to produce reliable proofs of theorems [24]. These tools employ expressive logic and check every proof with a small, trusted core, reducing the possibility of errors. Proof assistants have been used to prove complex correctness properties of software,

such as the CompCert certified C compiler, which was used to prove equivalence between a source code and its compiled version, providing a strong example of functional correctness.

3.2.2.2.4 Model Checking

Model checking is an automatic verification method that checks specifications on finite-state models of hardware or software systems by exhaustive exploration [24]. The benefits of model checking include achieving soundness and completeness, the use of temporal logic to express rich specifications, and the ability to check concurrent models. Recently, software model checking has targeted the direct verification of source code without requiring a hand-crafted model, but trade-offs had to be made to sidestep the intractability of an exhaustive exploration of the state space. Bounded model checking limits exploration to execution traces of fixed length, while counterexample-guided abstraction refinement (CEGAR) automatically extracts an abstract model from the source code based on a finite set of predicates, which is then verified using model checking.

3.2.2.2.5 Formal Methods in Machine Learning

The main differences between machine learning software and traditional software arise from the non-deterministic nature of the machine learning model training phase and the probabilistic guarantees provided by trained models [24]. Formal verification methods need to adapt to these differences in order to ensure the safe development and deployment of machine learning software in safety-critical applications. Most formal verification methods proposed so far in the literature apply to trained machine learning models, while only a few are dedicated to the data preparation and model training phases.

An example is Reluplex [29], an SMT solver for verifying safety properties of feed-forward fully connected neural networks with ReLU activations. The approach is based on the simplex algorithm and extends it to support ReLU constraints, maintaining a value assignment for all variables even if some constraints are violated. Reluplex fixes violated constraints at each step, splitting ReLU constraints into two cases to ensure convergence. The approach was applied to the verification of the ACAS Xu neural networks for the next-generation airborne collision avoidance system, consisting of six hidden layers with 300 neurons each, and required several hours to perform the verification. The derivation rules can be seen in Figure 6:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{Pivot}_1 \quad \frac{x_i \in \mathcal{B}, \quad \alpha(x_i) < l(x_i), \quad x_j \in \text{slack}^+(x_i)}{T := \text{pivot}(T, i, j), \quad \mathcal{B} := \mathcal{B} \cup \{x_j\} \setminus \{x_i\}} \\
 \text{Pivot}_2 \quad \frac{x_i \in \mathcal{B}, \quad \alpha(x_i) > u(x_i), \quad x_j \in \text{slack}^-(x_i)}{T := \text{pivot}(T, i, j), \quad \mathcal{B} := \mathcal{B} \cup \{x_j\} \setminus \{x_i\}} \\
 \text{Update} \quad \frac{x_j \notin \mathcal{B}, \quad \alpha(x_j) < l(x_j) \vee \alpha(x_j) > u(x_j), \quad l(x_j) \leq \alpha(x_j) + \delta \leq u(x_j)}{\alpha := \text{update}(\alpha, x_j, \delta)} \\
 \text{Failure} \quad \frac{x_i \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (\alpha(x_i) < l(x_i) \wedge \text{slack}^+(x_i) = \emptyset) \vee (\alpha(x_i) > u(x_i) \wedge \text{slack}^-(x_i) = \emptyset)}{\text{UNSAT}} \\
 \text{Success} \quad \frac{\forall x_i \in \mathcal{X}. \quad l(x_i) \leq \alpha(x_i) \leq u(x_i)}{\text{SAT}}
 \end{array}$$

Figure 6: Derivation rules for the abstract simplex algorithm (from [29])

3.2.2.3 Symbolic Execution

Symbolic execution has 3 basic building blocks: execution, symbolic backend, and forking/scheduling [30]:

- In the **execution module**, the program under test is executed, and the system produces symbolic expressions representing the computations. This block is essential for reasoning about the program. There are two types of execution: IR-based and IR-less execution.
- In the **symbolic backend module**, the sole purpose of describing computations symbolically is to reason about them. The symbolic backend comprises the components involved in the reasoning process, such as an SMT solver and pre-processing techniques.
- In the **forking and scheduling module**, some symbolic execution implementations execute the program only once and generate new program inputs based on that single execution, while others manage multiple executions of the program under test along different paths by forking the execution at branch points in the program and prioritizing them according to some search strategy.

SYMCC is an implementation of compiler-based symbolic execution built on top of the LLVM compiler framework. It includes a custom compiler pass written from scratch to insert code for symbolic handling into the LLVM bitcode. It also provides a thin wrapper around the Z3 SMT solver and optional integration with the QSYM backend. Direct embedding yields significant improvements in the execution speed of the target programs, outperforming current approaches by a large margin. The evaluation showed that faster execution accelerates the analysis at large and increases the chances of bug discovery, leading to the discovery of two high-impact vulnerabilities in a heavily tested library. Using a compiler to insert symbolic handling into target programs combines the advantages of IR-based and IR-less symbolic execution. SYMCC is architecture-independent and can support various programming languages with little implementation effort while still being considerably faster than current IR-less techniques.

3.2.2.4 Static Analysis

Static analysis has been applied to a large range of areas, the most recent focus being on smart contracts [26] and on IoT [31].

Static analysis tools such as Securify, SmartCheck, Solhint, Vandal, and EtherTrust analyze code without executing it to detect issues in smart contracts. They operate by translating the code to an intermediate representation and matching it against predefined patterns to identify potential security, functional, operational, and development issues. GASPER and GasReduce use static analysis to detect potential optimizations in contracts, with a focus on dead code and loop optimizations.

Slither is an open-source static analysis framework for smart contracts that provides rich information about contracts. It uses SlithIR, an intermediate representation designed for practical static analysis on Solidity code, and is the only platform that can find bugs, suggest code optimizations, and increase code understanding for a given contract. Slither outperforms other state-of-the-art tools in terms of performance, robustness, and accuracy in finding reentrancy bugs.

Regarding IoT, [31] presents a theoretical and practical proof of the hypothesis that machine learning can improve static analysis of Internet of Things (IoT) systems. The theoretical proof involves a generalized analytical model that describes the execution of each SA stage and the solution of ML tasks on each stage, which serves as the basis for practical implementations of intelligent SA algorithms. The practical proof involves a review of existing works applicable to the stages of SA of IoT systems from the perspective of the tasks solved by ML, which is summarized

in a matrix that substantiates the hypothesis from a practical point of view. The resulting models linking SA and ML allow designing methodological solutions in the interest of providing information security of complex IoT systems. A high-level overview of this can be seen in Figure 7: [31].

Figure 7: Static analysis using machine learning (from [31])

3.2.2.5 Fuzz Testing

The recent research is focusing on a testing classic application [27], but also on testing machine learning models [32].

[27] describes a set of fuzzing tools consisting of fuzz, ptjig, and testing scripts. Fuzz generates random characters, which can be used as input to utilities. It offers options to control the length of generated data, the type of characters, and the delay between each character. Ptyjig provides input to utilities that require input from a terminal. Testing scripts automate the process of generating trace data and provide more control over how utilities are tested. The scripts generate random files of different sizes, characters, and newline categories. The run.py script runs each utility program, sets up the test files as input, and stores the results. The configuration file specifies the list of utilities to be tested, the options to pass to them, and how the test input will be provided.

DeepHunter is a coverage-guided fuzz testing framework for deep neural networks (DNNs) [32]. It includes a metamorphic mutation strategy for image generation and a frequency-aware seed selection strategy. It is designed to be extensible, allowing for new testing criteria, seed selection strategies, and mutation strategies to be easily implemented. DeepHunter integrates 5 testing criteria and 4 seed selection strategies and is leveraged to answer research questions on metamorphic mutation, coverage, error detection, and platform migration. Its workflow can be seen in Figure 8:

Figure 8: DeepHunter workflow (from [32])

3.2.2.6 Runtime Verification

Runtime verification has been applied to a large range of domains, including distributed systems, hybrid systems, hardware-based monitoring, security and privacy, transactional systems, contracts, and policies, and monitoring large and unreliable traces [28].

Regarding distributed systems, runtime verification can help address the difficulties in assessing system correctness by offering mechanisms for correctness analysis after a system is deployed. This is particularly useful in detecting latent bugs that reveal themselves once the system is in operation. In the domain of Distributed and Decentralized Runtime Verification (DDR), challenges arise in monitoring distributed systems and in using distributed systems for monitoring.

Hardware-supported runtime verification (HRV) has the potential to significantly enhance the reliability of complex systems by providing continuous, non-intrusive, and detailed observations of system behavior. HRV solutions can leverage hardware description languages and reconfigurable hardware for observability, feasibility, expressiveness, and adaptability. These solutions can also be used for performance monitoring. Different approaches to HRV may vary in their methodologies, goals, and target system-induced limitations. The use of external or on-system hardware, the events of interest being monitored, the connectivity of the monitor to the system, and the level of instrumentation are all dependent on the characteristics of the system being monitored and the goals of the monitoring process.

Regarding cybersecurity, the exponential growth in the availability of large datasets has led to new opportunities for understanding nature and society but has also created challenges related to privacy and security. With the increasing complexity of interactions between applications and services, it is difficult to track and understand what personal data is being accessed and how it is being used. While static solutions can provide partial protection, the need for runtime monitoring, verification, and enforcement has become crucial against security and privacy threats, such as botnets, distributed denial-of-service attacks (DDoS), hacking, malware, pharming, phishing, ransomware, spam, and attacks that leak private information.

Regarding contracts, formal language is necessary to capture deontic notions, temporal and dynamic aspects, and real-time issues, in order to specify and analyze them using techniques such as model checking and runtime verification. Policies which prescribe behavior can also be seen as contracts. For privacy policies in Online Social Networks (OSN), epistemic logic is a suitable formalism to reason about who should and should not access certain information and perform certain actions.

3.2.2.7 Future Work

Runtime verification faces several research gaps and challenges that require further exploration [28]. In the distributed system domain, distributed specifications are limited by the partial ordering of distributed events and the lack of a global system view, making the search for expressive and tractable languages for distributed systems an important goal. The decomposition, placement, and control of monitors across multiple execution nodes have a significant impact on overheads, communication delay, and security. It is crucial to develop techniques that strike a balance between performance and confidentiality. Restricted observability, due to security and confidentiality constraints, further limits the monitorable specifications in practice. Investigating techniques to handle obfuscated or removed event data while preserving confidentiality is necessary. Fault tolerance is another crucial aspect to be addressed, requiring the development of a theory to determine guarantees for monitoring algorithms and specifications in the presence of failures. Ensuring deterministic analysis and strong eventual consistency or observational verdict determinism despite inherent non-deterministic computation is a challenge that demands further research.

Regarding hardware, observability is a fundamental concern; determining which hardware entities should be instrumented to guarantee the required level of observability and how to probe them at different levels of abstraction remains an open question. Ensuring the effectiveness of hardware-based probing while conforming to SWaP (Size, Weight, and Power) constraints is crucial to

maintain a balance between capturing all events of interest and hardware instrumentation complexity. Feasibility and flexibility in handling potentially high volumes of trace data is another challenge. This involves confining observed events of interest and employing advanced compression, pre-processing, and runtime verification techniques to reduce the gap between trace data output and processing capabilities. Mapping formal specifications of system properties into actual observing and monitoring actions with minimal and highly effective hardware/software probing components is essential. Supporting flexible observation and monitoring can enable the integration of runtime verification techniques in (self-)adaptable and reconfigurable systems. Hybrid approaches for observability, which combine software-based instrumentation with hardware-based observability, are promising for capturing program execution flows and timing, observing fine-grained data, and monitoring bulk data without the need for special-purpose software hooks. Lastly, extending hardware-based observability to advanced system architectures, such as processor and memory virtualization, time- and space-partitioning, and interpreted languages running on virtual machines, is an area that warrants further research.

Regarding security and privacy, hybrid information flow monitoring, which combines static and dynamic analysis, is crucial for achieving an efficient and permissive mechanism that can handle real programs and security policies. Monitoring declassification and quantitative information flow, while difficult, is another unresolved challenge. Developing a generic language for information flow security and studying its monitoring algorithms and limitations will enable the encompassing of various security policies, including hyperproperties. Browser extensions pose a challenge in preventing malicious extensions from exposing private information. Implementing robust runtime enforcement mechanisms might require invasive modifications to the browser core. Defining security and privacy policy languages to address known threats and employing runtime monitoring techniques for detecting threats are essential. This also involves learning policies at runtime, improving their precision using feedback from runtime.

3.2.3 Threat Modelling for Modelling Device Context

3.2.3.1 Introduction

Threat modeling in the device context is an essential aspect of modern cybersecurity, focusing on understanding and mitigating risks in a world increasingly dominated by interconnected devices. This process involves identifying potential threats to a device, assessing the risks these threats pose, and devising strategies to counteract or mitigate them. In the context of devices, this means considering various factors such as the device's operating environment, the data it handles, its connectivity, and the potential vulnerabilities inherent in its hardware and software. By comprehending the distinct context in which a device functions, security experts are better equipped to foresee and prepare for various security threats. This includes anticipating network-based attacks, software vulnerabilities, and other potential risks. Having this deep understanding allows for the development of more efficient defense strategies. These strategies are not just reactive but proactive, enabling professionals to prioritize risks based on their severity and likelihood. As a result, organizations can allocate their resources more effectively, focusing on the most critical threats first. This risk prioritization approach not only enhances the overall security posture but also proves to be more cost-effective and pragmatic in the long run. It ensures that security measures are aligned with the specific needs and vulnerabilities of the system, leading to a more robust and resilient security infrastructure.

This state of the art starts with definitions for key terms, then it's followed by the presentation of the most used threat modelling methodologies, and it ends with a comparison regarding the strengths and the weaknesses of each methodology.

3.2.3.1.1 Definitions for Key Terms

Threat Modelling (TM) is the process that identifies security vulnerabilities and their risks, to prevent or eliminate the negative impact that those could have in case a malicious actor would use them [33] [34].

A **threat agent** is a factor that can initiate an attack, be it a human, a technical one, e.g., technology, or an environmental one [33].

An **Advanced Persistent Threat (APT)** is a malicious group that is having well-funded resources, that infiltrates into computer systems and remain undetected for an extended period [33]. The attacks conducted by such organizations are characterized by a long information gathering phase and by sophisticated planned attacks [35].

An **Indicator of Compromise (IoC)** is an action that has been attributed to a malicious actor. These can be used to gather higher-level intelligence regarding an adversary such as its **Tactics, Techniques and Procedures (TTP)** that can be further used to describe the behaviour of the attacker [33].

The collected threat intelligence (TI) can be divided into the following categories [33]:

1. Strategic – High level information, relevant to the executives
2. Operational – Information relevant to security professionals, such as pen-testers, defenders, and incident response team
3. Technical – Information relevant to technical professionals
4. Tactical – Information that is analyzed after an attack already happened.

The same authors mention how the collected TI can be also divided by the structure of the data:

1. Structured TI – Information from reputable sources that can be ingested automatically with ease.
2. Unstructured TI – Information that requires manual analysis, from sources like reports or websites.

3.2.3.2 Threat Modelling Methodologies and Tools

In this section we are presenting the most used threat modelling methodologies. In the summary section we compare presented methodologies, by showcasing the unique characteristics of each. Based on these characteristics, we have decided that the most suitable methodology for ENTRUST is TARA.

3.2.3.2.1 Data Flow Diagram

A Data Flow Diagram (DFG) is a graphical way to represent how a system is functioning by using abstractions of the inputs, processes, and outputs [33] [36]. It is a simple way of modelling threats, and it can be a good choice if members of the threat modelling team are not trained to use UML [37]. The main drawback of using such a strategy is that making a DFG is time consuming and it shouldn't be use as the only solution to model threats [33]. An example of such a diagram can be seen in Figure 9:.

Figure 9: Data Flow Diagram (from [36])

3.2.3.2.2 STRIDE

Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Denial of Service and Elevation of Privilege (STRIDE) is a threat modelling strategy that is dividing threat into their explicit type [33] [34].

This model can be automated using other tools, e.g., Microsoft Secure Development Lifecycle (SDL) [38], but it doesn't identify specific attack vectors.

STRIDE has been previously applied to web applications [34] using the following mappings:

- Spoofing – Client could use brute-force or login using stolen credentials.
- Tampering – SQL database could be modified.
- Repudiation – Clients could give false information.
- Denial of Service – Application being overwhelmed with requests or by large amounts of data.
- Elevation of Privilege – Unauthorized clients could run queries.

A STRIDE model for a basic web application can be seen in Figure 10:.

Figure 10: STRIDE model for a basic web architecture [34]

3.2.3.2.3 TARA

Threat Agent Risk Assessment (TARA) is a threat modelling approach, particularly popular in the automotive industry, that focuses on evaluating the risks that different threat actors could pose.

The TARA framework is based on five principles:

1. **Threat Identification:** Recognizing potential system threats.
2. **Threat Agent Identification:** Determining potential threat actors.
3. **Risk Determination:** Assessing risk from each identified threat actor.
4. **Risk Evaluation:** Comparing risks against acceptance criteria for prioritization.
5. **Countermeasure Development:** Formulating strategies to reduce risks.

This is an iterative strategy, requiring organizations to continually update their understanding of the threat landscape.

While being a formal method, it offers flexibility to be visualized through graphical models such as DFD.

3.2.3.2.4 Attack Trees

Attack trees are conceptual diagrams inspired by the tree data structure. This strategy decomposes the attacker’s goal into multiple sub-goals, using child-nodes, that the malicious actor must achieve before moving to the next level of the attack, using parent-nodes [33].

Such a model was applied for representing attacks against web applications, with a focus on injection attacks [34], but also for testing the security of Internet of Things (IOT) systems from smart cities by combining trees with Priced Timed Automata [39], with a focus on password attacks, where the sub-goals of the attacker could be social-engineering or the usage of a key-logger.

The representations of these two can be found in Figure 3 Attack tree model for SQLi attack [34]) and in Figure 11:.

Figure 11: Attack tree model for SQLi attack [34]

Figure 12: Priced Timed Automata using trees [39]

3.2.3.2.5 Mathematical models

Threat modelling uses mathematical models to detect malicious behaviour via statistics. The common approach is by converting attacking stages into states of a Markov Chain, for threats that require certain previous conditions that an attacker needs to meet to advance, by using game theory, to collect information of deceptive APTs or by doing behavioural analysis on a compromised system [33].

The Markov chain model has been used in the healthcare industry to model threats of the medical devices and on their edge network [40]. The authors focused on both device level vulnerability, e.g., weak passwords, command injection, web interface issues, and network level vulnerability, e.g., insecure network services, unencrypted services, insecure cloud. In this model, the attacker needs to go from a safe state to a threat state, to an attack state. If countermeasures are implemented, the attacker may either not advance or to a previous state. A high-level representation of the Markov chain can be seen in Figure 13:.

Figure 13: Markov chain with countermeasures [40]

3.2.3.2.6 Kill Chain

Kill chain is a strategy inspired by ways to model threats in military environments, made by European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA) [33]. The goal of this model is to identify the attacker at different phases and to develop countermeasures [34]. The cyber kill chain has 7 phases:

1. **Reconnaissance** – A planning phase, characterized by the data collection about a target.
2. **Weaponize** – Attacker is using the gathered data to prepare an attack.
3. **Delivery** – Target is interacting with the malicious payload.
4. **Exploitation** – Threat actor gains access to the victim.
5. **Installation** – Attacker gains persistence, e.g., via backdoors.
6. **Command and Control (C2)** – Threat actor can remote control the target.
7. **Actions on Objectives (AOO)** – Malicious actor achieves the major goal.

This kind of model has been applied to ransomware attacks to assess the potential attack vectors by providing a taxonomy of ransomware features [41]. Such a model can be helpful when analysing attacks and when one wants to build an intrusion detection system (IDS). The taxonomy can be seen in Figure 6 Kill chain of a ransomware.

Such threat modelling was also applied for web applications [34], but the model was inferior to the other methods since different attacks were considered as one because the same process was followed. Author also found that Trike modelling tool wasn't appropriate since it didn't highlight all phases of the Kill Chain.

Figure 14: Kill chain of a ransomware [41]

3.2.3.2.7 Adversarial Tactics, Techniques & Common Knowledge (ATT&CK)

Adversarial Tactics, techniques & Common Knowledge (ATT&CK) is a threat modelling framework developed by MITRE [33]. It represents knowledge regarding real-world observations that is divided into 12 adversary tactics, that indicate threat actor tactical objectives, e.g., initial access, execution, persistence, and adversary techniques, that are the specific methods that the attacker can use, e.g., spear phishing, user execution, keychain [42]. This methodology can use security incidents to gather TTP, that can be furthered be sent to a machine learning algorithm [33] The same authors mention that this strategy can be used even if a dataset contains incomplete information.

ATT&CK has been applied to the Ukraine power grid attack of 2015 and to Cayman National Bank cyber heist of 2016 using enterpriseLang [42] It was found that this method was effective to help enterprises in decision making regarding attack scenarios. A simulation of the Ukraine attack can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Ukraine cyber-attack simulation [42]

3.2.3.2.8 Combined Models

To leverage each model's strengths while minimizing weaknesses, multiple threat models can be used [33]. Such a strategy was used to model attacks of the APT known as Fancy Bear [43] in which the author combined Kill Chain with the ATT&CK to create a more comprehensive framework. By combining them, the United Kill Chain model can provide tactics and techniques specific to a threat actor by identifying the stages of an attack using Kill Chain, and then applying ATT&CK to identify how the malicious actor is operating at each stage.

3.2.3.3 Summary

In Table 10 is presented a summary regarding the presented threat modelling methodologies and in Table 11 is presented the summary of their weaknesses. The unique characteristics of TARA, such as mapping exploits against vulnerable systems and environment to attack vectors, made it the most suitable decision regarding what threat modelling methodology should be used by ENTRUST.

Table 10: Threat modelling methodologies weaknesses and advantages [33]

Threat modelling methodologies weaknesses and advantages	DFD	STRIDE	Attack Trees	Mathematical modelling	Kill Chain	ATT&CK	TARA
Usage with STIX	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Can automate TM process	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No

Can be combined with other threat models	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Maps exploits against vulnerable systems & environment to attack vectors	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Easy to use	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
Extensible/Flexible	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
High Maturity	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	
Map defensive controls or countermeasures	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Prioritises Threats	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Uses one or many threat catalogues	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes

Table 11: Threat modelling methodologies weaknesses

Weakness	DFD	STRIDE	Attack Trees	Mathematical modelling	Kill Chain	ATT&CK	TARA
Challenging map attacks (TTP's) to environment (data, configurations, vulnerabilities)	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
Has trouble scaling to large environments	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Identifies high level details not specific attack details	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No
Labor intensive or time consuming to develop and maintain	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes

3.2.3.4 Future work

[33] is focused on the identification of research gaps in automation and intelligence extraction, which can be summarized as follows:

- Regarding automation, the authors mention the need to apply machine learning to threat modelling. There is research needed also needed regarding systems that can consume data to predict unknown threats.
- Regarding intelligence extraction, there is a need to identify ways of getting data from threat repositories, by creating a framework to analyse data and model collectively to test if a system has been compromised.

3.2.4 Trust Assessment Based on Subjective Logic and Properties to be Used as Runtime Trust Indicators to Construct Modular Protection Profiles for CMDs

In general, *Trust Assessment* refers to the methodology employed by a security framework that entails the collection and analysis of various types of data, in order to make a decision on the level of trust in the components comprising the system, as well as the system as a whole. In this regard, several Trust Assessment approaches have been proposed in the literature with regard to the types of information collected, the conversion of this information into statements that provide insight into the trust level of systems or components, and the extraction of trust decisions based on these statements. In the following, we provide a state-of-the-art analysis on Trust Assessment methodologies available in the literature, and we afterwards provide the reasoning behind the selection of the **Subjective Logic** method in the context of ENTRUST.

One decision logic approach that has been proposed in the literature is **Probabilistic Logic**, which is based on the observation that, in practice, it is impossible to determine with absolute certainty whether a given proposition is true or false. Specifically, this method relies on probability calculus in order to assign argument probabilities in the range $[0,1]$, thus allowing propositions to be partially true. One possible approach that aims to handle the concept of “degrees of truth” is **Fuzzy Logic**, which has been considered as a formal trust metric where vagueness and uncertainty are incorporated into the value of a variable [44]. Specifically, the truth value of a variable may be any real number between 0 and 1 (as opposed to **Boolean Logic**, where the truth value of variables may only be either 0 or 1 [45]). One of the most well-known fuzzy systems in the literature is **Mamdani’s rule-based system** [46], which uses the following rules:

- 1 **Fuzzify all input values** into fuzzy membership functions.
- 2 **Execute IF-THEN rules** that map input or computed truth values to desired output functions.
- 3 **Defuzzify the fuzzy output functions** in order to get a continuous variable from fuzzy truth values.

During the fuzzification process, numerical inputs of a system are assigned to fuzzy sets with some degree of membership between 0 and 1, where the values 0 and 1 indicate that the value does not belong or belong to the fuzzy set, respectively. Any value between 0 and 1 represents the degree of probability that the value belongs to the set.

Another interpretation of the concept of probability is **Bayesian Probability**, which can be seen as an extension of probabilistic logic that enables reasoning with hypotheses. In this approach, a probability is assigned to a hypothesis, unlike a frequentist inference where a hypothesis is tested without being assigned a probability [47]. Therefore, in this approach, a **prior probability** is assigned to a hypothesis before any evidence is accounted for, and this probability is updated when new evidence becomes available through a method referred to as **Bayesian inference**. This process consists of three steps:

- 1 Represent all sources of uncertainty as **statistical random variables**.
- 2 Determine and assign a **prior probability distribution** to the random variables.
- 3 As more evidence is available, apply the **Bayes formula** [48] in order to update the probability distributions.

Another approach that provides a flexible theoretical framework for representing uncertain data and merging independent belief pieces of evidence collected from different agents is the **Dempster-Shafer Theory (DST)** [49] [50], also referred to as **evidence theory** or **theory of belief functions**, and can be seen as a generalization of the Bayesian probability. In the DST approach, the degree of belief is named **mass** and is represented as a belief function (as opposed

to a probability distribution, as in the Bayesian approach). A belief function maps degrees of belief (confidence/trust) for one question based on the subjective probabilities for related questions. Afterwards, **Dempster’s rule** is applied for combining such degrees of belief stemming from independent sources of evidence. This approach also applies a normalization that effectively redistributes conflicting belief masses to non-conflicting ones, thus eliminating any conflict between sources.

Subjective Logic (SL) [51] [52], as shown in Figure 16:, is a framework for artificial reasoning based on probabilistic logic and the aforementioned Dempster-Shafer theory of evidence [49] [50], from which it inherits the idea of explicit representation of ignorance and fusing various sources of evidence. In addition, the interpretation of an opinion is possible by mapping opinions into probability distributions through a Bayesian perspective. Two of the core properties of SL are that it inherently allows (i) **uncertainties representation** as part of the fundamental building block of SL, referred to as **subjective opinion**, and (ii) reasoning about the uncertainties through a process of **belief fusion** in which multiple **subjective opinions** are aggregated based on the selected fusion operator. Note that subjective opinions are the fundamental building blocks of SL, and represents the amount of uncertainty on the degree of truth about a proposition. The representation of a subjective opinion is a composite function consisting of belief masses, uncertainty mass, and base rate. These subjective opinions can be merged or aggregated into a single, collective opinion through belief fusion, where the resulting opinion represents the truth better than each opinion independently. Finally, the target application may require the fusion of subjective opinions on different properties, and depending on the specific application, a suitable operator of belief fusion with the considered properties is needed.

Figure 16: Subjective Logic Framework

As aforementioned, in the context of ENTRUST, we elected to employ **Subjective Logic** in the context of the Trust Assessment framework. This selection was made considering the properties and capabilities of each of the aforementioned approaches. Specifically, Binary Logic was excluded, as it is not capable of expressing probabilistic truth values. In addition, while Bayesian Probability incorporates past evidence through the prior consideration of the prior probability of a proposition, it is not able to consider subjective beliefs from multiple sources on the same proposition. This is not sufficient in the context of ENTRUST, where we rely on the collection of evidence from multiple sources in order to evaluate multiple CMD parameters. Therefore, among DST and SL, we observed that the use of Dempster’s rule is mathematically possible only when the belief masses of two different sources are not in total conflict. In addition, DST does not support and model the notion of trust transitivity, thus making it inefficient for performing trust assessment in complex networks such as the ones typically present in the types of large-scale medical organizations considered by ENTRUST, where the notion of referral and direct trust relationships are of paramount importance. Considering all the above, we have decided to employ the SL theory for trust assessment under uncertainties.

3.2.5 Digital Twins for Simulating Various Attack Vectors and Evaluating the Defined Security Policies and Mitigation Actions

In the context of ENTRUST, digital twinning techniques are utilized to simulate and emulate various attack vectors based on the real-time monitored system traces, in order to: (i) generate a scalable testbed, (ii) generate a digital representation of the deployed connected medical devices, safety-critical components, and services, and (iii) evaluate the compiled security (attestation) policies with regards to connected medical device attack resilience, fault tolerance and prediction of any unforeseen cyber threats. Several attack validations will be performed on a digital twin by simulating the monitored execution path (by collecting the runtime execution state of a device). The output of attack validations will be fed to the Risk Assessment engine to recalculate the risk quantification graph and the subsequent recommendation of any new policies or other mitigation actions.

Digital Twins (DTs) can be built for any living or non-living thing [53]. However, in our context, we focus DTs of the deployed connected medical devices and safety-critical components and services which we consider in the scope of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs). Several approaches have been proposed to implement the concept of digital twins under different terms [54]. Yue et al. [53] introduce a conceptual model for digital twins that includes the common concepts used in different digital twin approaches in the literature. They define *Physical Twin* as the central concept in their conceptual model. It represents the physical artifact for which a *Digital Twin* is built. In the context of ENTRUST, a physical twin can be a connected medical device, any safety-critical component of the device, or a software service running on the device. Figure 17 shows the part of the conceptual model (from Yue et al. [53]) including the concepts of digital twin, physical twin, and the relations between these two.

Figure 17 Part of the conceptual model for digital twin, physical twin, and their relations [53]

A physical twin performs one or more *physical processes* which require different treatments by the digital twin (e.g., critical processes need to be monitored by the digital twin). For instance, a physical process of a patient monitoring device could be a process of automatically alarming the doctor for patient's sudden heart activity increase. A *physical environment* contains all the environmental elements that impact the operation of the physical twin, e.g., everything in the

operating environment of the patient monitoring system (including the patient) characterized with factors such as patient's heart activity and temperature.

Another main concept of the conceptual model in Figure 18 is the *Digital Twin*, which is the digital, live replica of the physical twin. A *virtual environment* is the digital replica of a *physical environment*. A digital twin interacts with its virtual environment. A digital twin needs to be synchronized with its physical twin. This synchronization concept is represented by *Twining* in Figure 18. It has a synchronization rate (*twining rate*) and is achieved via *PT-To-DT Connection* (digital twin is updated with the information of physical twin) or *DT-To-PT Connection* (digital twin triggers some operations on the physical twin). In the context of ENTRUST, the digital twin of a connected medical device is updated with the traces of the runtime execution state of a device (i.e., *PT-To-DT Connection*). Several attack validations will be performed on a digital twin. The mitigation actions obtained from the output of the attack validation component might trigger the deployment of any software or firmware patches as defined in task T4.4 (*DT-To-PT Connection*). A human operator may perform the *DT-To-PT Connection*. The term Parameter in Figure 18 represents the information (e.g., execution state of a medical device) exchanged between the physical and digital twins. The *fidelity* of the digital twin depends on the number and accuracy of the information exchanged between the twins. With the low number of parameters and low parameter accuracy, the digital twin has a more abstraction but lower fidelity [53].

Figure 18: Part of the conceptual model characterizing digital twins [53]

Figure 18 shows part of the conceptual model characterizing digital twins. A human operator (*DT Human Operator*) can operate a digital twin (e.g., a human operator decides the software patches to trigger for the physical twin based on the output of our digital twin for attack validation). *DT Functionality Type* represents the functionalities a digital twin aims to achieve (e.g., what-if analysis, predictive maintenance, and data visualisation). For instance, the specific functionality of digital twins which we will develop in the context of ENTRUST will be attack validation as part

of dynamic trust assessment. Several technologies (*Technology* and *Technology Type* in Figure) such as machine learning and modelling and simulation techniques (e.g., Simulink and SysML) can be employed to support a digital twin achieving its functionalities. The maturity of a digital twin (*DT Maturity Level* in Figure) is by the achieved functionalities. In order to replicate complex physical twins, a digital twin may contain multiple digital twins in the same or different nature. In ENTRUST, we might have a digital twin of the connected medical device which is composed of multiple digital twins replicating different software components running on the device. A *Human-Machine Interface (HMI)* has an *HMI Type* and supports communication between humans and digital twins where fully autonomous digital twins are not feasible. Additional devices (*DT Device* in Figure 18) can be employed to improve the human-twin interface (e.g., virtual reality for manufacturing cyber-physical production system [55] or for multi-robot manufacturing cell commissioning [56]).

There are some works (e.g., [57] [58] [59] [60]) that study state-of-the-art techniques that focus on digital twins and security. For instance, De Benedictis et al. [57] study the literature from both digital twin for security (i.e., the digital twin technology is used to analyze and mitigate cyber-security risks affecting the system) and security for digital twin (i.e., digital twins are inherently exposed to security risks) perspectives for cyber-physical systems. Figure 18 gives a classification of the literature from these two perspectives.

3.2.5.1 Digital Twin for Security

The application of digital twins for security analysis and monitoring can be considered under the term *Cyber Digital Twin* [61] [62]. De Benedictis et al. [57] classify the digital twin applications for security as follows:

Digital Twin for Security-By-Design (Secure Design): De Benedictis et al. discuss using digital twins to detect vulnerabilities and identify unnecessary/unused or unprotected components and services (an attacker can exploit) at the design stage. For instance, Vielberth et al. [63] propose the use of digital twins to create testbeds that can be used to train analysts by simulating realistic scenarios without disrupting business operations.

Intrusion Detection: Digital twins can also be used to create intrusion detection systems (rather than using the real system to create it so that we can test the twin without disrupting the real system) to detect and counterattack behaviours that can damage a cyber-physical system [57] [58]. For instance, Eckhart et al. [62] implement a digital twin-based intrusion detection system without employing real-time data obtained through sensors. In addition, they implement an intrusion detection system using digital twins in replication mode to identify anomalies a real cyber physical system produces [64].

Hardware/Software Misconfiguration Detection: If a digital twin operates in a threat-free environment (isolated from malicious attacks), it can be used to detect manipulated hardware/software configurations of physical devices, e.g., by comparing the configurations of physical and digital twins [57].

Security Testing: Digital twins can be used as a medium to run security tests (e.g., for security assessments, security weakness reporting, and penetration testing) on digital replicas rather than on real systems. For instance, Xu et al. [65] propose a digital twin-based anomaly detection method, called ATTAIn, which takes advantage of both historical and real-time data of cyber-physical systems. They later provide another approach [66], named digital twin-based Anomaly deTeCtion wLth Curriculum lEarning (LATTICE), which extends ATTAIn by introducing curriculum learning to optimize its learning paradigm.

Improved Patch Management: Digital twins can be employed in order to analyze the impact of security patches and configuration changes on the overall system without testing individual devices in isolation or without the need for maintaining secondary systems for testing [57] [61].

Privacy and Legal Compliance Enforcement and Verification: Damjanovic-Behrendt [67] proposes a digital twin demonstrator for privacy enhancement in the automotive industry. The proposed method detects privacy concerns and reduces security risks which smart car drivers may experience through connected smart car services. It uses digital twins to simulate various scenarios that may happen during the operation of a smart car.

Digital Forensics: Digital twins can play a role in digital forensics that focuses on identifying, acquiring, processing, analysing, and reporting on data stored electronically.

Figure 19: Digital twins and security for cyber-physical systems [57]

3.2.5.2 Security for Digital Twin

As outlined by De Benedictis et al. [57], digital twins inherently expose security vulnerabilities, and security threats can be classified from security requirements and attack surfaces perspectives.

Security Requirements Perspective: Security for digital twins can be studied for *availability*, *accessibility*, *integrity*, and *confidentiality* requirements [57]. The interaction with the digital twin may create potential failures where the digital twin is unreachable, which causes disruptions in the operation of the physical twin (i.e., *availability*). Digital twins must be protected from unauthorized modification of data and operations to ensure that the physical twin is reliable and safe to operate with its digital twin (i.e., *integrity*). On the other hand, authorized access to facilities and system data in digital twins needs to be provided for the confidentiality of system data and operations (i.e., *confidentiality*).

Attack Surfaces Perspective: Threats to digital twins can also affect physical twins. For instance, side-channel attacks obtain information on physical devices by analyzing various physical parameters such as voltage and execution time. If the attacker captures the system data shared with the digital twin, he/she can use these data to extract information on the physical device (i.e., *physical layer perspective*). Common attacks and threats to communication technologies (e.g., *man-in-the-middle attack*, *denial of service*, *distributed denial of service*, *eavesdropping attack*, and *spoofing attack*) can also lead to security problems for the communication between digital and physical twins (i.e., *connectivity layer perspective*). On the other hand, various security attacks can directly target models, codes, and software components that form the digital twin (i.e., *digital layer perspective*). For instance, digital twins using machine learning for decision-making are vulnerable to security and privacy attacks [57] [68].

Blockchain for Digital Twins: Blockchain technology is a promising solution that can address security and privacy issues digital twins experience. It can be employed to enhance the trustworthiness of data sources and support secure data distribution and storage [57]. Blockchains provide tamper-proof and immutable features that can be used for secure data distribution to multiple entities through unalterable digital twin transactions (i.e., *digital twins data protection*). Using pseudo-names, blockchains also support the node privacy. On the other hand, having public addresses of blockchain users ensures *transparency and accountability*. We can also employ blockchains to track digital twin data (i.e., *data traceability*) and to avoid unauthorized access to digital twins (i.e., *access privileges of digital twins*).

3.2.6 Runtime Attestation to Monitor and Assess the Secure State of the CMD During Runtime

The main goal of ENTRUST is to design a novel runtime attestation technique to validate the secure state of the devices by attesting the correct execution behaviour as well as the communication patterns and their relationships, through cryptographically verifiable security proofs and efficient remote attestation. A customizable TC-based middleware will be responsible for interpreting the formally and cryptographically verified protection profiles (defined during the design phase) to achieve the required level of trustworthiness and provide verifiable evidence and strong levels of assurance by design.

ENTRUST will provide cryptographic protocols with different levels of assurance pertaining to data management and access, as well as to enable different levels of granularity in the access control to capture different roles of users of medical devices that need to showcase the necessary attributes and privileges for accessing the data. To this end, ENTRUST takes an attribute-based approach to data management, meaning that data access is determined based on the attributes that a medical device can exhibit in a verifiable manner. This is achieved through the issuance of

verifiable credentials that contribute to realizing proper access control using novel attribute-based cryptography, and the establishment of secure and authenticated communication channels between the users.

Therefore, the use of runtime verification will enable the connected medical devices to act as self-verifying systems providing themselves the required assurance claims without the need for a central authority ensuring continual quantitative verification during runtime. Based on the verifiable evidence, the mechanism will dynamically update the verified models according to real-time reliability parameters.

The aim of the Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) scheme is to ensure the verification of the correct configuration of an MD device before being allowed to join a healthcare network. CIV allows the creation of trust chains through the provision of zero-touch configuration functionalities which means that every medical device that wants to join a network should be able to provide verifiable evidence of the correctness and integrity of its configuration. ENTRUST framework guarantees that an MD can join a network only if it can prove to an external verifier, that it is in its “correct state” – without revealing any information about the value of their configuration.

While the ENTRUST Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) such as in [69], can attest to the correctness of the configuration state of a single medical device when joining the ENTRUST services, the issue arises in large-scale ecosystems considered in ENTRUST where the attestation of several medical devices separately is not efficient, as it requires a large amount of time and computational resources.

In the context of ENTRUST, medical devices are connected in a heterogeneous way based on their resources and capability of performing different levels of crypto operations. Therefore, there is a need for a type of attestation that addresses:

- Scalability, which means that it can attest the whole group of the connected medical devices based on the connection topology.
- Providing the attestation crypto operations that are suitable for different medical devices with different resources, namely gateways that are equipped with embedded hardware as a root of trust and IoT devices that are usually low-resource medical devices.

In the ENTRUST framework, we introduce an attestation enabler, that attests to the behavioural and/or configuration state of each device, as well as the group of connected MDs. One of these attestation schemes is the Swarm Attestation. Swarm Attestation [70] [71] is a scalable and distributed scheme that aims to attest to the correctness of a swarm of MDs simultaneously, in a more computationally efficient way than attesting each device separately. To this end, in ENTRUST, we will design a Swarm Attestation scheme for achieving Scalable Aggregate Network Attestation for establishing trust in complex MDs system of Systems (SoS). The design and release of this scheme will take a part of D4.2 [72], where we will define the security properties of the ENTRUST Swarm attestation and discuss how our scheme addresses the challenges of CMs in complex and dynamic swarms of MDs.

3.2.7 Self-Certification of CMDs Based on Runtime Evidence and the use of Verifiable Presentations to Expand the MUDs

Healthcare systems typically employ physical credentials (such as insurance card, patients' cards, and employee badges) to identify individual attributes. Individuals can choose where to store their physical credentials and decide to whom their credentials are disclosed. Similar to the physical credentials, a concept of digital credential referred to as Verifiable Credential (VC) was introduced in [73]. Similar to physical credentials, individuals can store their verifiable credentials in a device or in the cloud. Verifiable credentials are used for identification, authentication, and

authorization. An anonymous credential [74] is a data structure that certifies user attributes in a way that allows the user to prove the possession of the attributes without revealing any information about them. This is done through the issuance of Verifiable Presentations (VP) that contain proofs of knowledge that the hidden attributes were previously certified in the issued VC during the enrolment phase. This approach extends to the need for zero trust with regard to data access. In other words, when someone aims to access a set of data by disclosing a set of attributes, we cannot assume that the party responsible for the verification of these attributes is trustworthy. Therefore, a medical device should be able to disclose the particular set of attributes required in order to access the desired set of data (selective disclosure). To this end, the ENTRUST Secure Device Enrolment process includes the issuance of Verifiable Credentials (VCs) by a Certification Authority (CA), which contain the set of attributes of the device and are stored in the Trusted Component (TC) of the medical device. Afterward, when aiming to access a set of data that has been encrypted based on a set of attributes, the medical device is able to create a Verifiable Presentation (VP) as a subset of the issued VCs, only containing the required attributes. This approach provides the basis for the implementation of all the ENTRUST data access and management methods and algorithms and serves towards the core tenet of ENTRUST towards shifting trust to the “edge” and providing more control to the medical device with regards to the management of its own identity.

3.2.8 Use of PUFs as a Trusted Component for Enabling Attestation

3.2.8.1 PUFs Taxonomy and Implementations Considered in the Context of ENTRUST

One of the attractive approaches to digital keys for secure cryptographic protocols in IoT devices is the usage of Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) [75]. The inherent unclonability of the PUF cannot be controlled as it is based on multiple random parameters that are generated during the manufacturing process. Essentially, a PUF is the physical analogue of a one-way mathematical function, based on an unclonable, non-reproducible and complex physical mechanism. Combined with their deterministic operation, PUFs are appropriate for cryptographic key generation on demand, eliminating the need for key storage (no key-at-rest property). When an external stimulus (challenge) is applied to a PUF implementation, it will react with a corresponding response and this combination is called challenge-response pair (CRP). The PUF system contains uncontrollable random components, so when the challenge C applied to the PUF system it will react with these components in a way to produce unpredictable and random response R . These random components (e.g. a SRAM, a multiplexer, a sandblasted silica glass) and the inability to control their manufacturing process, constitutes a PUF system unpredictable, unique, and more important, physically unclonable [76].

PUFs have been widely used to provide essential security services, such as authentication and secret key generations, especially at constrained environments, such as IoT, where power consumption and security need to be balanced. In general, PUFs taxonomy includes two main categories, silicon, and non-silicon PUFs (Figure 20:), based on the fabrication process [77]. In the context of ENTRUST, the most appealing architectures of the aforementioned categories, in terms of implementation and resilience to tampering, modelling, and cloning attacks, respectively, are considered.

Figure 20: PUF taxonomy based on fabrication process [77] and the district PUF implementations considered in the context of ENTRUST.

It has to be noted that PUFs are also categorized based on their strength, i.e. the size of the available pool of the CRPs, to weak and strong PUFs. The strength of a PUF is generally determined by how the number of potential CRPs scales with the increasing PUF size. In general, if the number of CRPs supported by the PUF scales exponentially with its size, it is considered strong, while linear or polynomial increases typically correspond to weak PUFs. Exponential scaling produces exceptionally large CRP sets with the increasing device size [78]. In the context of ENTRUST, both PUF types are investigated, serving as a baseline for guaranteeing the HW and SW security design properties of MDs and provide the necessary cryptographic enablers, such as efficient CIV and efficient dynamic attestation mechanisms (secure identity management and cryptographic operations based on true random number generation).

Weak PUFs, support a relatively small number of CRPs, typically as a consequence of a low-order rate of scaling. This means that the full set of these pairs can be read from the device should an attacker gain physical access to the PUF for any given time. While it would not be possible to copy the physical PUF itself, with knowledge of the PUF’s CRPs an attacker could convincingly respond to query as if they still possessed the device—long after the device has left their possession. Weak PUFs can be used for secure key storage and entity authentication techniques, for instance, using the protocol featured in Figure 21: (a). However, for authentication purposes, the PUF must be examined in an environment where an authenticating party is present to ensure that the PUF itself is being evaluated [79].

Strong PUFs, on the other hand, scale in a manner as to support a much larger set of CRPs. The number of these pairs is so large, in fact, that even if an attacker has access to the PUF they cannot feasibly record them all. If in the manufacturing stage a sample of these CRPs is randomly taken, the chances that the attacker also recorded the response to the same challenge can be negligible. This results in a system where even if the attacker had access to the PUF at a certain point, only the user with physical access to the PUF at the time of the challenge can give the correct response and be authenticated. Additionally, such a large repertoire of CRPs means that each CRP can only be used once, if the application dictates such an operation. This protects against an attacker eavesdropping and can facilitate secure communication protocols using the PUF (for instance, with each CRP acting as one unit in a one-time pad) A simple example of a

strong PUF authentication protocol is featured in Figure 21(b). Strong PUFs can be used for authentication and key establishment [80] [81].

Figure 21: (a) A simple implementation of the weak PUF. The response of any attempted counterfeit would detectably differ compared to the response recorded of the genuine PUF. (b) A simple implementation of the strong PUF.

Here, even if the PUF is compromised an attacker would not know the relevant challenges to record, and an eavesdropper could never hear a usable challenge response pair.

3.2.8.2 PUF-based TC as a Root-of-Trust

CMDs, as IoT devices, are characterized by their constraints on processing power, memory and often battery-power. Also, MDs, in most of the cases, are delivered to the final user compliant with all medical and healthcare safety regulations and any interference at device-level is prohibited due to specific certification they possess. Thus, in order to provide security services at software and hardware level is very challenging. Additionally, providing security at hardware level is nowadays limited only to hardware security modules that perform a set of cryptographic operations (e.g. key management, key exchange, and encryption) at processor level. They are thus applicable only to modern and not to existing CMDs devices. An alternative solution towards that direction is the use of PUFs. PUFs can potentially provide an increased level of hardware security for MDs by introducing randomness in the key generation process of secure device onboarding, support the identity management as well as the cryptographic operations when the design of advanced attestation schemes is considered [82].

The most widely known types of PUFs, based on fabrication process are two: the optical (photonic) and the electronic. The former is considered a strong PUF [83], whereas the latter is classified as weak [84]. In the context of ENTRUST, both flavours will be thoroughly tested, tailored to the needs and challenges opposed by MDs per se, as well as by the technical and use case requirements. Special focus will be devoted to electronic PUFs (e-PUFs), also considering their size, their cost, and their implementation flexibility, whereas their optical counterparts (o-PUFs) will be also explored leveraging their exceptional security properties originated from probabilistic procedure involved for the key derivation from a high-entropy optical medium (e.g.

photonic chaotic cavity, disordered random optical scattering media etc.) commonly utilized. As regards to the silicon PUF considered here, a memory-based PUF was selected, whereas for the non-silicon PUF, a speckle imaging based optical PUF was considered.

Memory-based PUF category, focuses on the mismatches of memory elements at a start-up state that results in a random value. These PUFs are based on memory cells, which are commonly available in FPGA, unlike the delay-based PUFs which need special designs for different PUF types. The memory chip in circuits can be used to generate the signature and identity for these circuits [85]. A number of proposed memory-based PUF designs are shown in Figure 22: such as SRAM-PUF (S-PUF), butterfly PUF (B-PUF), SR latch PUF (SR-L-PUF), flip-flop PUF (FF-PUF), bistable ring PUF (BR-PUF) and MECCA PUF.

Figure 22: Memory-based PUFs: (a) S-PUF, (b) B-PUF, (c) SR-L-PUF, (d) FF-PUF, (e) BR-PUF, (f) MECCA PUF (M-PUF)

In the context of ENTRUST, SRAM-PUFs architectures are utilized, since they constitute the most prominent solution for IoT devices, thus can fulfil the requirements of MDs. As depicted in Figure 22: (a), the basic SRAM cell structure consisting of two cross-coupled inverters and access transistors. The initial state Q after a new power-up is determined by uncontrollable variations during manufacturing. The preferred power-up state is persistent and stable after manufacturing. On the other hand, in case of a small quantity of SRAM cells, they are unstable and show a random preference at every power-up. Taking both stable and unstable SRAM cells into consideration, previous research has shown that the power-up pattern of SRAM memory is perfectly reproducible (with the proper application of error-correction codes), unique [86] and also capable of providing randomness [87]. Therefore, SRAM PUF can be applied in the following scenarios:

1. **Secure Key generation:** The most common application of PUFs is secure key generation and storage. The cryptographic key is derived based on SRAM PUF and stored via helper data scheme. In this application, reliability and security are important properties for SRAM PUFs. Reliability means the response of SRAM PUFs is reproducible with limited amount of bit error rate in predefined environmental and system conditions. Error correction codes can be designed to correct up to 25% of bit error rate without reproduction failure [88]. On the other hand, security means two properties. First, SRAM PUF should have sufficient entropy to prevent significant information leakage on the generated key. It implies that bias present on SRAM PUFs should be within the boundary. Current debiasing schemes

can deal with 25% / 75% bias [89]. Second, the response of an SRAM PUF is unpredictable even given all the responses of other SRAM PUFs. It implies that SRAM PUF should have good uniqueness.

2. **True Random Number Generation:** True Random Number Generator (TRNG) provides an unpredicted seed to cryptographic systems. Electrical noise influences the initial state of unstable SRAM cells. By utilizing these noises in the circuits, SRAM PUFs can also serve as TRNG. In this application, a sufficient number of bits should flip over multiple power-ups in order that SRAM PUFs can provide sufficient randomness at next power-up test.

The obfuscation and recovering of a secret with a PUF generally use a fuzzy extractor with a code-offset based secure-sketch [75]. In a generation phase, helper data HD are computed from a PUF response R and a secret K generated by a True Random Number Generator (TRNG). The secret is conveniently encoded, $Enc(K)$, by using the encoder of an error-correcting code. The simplest generation of HD uses XOR operations as follows $HD = R \oplus Enc(K)$. In a reproduction phase, another PUF response R' , which is similar to R but not exactly the same, is employed to recover R and the secret K from HD , by using the decoder of the error-correcting code, $K = Dec(R' \oplus HD)$ and $R = HD \oplus Enc(K)$. Then, using a hash function, the recovered R or K is usually converted into a cryptographically secure and uniform random string to be used as a secret key [90]. An important property of fuzzy extractors is that the HD can be stored and transmitted publicly without revealing the PUF response or the secret. An SRAM can be used to generate PUF responses and true random numbers for this application because SRAM cells can be classified into stable and random cells. If the cell shows preference to power up as 0 or 1, it is a stable cell that is good to be part of the PUF. If the cell shows no preference for any state, it is a random cell that is good to be part of a TRNG [91] [92]. The main advantages of SRAM-PUFs are their small footprint, low energy consumption, very high encryption key generation rate, cost-effectiveness, and operation in harsh environments.

One of the biggest benefits of an SRAM PUF is that it is based on a physical structure that is available in virtually any chip: the SRAM memory. Because this PUF type uses standard “off-the-shelf” SRAM, it is the only hardware entropy source option for securing IoT products that does not need to be loaded at silicon fabrication. It can be installed later in the supply chain, and even remotely retrofitted on deployed devices. This enables a never-before-possible remote “brownfield” installation of a hardware root of trust and paves the way for scaling the IoT to billions of devices. The only hardware required in order to develop a PUF is the actual unique physical structure of the PUF itself. So, on any device where access to (uninitialized) SRAM is available to the PUF algorithms, a working SRAM PUF can be implemented. This property makes the SRAM PUF unique among the spectrum of different silicon PUFs currently available in the market. The SRAM PUF is the only currently existing type of PUF that can be implemented in hardware by simply loading software onto a device. On the contrary, SRAM PUF is a weak PUF, with a limited number of CRPs. Therefore, it needs obfuscated interfaces, which cost extra security layers [93], otherwise they are vulnerable to adversarial attacks.

As already mentioned, a PUF alternative that will be explored in the context of ENTRUST is the speckle imaging based optical PUF, which in contrast with the SRAM PUF, is considered a strong PUF. Such a PUF type, could be the successor technology provided that they can potentially satisfy to a large degree the ideal PUF requirements, i.e. deterministic (time invariant operation), support of very large number of challenge response pairs, resistance to machine learning / brute force attacks, unclonability, and of course, real time on demand operation (no digital storage). A schematic representation of a speckle imaging-based o-PUF is depicted in Figure 4. In such a case, the physical medium been leveraged as a source of entropy is called PUF token. When a

temporal and spatial coherent light source (Fig. 4 (1)), e.g. a diode laser, illuminates a challenge generator (Fig. 4 (2)) e.g. a Spatial Light Modulator (SLM) [94], an Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) [95], a Digital Micromirror Device [96], a specific light pattern is created on demand which in turn illuminates the PUF token (Fig. 4 (3)), e.g. titania (TiO₂) nanoparticles in polymethy methacrylate (PMMA) matrix [96], sandblasted silica glass [95], multi-mode optical fibers [97]. Upon the PUF token illumination, a corresponding output (response) is generated in the form of an optical speckle pattern (alternating and overlapping bright and dark spots). Each PUF response is determined by inputting light pattern incident to the randomly disordered medium (token) and its optical scattering properties, the characteristics of the coherent light source, like wavelength, spatial profile etc. The recorded by a CCD or CMOS camera (Figure 23: (4)) speckle patterns undergo a hashing procedure resulting to unique bit-string outputs. The light source, the challenge generator and the speckle images acquisition device are manipulated by the main control unit (Figure 23: (5)), which is also responsible for the image processing and the extraction of the unique keys.

Figure 23: Operation principle of an optical-PUF and its main building blocks

While the physical characteristics of the p-PUF card are permanent in nature, the information extraction from PUFs (and other noisy sources like biometrics) is a probabilistic procedure; on a single challenge, a different response may be produced, due to the uncontrollable and random noise during the evaluation procedure (evaluation noise). To compensate for the evaluation noise, the p-PUF lock is combined with a fuzzy extraction algorithm that maps slightly different responses from the same challenge to the same unique output. Fuzzy extraction algorithm comprises two phases: the enrolment and the authentication. The former corresponds to the first time that a challenge is applied whereby the output string is generated along with a set of public helper data, while the latter represents the noisy rerun of the enrolment phase, during which the same result is reproduced by using the helper data created.

O-PUFs, as mentioned previously, are considered strong PUFs, with exceptional characteristics as regards the security they are capable to deliver. Optical PUFs leverage the inherent variations in optical components (such as photonic waveguides or scattering elements) to create unique and unclonable identifiers for each device. This uniqueness is a fundamental characteristic that enhances security and makes them suitable for applications where security is a critical concern, such as in **secure key generation** and **authentication**. Unlike traditional cryptographic methods where keys are stored, optical PUFs generate keys or authentication tokens on the fly, **eliminating the risk of key storage** vulnerabilities. Also, the response generated by an optical PUF is inherently random, making it suitable for **true random number generation**. Also, their inherent properties make them extremely resistive to a set of adversarial attacks [98]. However, despite their exotic properties, their main disadvantages are their sensitivity to environmental

factors, such as temperature, humidity, and radiation that may affect the PUF's behavior and could lead to incorrect responses, their complexity and cost since implementing optical PUFs may require specialized optical components, which can increase the complexity and cost of manufacturing devices which make optical PUFs less practical for some applications, whereas integrating optical PUFs into existing systems or scaling them for mass production can be complex while ensuring compatibility with various devices and platforms may pose challenges. In the context of ENTRUST, o-PUFs will be explored as an alternative for enhancing the security primitives of the framework, showcasing a proof-of-concept solution towards o-PUF based novel attestation schemes.

3.2.9 CMD Evidence Monitoring Collection and Dynamic Tracing Functionalities for In-Depth Investigation of the CMDs Behaviour

Among the research pillars of ENTRUST is the CMD evidence monitoring collection and dynamic tracing functionalities. These functionalities play a pivotal role in providing an in-depth investigation of connected medical devices' (CMDs) behaviour, which is vital for ensuring their trustworthiness and security. In the current state-of-the-art, the monitoring and tracing functionalities have emerged as essential components in the field of healthcare cybersecurity [99]. With the increasing complexity of CMDs and their integration into critical healthcare systems, it becomes imperative to have a systematic and robust mechanism to collect evidence and trace the behaviour of these devices in real-time.

The CMD evidence monitoring collection function focuses on gathering relevant data and evidence related to the CMD's operation, communication, and execution. It involves capturing various metrics, events, and logs associated with the CMD's activities. This data collection mechanism allows for the comprehensive analysis and assessment of the CMD's behaviour and performance. By continuously monitoring and collecting evidence, potential anomalies or security breaches can be detected promptly, enabling timely interventions and mitigations. Furthermore, the dynamic tracing functionalities delve deeper into the CMD's behaviour by tracing the control and information flow execution paths. This involves tracking the sequence of commands, data exchanges, and interactions within the CMD and its surrounding environment. By tracing the dynamic execution paths, it becomes possible to identify potential vulnerabilities, security risks, or deviations from expected behaviour. The tracing functionalities enable a granular understanding of how the CMD operates, facilitating in-depth investigations and forensic analyses when needed.

Since the use of CMDs is growing, many challenges need to be addressed [100], leveraging the current state-of-the-art techniques and technologies for CMD evidence monitoring collection and dynamic tracing functionalities. This involves leveraging advancements in data analytics, machine learning and AI algorithms to analyse the collected evidence and detect anomalous patterns or behaviours. More specifically, advanced data analytics takes center stage, deploying intricate tools and algorithms to meticulously process CMD-generated data in real-time, unveiling patterns, anomalies, and potential security threats [101]. The fusion of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) empowers CMDs to evolve alongside emerging cybersecurity threats, adept at discerning nuanced deviations from standard behavior [102] [103] [104]. At the same pathways, blockchain integration emerges as a bedrock, guaranteeing secure and transparent data exchange among CMDs through an immutable ledger, fortifying traceability and supporting forensic investigations [105] [106]. Additionally, ENTRUST explores cutting-edge approaches in runtime attestation mechanisms that provide continuous scrutiny, promptly detecting unauthorized alterations or deviations, ensuring CMD integrity and security.

3.2.10 AI-based Misbehaviour Detection on Blockchain Data

Nowadays, many companies and institutions are based on distributed environments to offer crucial services to the users. Usually, distributed systems comprise various devices which are allocated across different network nodes and communicate for the provision of services to the users. Recently attacks on such devices have been intensified, posing a significant risk on the proper behaviour of devices in the distributed network. Misbehaviour describes the abnormal performance of nodes in distributed networks due to malicious external events or inherent malfunction on such nodes. Misbehaviour detection provides automated mechanisms to monitor the distributed network nodes and discover any misbehaving performance towards addressing the threats and mitigate any security issues timely [107].

The misbehaviour detection systems can be classified in the following categories [108]: (a) Node-driven, where the system monitors the behaviour of each node to comply with the protocol requirements, (b) Data-driven, where the monitoring occurs on the data shared among the nodes, rather than on the protocols of the distributed network, (c) Hybrid, where a dual approach is envisaged, as the evaluation of nodes is based on their shared data, while a node-driven detector verifies the correctness of nodes. In such systems, the information of each node along with the data shared among them can train ML models for misbehaviour detection. As IoT devices face certain inherent restrictions, such as energy-wise, the cumbersome misbehaviour detection applications are subsequently hardly performant [109]. Thus, the introduction of AI techniques in the detection of malicious behaviours in distributed systems is important. Traditional ML techniques may be employed, such as anomaly detection, which recognizes unusual events without prior knowledge.

In addition, DL (deep learning) approaches that are based on artificial neural networks can apply in datasets of large size to detect misbehaviours. Advanced ML techniques can be also used for misbehaviour detection, such as Federated Learning (FL), which focuses on the cooperation among nodes towards training a global model, while no data are exchanged among these nodes. Transfer Learning is another ML advanced approach, where the knowledge acquired from one task is used in another task, meaning that recognizing anomalies in one system may also apply successfully in another system. However, extreme attention should be given and necessary measurements, such as frequent retraining of models, should be taken against poisoning attacks in AI algorithms as these could mislead the misbehaviour detection capabilities [107] [110]. AI algorithms may be also employed for misbehaviour detection on attestation results and system traces towards recognizing any anomalies. Attestation results comprise the measurements that validate the integrity of all system aspects (software, hardware, firmware). System traces constitute the log of system activities that can showcase the behaviour of the system. Such attestation results and system traces can be stored in a blockchain network to safeguard their security and privacy. AI models are utilized for analysing distributed network logs towards monitoring the security of the system and hindering malicious events [111]. The diversified nature of network traffic data has driven the use of deep neural networks (DNNs) for the misbehaviour detection on unlabelled data [112].

ENTRUST envisages to research and utilize such AI-based algorithms that will analyse the operation of distributed medical devices towards detecting malicious behaviours by using the operation logs stored in the blockchain network.

3.2.11 MUDs and Certificates of Conformity

3.2.11.1 MUD Framework

The Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) [113] was standardized in 2019 within the scope of the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF). The MUD specification's major goal is to limit the threat and attack surface of a certain IoT device by allowing manufacturers to establish network behaviour profiles for their devices. Each profile is built around a set of policies, or Access Control Lists (ACLs), that specify the communication's endpoints. MUD represents a scalable and flexible approach to the definition of network access policies beyond the use of IP addresses to enable communications with other services. A manufacturer could, for example, declare that access to particular cloud services, as well as connection with other manufacturers' devices, should be permitted. MUD also allows to specify protocols and ports for each communication to provide a more fine-grained configuration of access control rules. The standard also possibilities the extension of the scheme, allowing manufacturers to express other types of conditions or policies based on their needs. For example, while the MUD is focused on network access control regulations, MUD model expansions are being considered for Quality of Service (QoS) aspects of the communications. Several MUD file extensions are available to enhance the security profiles and capabilities of MUD, which can aid in achieving a more comprehensive security posture for an organization [114] [115].

One of the key advantages of the MUD approach is that the manufacturer is responsible for defining the devices' behavioural profiles (instead of the typical network administrator). Indeed, the MUD design and format make it possible to automate the creation of network access policies based on the manufacturer's MUD profile. It should be noted, however, that the instantiation of these profiles may be influenced by the network domain in which the device is deployed. The standard also defines an architecture to allow the network domain where the device is deployed to obtain and enforce this profile.

Since its adoption, MUD has received a significant interest from the research community and standardization bodies. In particular, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) proposes the MUD standard as a promising approach to mitigate security threats, and to cope with denial-of-service (DoS) attacks in IoT environments, including home and small-business networks. Additionally, the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) considers the use of MUD as part of IoT security good practices to improve, allowing devices to advertise their supported and intended functionality.

One of this proposes and defined by the NIST is the Threat MUD that is a variation of the MUD specification [116], that associates a specific threat with a Threat MUD file. This file is then used to establish configuration rules that limit network access to compromised domains associated with the threat. When combined, MUD and Threat MUD provide a powerful toolset that effectively reduces vulnerabilities and mitigates potential network attacks on IoT devices. By leveraging these specifications, administrators can more effectively protect their networks from cyber threats and ensure the security and integrity of their IoT devices.

The IETF has proposed the most widely used architecture for implementing MUD, which has been realized through an open-source implementation called "osMUD" [117]. This implementation is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/osmud/osmud>), anyways there is some literature about the different implementations [116]. The MUD architecture consists of various components that are deployed both on local premises and in the manufacturer's premises.

- **MUD MODEL**

The MUD standard restricts IoT devices connection by defining Access Control Lists (ACLs) [118], using the Yet Another Next Generation (YANG) standard to model network restrictions and using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) for serialization, It's worth noting that the MUD model includes

Network ACL extensions for the YANG data model, which are augmented by the MUD standard to specify more expressive ACLs.

The MUD file contains two main blocks: the “mud” and “acls” containers, as shown in Figure 24:.

```

module: ietf-mud
  +--rw mud!
    +--rw mud-version          uint8
    +--rw mud-url              inet:uri
    +--rw last-update          yang:date-and-time
    +--rw mud-signature?       inet:uri
    +--rw cache-validity?      uint8
    +--rw is-supported         boolean
    +--rw systeminfo?          string
    +--rw mfg-name?            string
    +--rw model-name?          string
    +--rw firmware-rev?        string
    +--rw software-rev?        string
    +--rw documentation?       inet:uri
    +--rw extensions*          string
    +--rw from-device-policy
      | +--rw acls
      |   +--rw access-list* [name]
      |   +--rw name        -> /acl:acls/acl/name
    +--rw to-device-policy
      +--rw acls
        +--rw access-list* [name]
        +--rw name        -> /acl:acls/acl/name
  
```

Figure 24: Tree representation of YANG MUD model in [113]

The “mud” container specifies several features related with the MUD file itself. The property mud-version specifies the current version of the MUD file, whereas the last-update defines when the current version of the file was generated. The MUD is identified by the mud-url, that is, the URL that can be used to retrieve the MUD file. The mud-signature (optional) verifies the integrity and authenticates the MUD file to avoid security issues. Furthermore, this container also allows to define optional aspects such as the model of the device (model-name), the firmware and software revision (firmware-rev, software-rev), minimum period of time before checking for updates (cache-validity), if the device will receive MUD/software/firmware updates (is-supported), additional information (systeminfo), link to the device documentation (documentation) and additional extensions. Finally, the containers to-device-policy and from-device-policy containers represent access lists references by indicating the appropriate direction of a specific flow to define the communication pattern of the device.

Consequently, the “acls” container defines those ACLs. Each ACL has a name, a set of conditions to apply the rule (matches), and the actions to apply in case the conditions are satisfied (e.g., forwarding accept or deny). By default, the MUD specifies only the allowed connections, but in certain cases, it can be also useful to define an explicit access restriction to a service (for example, if it has been compromised). The ACL extensions to the YANG data model adds additional keywords that facilitates the definition of high-level policies without the need to know the associated IP addresses. These keywords are manufacturer, same-manufacturer, model, local-networks, controller, and my-controller. For example, the keywords manufacturer and same-

manufacturer enable the definition of policies to allow or deny the interaction with devices from the same manufacturer. This way, MUD files define the type of communications and access of a certain device in the form of policies or ACLs. Some examples of these restrictions could be “allow the communication to devices of the same manufacturer”, “allow the access to a specific DNS service”, or “deny the access for a specific port”.

Figure 25: MUD architecture defined in [113]

These components are the following:

Local premises:

1. **MUD Manager:** This is in charge of managing MUD Files, which is, receiving MUD URLs from the devices, retrieving the related MUD Files, storing them, and sending them to the policy translator.
2. **Policy Translator:** This component receives MUD Files from the Manager and translates those Files into policies; these policies will be the output of MUD.
3. **Orchestrator:** This component is in charge of managing the different policies that are included in the MUD and also the local one deployed in the organization. Note that this component is not a MUD component is just a functional organization component.
4. **Device inventory and registering:** This component is an inventory of all deployed device with its information, included MUD URL. Note that this component is not a MUD component is just a functional organization component.

Manufacturer premises:

5. **MUD File Server:** This server allocates all MUD Files and their signatures. It is also exposed to all device clients that could need to at any moment retrieve MUD Files. Moreover, it has a connection with the Certification Authority who can update or add MUD Files anytime.

The MUD Manager processes the URL and asks the MUD File Server for the MUD File and its signature. After validating the signature, the MUD Manager asks the administrator for permissions to add the device along with the associated policy that has just been collected, then instantiates the local configuration based on the file.

Finally, the MUD Server configures the switch closest to the device, among other systems that need it based on the policy. The configuration remains valid until the device is disconnected.

MUD has a close relation with the certification process and Certification Authority, MUD File Server is a repository where the CA has to upload the MUD Files its signature.

Figure 26: Certification Authority MUD sequence proposal

The certification process for IoT devices commences at the manufacturer's premises, where a new device or new anomaly behaviour is identified in the device, or it is a new device. In order to proceed with the certification process, the device and its associated MUD file are submitted to a Certification Authority for evaluation. The Certification Authority performs a series of rigorous security tests to validate the completeness and accuracy of the MUD file before granting the requisite certification. After completing the certification process, the Certification Authority will issue a certification for the IoT device to ensure compliance with necessary security standards and prevent potential security threats or breaches that could compromise the device or its network. If the device is new, the MUD URL, along with a device certificate, will be embedded in the device. In addition to this certificate, the MUD file will be signed by the Certification Authority and uploaded to the MUD File Server. This process ensures that IoT devices are securely deployed in their respective networks and that the MUD file is valid and can be used for network access control.

These steps could be executed during any point of the device lifecycle if there is a new vulnerability discovered that implies re-certify the devices and generate a new MUD File, this new MUD File will be updated at the MUD File Server. Note that, in case of update the device certificate don't need to be embedded to the device again because in the device MUD information is just the MUD URL, the direction of where is allocated the MUD File.

3.2.11.2 Conformity Methodology

The security evaluation methodology developed defines a set of steps to evaluate the security of a system, it builds a framework on top of the two main streams of this proposal: security testing to identify security vulnerabilities and security risk assessment to measure the associated risk.

The first phase is the context phase, which considers the existing regulation, the best practices, current standards etc. [119] to build an initial set of security claims that can be used as starting point for the security evaluation.

From this initial set and taking into account the particular Target of Evaluation (TOE), in the risk identification phase, a set of applicable threats can be selected. This set can be also extended with specific threats not considered in the initial set, by examining the special characteristics of the TOE.

Once the threats are selected, we start the security testing block. The test implementation phase deals with the design and implementation of the tests necessary to verify if the system is vulnerable to these threats. The needed entities and context to execute the tests is established

in the environment set up phase and the tests are executed in the test execution phase, generating at the end of the process a test report.

The test results of the previous phase are used to estimate the risk of every component of the TOE during the risk estimation phase. Towards this end, information from the risk identification phase is required, regarding the components, the identified threats, and their impact. The overall risk evaluation phase combines the risk coming from every component, obtaining an overall measure of the system security.

At the end of the evaluation process, a label showing the evaluation results is generated. Other actions are also possible to mitigate the security flaws encountered during the process. Additionally, the methodology also considers a transversal and supportive process for continuous communication and auditing meant to deal with the lifecycle management of the TOE.

- **ESTABLISHING THE CONTEXT**

In this phase we establish the basis for the evaluation, answering the question *what we are going to evaluate?* In particular, we consider three different sources: the security and privacy claims obtained from current standards, best practices and regulation and the tolerance profiles, which reflects the security level that should be achieved by the system under test (SUT).

The security and privacy claims are the basis on which to evaluate the SUT, since they represent the security properties that the system must meet in order to be certified. The claims can be given by the owner of the SUT in order to demonstrate its compliance with basic security principles or even with a particular security standard, or they could be given by a third party that needs the SUT to comply with certain claims in order to be integrated into her/his system, thus guaranteeing the security of the whole ecosystem.

Based on the particular context of the system, it is needed to specify to what extent the selected claims must be fulfilled, what is the acceptable risk to be able to be certified and what security levels are established within said limits.

- **RISK IDENTIFICATION**

The risk identification phase focuses on describing the system, its components, and its degree of dependency, and identifying possible vulnerabilities that may be present in them through a preliminary analysis. The identified vulnerabilities are associated with the corresponding vulnerability claims, and during the testing phase it will be verified whether they are really present in the system or not.

In the methodology the system should be decomposed in its applicable security properties and affected components. Each system component will have a list of claims to check, claims that can be pure, if they are directly linked with tests or vulnerability claims if they are related to the presence of known vulnerabilities, which are empirically verified through tests. At the end of the system decomposition, we have the tests that should be designed and implemented in the security testing phase.

It is also necessary to take into account the relationship between the different components of a system, as current systems are made up of different interconnected components that work together to provide a service. In this context, a failure in one of the system components, may have cascade effects over other components, or even produce a generalized system failure. Therefore, analysing the existing dependencies among the system components and its degree, can help to determine the impact that a vulnerability would have over the rest of the system components.

- **TESTING PHASE**

Implementation of tests on the system, using the different types of testing that best suit the system being evaluated [120]. It could be functional testing over the selected components of the system as unit testing, integration testing, system testing, acceptance testing, but primarily nonfunctional testing, i.e., security testing, performance testing, usability testing or compatibility testing. The approaches followed on the test design phase may vary between a static, dynamic, passive or “box” approach, the focus is on the adaptability of the use case system.

An agreed format is necessary to express the results of the tests once they have been executed, in this way a risk estimation can be carried out in the following phases of the methodology.

- **RISK ESTIMATION**

The results of the tests are analysed to obtain a numerical value of the risk, based on the mapping between the security claims and the tests implemented, and also using the concepts developed in the risk identification phase.

- **RISK EVALUATION, LABELING AND TREATMENT**

This phase combines the complete description of the system, the output of the risk identification and risk estimation phases to assess the risk [121] of each component. Once calculated, these risks are combined to calculate the overall risk of the system.

A labelling metric is used to certify the safety properties of the system as a final part of the process.

Based on the results obtained, it may be necessary to update properties indicated in files such as MUD files, as part of the ongoing security evaluation of a system. In that case an update of these files is carried out.

4 Technical Requirements

In Section 2.3, we provided a detailed overview of the current standards and regulations pertaining to various aspects related to the security, maintenance, and operational assurance of medical devices throughout their operational lifecycle, including their manufacturing, deployment, integration, normal operation, and end-of-life. However, since a number of the requirements specified in those standards were identified to be out of the scope of ENTRUST, we aimed to **adapt the list of extracted requirements and tailor them to the context of the project**, considering the **needs set forth by organizations belonging to the healthcare sector**, as well as the overall **core tenets of ENTRUST**.

As aforementioned, one of the core considerations in the extraction of these requirements was their **validation by healthcare sector organizations**. In the context of ENTRUST, this was performed through the **alignment of the ENTRUST requirements with those identified by the Use Case Demonstrators**, which represent a wide range of types of medical organizations employing network infrastructures comprising multiple CMDs. The successful fulfilment of these requirements is going to be evaluated through a set of **user stories**, defined in Chapter 6 for all four envisioned use cases, which have been designed in order to cover the specific needs of the corresponding organizations by leveraging the core components provided by the ENTRUST framework. The list of requirements has been reviewed both by the aforementioned use case demonstrators, as well as the members of the ENTRUST Advisory Board (AB), who have provided valuable insight into the best practices towards formulating and refining the final requirements list.

In this Chapter, we provide a description of the methodology employed in order to perform the aforementioned adaptation and to extract the final list of requirements to be considered in the context of ENTRUST. Afterwards, we provide the final list of requirements, which have been split into three categories: (i) **Framework Requirements**, which contain the functional requirements of the ENTRUST framework pertaining to actions that need to be performed in all phases of the lifecycle of a device, (ii) **Security Requirements** related to the secure operation of CMDs and the protection of the security and integrity of the exchanged data, and (iii) **Operational Requirements** related to the operation of CMDs in the context of medical organizations.

4.1 Methodology

As aforementioned, the approach followed in ENTRUST with regards to the definition of requirements had two main goals: (i) the **identification of gaps in the existing standards**, and (ii) the **compilation of the list of requirements to be followed in ENTRUST**, based on the aforementioned standards. In other words, after the identification of the comprehensive list of requirements pertaining to the lifecycle of medical devices, we aimed to first identify weaknesses in the defined approach, and then **adapt this list to the scope of ENTRUST**.

Specifically, the project employed a systematic approach to develop its architecture. Initially conceived during the proposal phase, this architecture underwent multiple revisions, particularly in WP2 and specifically in Task 2.1. Between January and June 2023, a series of workshops took place for its refinement. This process involved a detailed examination of cybersecurity needs and existing gaps in connected medical devices domain. The refined architecture was presented in the plenary meeting that took place in June 2023. This phase led to the identification of various gaps and resolution of several implementation challenges, paving the way for the architecture design. These insights, combined with the defined design goals and gathered requirements (as extracted by the standards and the end-users), were then deliberated with technical partners. An iterative design process, engaging all project stakeholders, concluded to the final architecture detailed in Chapter 5. During the second stage, the primary focus for the architecture team and

technical partners was aligning design objectives and requirements with functional specifications and actual architectural design.

Since security requirements apply to different stages of the lifecycle, the standards mapping takes a second dimension allowing manufacturers to better navigate through the standards depending on at what stage their product is. In Figure 27:, we present a high-level generic lifecycle that applies to all diversity of medical products.

Figure 27: High-level generic lifecycle of medical products.

In Figure 28:, we outline the process followed for mapping the aforementioned phases of the operational lifecycle of a medical device to actual requirements of ENTRUST. Specifically, a first selection of requirements was performed based on the requirements identified in the aforementioned standards, as well as any potential sub-requirements based on key security goals of ENTRUST. Next, we identified the stage of the lifecycle of the medical device corresponding to each requirement. Afterwards, any potential gaps in these standards were identified and a coverage rationale was provided, as outlined in Section 2.4.

Figure 28: Mapping of ENTRUST requirements.

The aforementioned process resulted not only in the identification of gaps in the existing standards as outlined in Section 2.4, but also the definition of the requirement list to be considered in the context of ENTRUST. In the remainder of this Chapter, we provide this list, as well as the approach followed for the fulfilment of these requirements by the methodologies and core artefacts to be designed and implemented as part of the ENTRUST framework.

4.2 Framework Specifications

Following deliberations with the use case partners of ENTRUST with regards to the specific needs of organisations operating within the healthcare domain, as well as discussions between the technical partners of ENTRUST in order to identify the most appropriate methods to be developed and implemented in order to fulfil these needs, in Table 12 we provide a comprehensive list of requirements that need to be fulfilled by the ENTRUST framework. In addition, we provide the reasoning behind the definition of each requirement, as well as the components that are responsible for their fulfilment.

These requirements capture the entire range of functionalities that need to be performed during all phases of the lifecycle of a device, starting from the manufacturing phase and including the deployment of the device into the infrastructure of the target healthcare organisation, as well as the normal operational mode of the device. The goal is to ensure the safe, secure, and uninterrupted provision of healthcare services depending on the capabilities of the device, while also ensuring that any threats (including malicious activity by potential attackers) are addressed using the appropriate mitigation measures.

Table 12: ENTRUST framework specifications

Specification	Name	Description	Reasoning	Connection to ENTRUST Components
FS_1	Device and Network threat modelling	Identify and prioritize potential threats according to the device context (e.g., the location the device will be deployed, network characteristics, capabilities of in terms of processing power and the available connectivity interfaces (Bluetooth, RF, etc.). It should provide indicative mitigation actions (e.g., disable network interfaces).	The analysis of the threat model will allow the risk assessment to quantify the risks given the threat context (e.g., connection to other devices, mobility aspects, introduction of new technological and cross-cutting developments) and extract risk scores, possible attack paths, and attack simulation by the validation component.	Threat Modelling
FS_2	Software threat modelling	Identify and prioritize vulnerabilities based on static code analysis and known vulnerabilities collected by external public sources such as OSV, CVE databases and others. It should provide indicative mitigation actions (e.g., patches)	Using data from the static analysis, this module will provide a report regarding threats that could use the analysed software as an attack vector. This analysis will allow the risk assessment to quantify the risks and extract risk scores, possible attack paths, and attack simulation by the validation component.	Threat Modelling
FS_3	Source code static analysis and SW validation mechanism	Analyse source code for known security vulnerabilities through SW unpacking leveraging Code integrity Validation (CIV) techniques such as memory fuzzing and concolic testing.	Catching security vulnerabilities early in the development process, before being deployed to the medical devices.	SW Verification
FS_4	Security code coverage	Identify areas that are not adequately covered by security tests	Helps developers identify vulnerable areas and comply with industry regulations, by measuring the quality and completeness of security tests	SW Verification
FS_5	Awareness on potential vulnerabilities and threats	The ENTRUST framework should be able to collect and report information regarding vulnerable assets/devices or	Based on this evidence will perform an informed analysis over the deployment being monitored	Risk Assessment

		assets being under attack.		
FS_6	Complete overview of the deployed environment	The framework should offer an interactive tool for visualising the assets taking part in a monitored environment including their characteristics, network topology and dependencies/inter-connections among them.	The risk assessment needs a detailed overview of the connected assets to produce attack risk graphs based on the network topology, dependencies, and the evolvement of a threat in the network's assets.	Risk Assessment
FS_7	Risk quantification and impact analysis	The framework should be able to quantify the risks and analyses the impact of the successful exploitation of each identified vulnerability and calculate cascading effects to other connected devices in the network.	The security admin needs an overview of the identified risks so as to deploy mitigations actions given the results of the risk assessment results, for regulating the risk to the desired level and meet a desired protection level.	Risk Assessment
FS_8	Using Detailed Threat Models in Digital Twins as Input for Attack Validation	The attack validation component needs to take as input detailed threat models for the specification of attacks to be simulated.	The attack validation should be able to simulate attacks for the real system, so that new vulnerabilities and zero-day exploits can be identified and the appropriate mitigation measures (e.g., attestation schemes) can be implemented and applied.	Threat Modelling
FS_9	Simulating the monitored execution path for attack validation	The attack validation component is required to take the output of the device data and execution tracer component to simulate the monitored execution path during attack simulation.	The digital twin should be up-to-date and able to simulate real execution for attack validation, so that the latest version of the software can be secured against malicious activity through the implementation of the appropriate mitigation measures.	Device Data and Execution Tracer
FS_10	Device lifecycle modelling	The formal verification component allows explicit specification of the overall device behaviour throughout its lifecycle.	The Formal Verification component should be able to provide rigorous mathematical proofs for the correctness of all implemented processes where such a verification is possible considering the limitations of the verification method, thus ensuring that all security requirements are met, and the behaviour of the device is correct, based on the provided specifications.	Formal Verification Toolset

FS_11	Service modelling considering the concept of trust explicitly	The component allows specification of the behaviour of all services that are relevant for the safe and secure device operation.	The mathematical analysis performed by the Formal Verification component should be performed for each possible service considering the limitations of the employed verification methods, and ensure that all the security requirements are met, which are relevant for the safe and secure device operation, so that healthcare services can be provided in a reliable manner, based on the underlying specifications.	Formal Verification Toolset
FS_12	Formal verification of security requirements	The component allows specification of the security properties and supports their verification using suitable tools (e.g. protocol verifiers)	This is an essential requirement that provides confidence in the trust models by using formal verification techniques and ensures secure-by-design approach, for the methods where such verification is possible.	Formal Verification Toolset
FS_13	Protection Profiles including the Required Level of Trustworthiness (RTL) per device and service	The Protection Profiles should contain the defined properties for each device/service that needs to be monitored and verified during runtime.	The protection profiles will include the operational parameters that should be attested during runtime verification for the various predefined levels of trustworthiness that cannot be covered by the formally verified crypto schemes.	Trust Abstractions and Protection Profiles (DLT infrastructure)
FS_14	Device status auditing	The "health" status of a CMD shall be auditable for certification purposes. Collected data should reflect the trustworthiness of the device.	When setting up a communication with another device, the interacting device wishes to know the status of that device before proceeding. This should ensure that, when a communication channel is established, the communicating partners have not been compromised by a malicious party and are in a correct operational state.	Runtime Attestation
FS_15	Device Data and Traces collection	The ENTRUST runtime verification should be able to collect periodically data.	In the context of the attestation schemes of ENTRUST, the device should be able to collect data to be used as attestation evidence, which can be used in order to prove the correctness of the configuration state of the device. Thus, the device should be equipped with a Tracer that is capable of collecting the types of data required in order to perform attestation of the trust properties specified in the Protection Profile of the device.	Runtime Attestation, Tracer

FS_16	Runtime attacks detection	The ENTRUST runtime verification and tracing should be able to detect sophisticated attacks during the runtime.	The attestation schemes of ENTRUST should be able to detect when one or more trust properties of the device do not deviate from values that are known to be correct. In addition, the Misbehaviour Detection component should be able to analyse network traffic data in order to identify any type of attack that may have occurred.	Runtime Attestation, Misbehaviour Detection
FS_17	Validation of systems' integrity	The state of a system component should be monitored and verified. This verification may refer to configuration of a system or to the integrity of a critical binary of the system.	The attestation schemes of ENTRUST should be able to verify the configuration integrity of the device through the collection of the appropriate attestation evidence (i.e., configuration traces), for all specified trust properties.	Runtime Attestation (Configuration Integrity Verification)
FS_18	Execution data collection for runtime attacks	The execution tracer is required to collect data from the CMDs and provide the corresponding information to be logged on the DLT and ultimately be processed by the Attestation mechanism and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component.	The collected data will be given as input to the Attestation mechanism and digital twins, while the data will also be used by the AI to identify and classify any type of possible misbehaviour profiles.	Digital twins, AI-based Misbehaviour Detection
FS_19	Threat intelligence data sharing	The MUD and Threat MUD should include the behavioural profile and mitigation strategies for threat intelligence data sharing	The MUD should be accessible and should enable the collection of all the information required for the secure deployment of the device.	Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine
FS_20	Behaviour profile enforcement	A component will require the enforcement of the security profile in the deployment scenario within the bootstrapping phase, as well as in case mitigation actions are needed.	When a device is enrolled into the ENTRUST framework, the secure bootup process is performed and the Risk Assessment engine performs a re-evaluation of the risk profile of the device, considering the asset cartography and interconnectivity of assets. In addition, the Protection Profile of the device will provide the appropriate mitigation actions for addressing any identified threats and vulnerabilities.	Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine and Runtime verification
FS_21	Dynamic verification and possible	Recertification and Risk evaluation	Within the operation of the CMD, continuous monitoring needs to be performed in order to check if the ATL of the device is below the RTL based	Formal Verification Toolset and Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine

	recertification		on the attested trust properties. In this case, it should be checked if any device reconfiguration or software update is needed.	
FS_22	Decentralised identity management using self-issued Verifiable Credentials/Presentations	Devices should be able to issue verifiable credentials which are backed by trustworthy evidence of their provenance. The VC/VPs can be used in the context of access control mechanisms for trust aware authentication and authorisation.	when someone aims to access a set of data by disclosing a set of attributes, we cannot assume that the party responsible for the verification of these attributes is trustworthy. Therefore, a medical device should be able to disclose the particular set of attributes required in order to access the desired set of data (selective disclosure).	SW Verification
FS_23	Mitigation actions to maintain system operation	The protection profiles should include mitigation actions to maintain the required level of trustworthiness. This information will be integrated to MUD protection profiles.	Considering the available mitigation measures within the ENTRUST framework (e.g., attestation enablers), the Protection Profile of the device should specify the most appropriate mitigation measures for the identified types of threats and vulnerabilities. In addition, in case of a failed attestation, the Protection Profile should be updated in order to include any additional mitigation measures to address any newly identified vulnerabilities.	Risk Assessment, Threat Modelling
FS_24	Data provenance	The devices should be authenticated and attested to ensure that data originates from reliable sources. The blockchain infrastructure will be responsible for managing the data provenance and maintaining the chain of provenance.	During the Domain Bootstrapping process, the Domain Manager issues a challenge which is signed by the CMD using its Wallet, in order to verify its correctness before it is enrolled into the framework. In addition, the device is registered with the DLT based on its DID identifier and the signing keys generated during enrolment.	Wallet, DLT
FS_25	Trust assessment to calculate the ATL	The ENTRUST framework should be able to calculate the Actual Level of Trustworthiness and validate it against RTL.	After an attestation process on a number of trust properties is complete, the ATL of the device is calculated based on the number and safety-criticality of the properties that were found to be incorrect. Afterwards, the ATL is compared to the RTL and, if the ATL is lower than the RTL, it is determined that additional measures need to be taken in order to increase the security posture of the device.	Trust Controls, Certification Auditing, Runtime Attestation

FS_26	Using Digital Twins for Dynamic Trust Assessment	The attack validation component should simulate and emulate various attack vectors based on the real-time monitored system traces.	The output of the attack validation component will be fed to the Risk Assessment engine to recalculate the risk quantification graph and the subsequent recommendation of any new policies or other mitigation actions.	Device Data and Execution Tracer, Risk Assessment, Threat Modelling
FS_27	Recording of evidence-related information in DLT	The DLT Infrastructure should accommodate the secure storage of information from ENTRUST operations, such as attestation and operational data.	Metadata from ENTRUST operations should be written in the Blockchain, while data should be stored encrypted in off-chain facilities for traceability of operations. In case of a failed attestation process, the raw trace data used as attestation evidence should be encrypted and stored (either on-chain or off-chain) so that they can be used in order to determine the cause of the failure.	DLT Infrastructure
FS_28	Support of smart contracts in DLT	The DLT should facilitate the writing of smart contracts for transparency, immutability and traceability purposes, every time a transaction takes place in ENTRUST.	The use of smart contracts for the execution of security policies enables the monitoring and transparency of blockchain-enabled transactions.	DLT Infrastructure
FS_29	Support of private and public channels in DLT	The DLT should include both a private and a public channel, where the private channel will contain sensitive and private information, while the public channel will store anonymous metadata for any verification/certification purposes.	Depending on the privacy requirements of the system under consideration, the DLT infrastructure of ENTRUST should provide data access capabilities depending on the confidentiality level of the data and the permission of the parties attempting to access the data. In this context, the data stored on the public ledger should not contain data that may compromise the anonymity of a device or the confidentiality of the stored data.	DLT Infrastructure
FS_30	Analysis of network traffic data using AI-based methods	The Misbehaviour Detection component should be able to detect anomalies in network traffic data through the use of AI-based methods.	During the operation of a device, it is possible to deploy Network Monitors in order to collect network traffic data which provides information on the volume and frequency of data exchanged with the device. This data is stored on the DLT in the context of collaborative data sharing, and can be used in the training set of the AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component in order to enable classification between benign and malicious behaviours.	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection

FS_31	Use of time-series for device misbehaviour analysis	The AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component should run analysis on runtime through the use of time-series data based on network traffic data.	After the AI-based classification model of the Misbehaviour Detection component has been trained, it should be able to receive network traffic data and detect any abnormal or unexpected behaviour (e.g., unusually high traffic load or traffic spikes).	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection
FS_32	Use of Trusted Components for misbehaviour detection	The AI-based Misbehaviour Detection component should use TCs for analysis purposes	In order to safeguard data used in misbehaviour analysis, the Trusted Components of the device are used in order to sign any transmitted data, and the DLT is used in order to ensure the integrity and correctness of the stored data.	AI-based Misbehaviour Detection
FS_33	Use of a hybrid Trusted Component approach	ENTRUST should employ a hybrid approach with regard to the Trusted Components (TCs) integrated into the device, utilizing both a PUF and a TEE.	The two employed TCs will serve different needs. Specifically, the PUF will be used for integrating hardcoded device keys on the device so that its identity can be verified based on physical properties, and the TEE will use keys derived by the aforementioned device keys in order to perform various cryptographic operations.	Runtime Attestation, Trust Abstractions and Protection Profiles (DLT infrastructure)
FS_34	Use of high-entropy cryptographic keys	The cryptographic keys employed in the context of ENTRUST should be created based on seeds provided by the PUF.	The PUF is able to provide seeds with high entropy, thus leading to highly cryptographically secure keys. This will guarantee a high level of trustworthiness with regard to the security of the performed cryptographic operations, as well as a system as a whole.	Runtime Attestation

4.3 Security requirements

In order to ensure the operation of CMDs in a manner that ensures the integrity of the performed operations and exchanged data, as well as protection from tampering or other malicious activity from attackers, in Table 13 we identify the security requirements that need to be fulfilled by the ENTRUST framework. These include requirements pertaining to the correctness of the operational state of the device, the integrity of the exchanged data, the prevention of tampering on the device or data by any malicious actors, and the mitigation of any potential threats or identified vulnerabilities.

Table 13: ENTRUST security requirements

Requirement	Name	Description	Reasoning
SR_1	Access Control	The CMD allows each role to access only the functions it is authorized for.	It should be possible to provide the required level of granularity in system and data access, based on the role of the party attempting to access a particular function or set of data (e.g., doctor, nurse, hospital

			administrator) in a manner that fulfils all relevant security requirements.
SR_2	Critical Data Protection	The CMD protects critical data against accidental/intentional change and loss.	It should be ensured that safety-critical data pertaining to patient health must be protected against tampering or other compromises, in order to ensure that the provision of healthcare to patients is not jeopardized,
SR_3	Code Integrity Check	The CMD checks the integrity of the program code every time it is restarted	It should be ensured that the CMD is in a correct operational state, both with regard to the integrity of the firmware and the properties specified by the Protection Profile, in order to ensure the reliability and safety of all actions performed pertaining to the security of the handled data.
SR_4	Patch Application, Roll-back and Access Control	The CMD allows patches to be applied. It allows to remove defective patches again and it limits the ability to apply or remove patches to users. Also, the CMD checks changed program code (patches) for integrity before first use and when restarted.	To facilitate updates and fixes, to ensure system stability and safety and maintain system security, and to ensure system stability and safety, it should be ensured that system updates on devices should be performed in a manner that guarantees the correctness of the software patch, as well as the correctness of the device configuration, both before and after the update has been performed.
SR_5	Audit Log and Traces Protection	The CMD logs all essential actions on the system in an audit log and collect traces related to the operation of the CMD.	It should be possible to record the outcomes from the execution of all security controls (e.g., attestation actions), so that an auditor or certification body with the appropriate permissions is able to access those results. In addition, it should be possible to maintain and isolate a record of system activities for analysis and identification of new threats and vulnerabilities.
SR_6	Runtime identification of vulnerabilities and attacks	The CMD is protected through the implementation of mechanisms capable of detecting runtime attacks.	Following a failed attestation action, it should be possible to use the attestation evidence (e.g., system raw traces) in order to perform intrusion detection actions and to identify vulnerabilities in the system, thus ensuring the security and reliability of the CMD.
SR_7	Authenticated and Encrypted Communications	All communications of CMD should be encrypted and authenticated. The CMD only transmits data via its data interfaces in ciphered form. This applies to the communication between CMDs but also to external data carriers.	All data exchanges between devices and parties should be performed in a manner that achieves security and integrity of the transmitted data, and it should be ensured that this data has not been compromised by a malicious third party.

SR_8	Data Integrity	Protects the integrity of the data against unwanted modification.	It should be possible for all parties receiving messages from a device or actor participating in the ENTRUST network to be able to verify the integrity of the message and the contained data, in a manner that ensures a high level of trustworthiness in all data exchanges.
SR_9	Certificate Exchange	Allows the exchange of certificates.	It should be possible to establish a secure communication channel between the CMDs and the Certification Authority (CA) during the secure enrolment phase for the issuance of certificates.
SR_10	Cryptographic Libraries Integrity	The libraries for all cryptographic functions have been tested in advance.	The security of all cryptographic operations and schemes employed in the context of the ENTRUST framework should be ensured through the use of formal verification methods, so that the reliability and security of the underlying cryptographic functions is guaranteed through rigorous mathematical proofs for all required security properties.
SR_11	Cryptographic Libraries Updated	Check that all cryptographic libraries are updated.	It should be ensured that the version of the employed cryptographic libraries is not outdated or deprecated and that the installed libraries are up to date, so that the latest identified threats and vulnerabilities are considered, and all identified exploits have been patched so that they cannot be utilized by a malicious third party.
SR_12	Key Uniqueness	Uses different technologies or keys for different functions.	It should be ensured that we do not use the same key for two or more different cryptographic functions, so that in case one key has been compromised, the security breach is contained to one specific context and does not propagate to other security functions of the system.
SR_13	Certificates Authentication	Certificates need to be authenticated.	It should be ensured that certificates originate from a legitimate source and not have been tampered with during transmission or storage. It should also be ensured that an outdated or deprecated certificate is not used, so that it cannot be exploited by a potentially malicious third party.
SR_14	Integrity of Traces	The integrity of the collected traces which reflect the system state needs to be ensured.	In the context of the attestation schemes of ENTRUST, the correctness and integrity of the raw traces collected by the Tracer as attestation evidence should be ensured, so that they have not been corrupted or tampered by a malicious third party, thus leading to incorrect attestation results (e.g., generating a successful attestation result while a malicious third

			party has tampered with the traces in order to mask their compromise of the device).
SR_15	Isolated execution of security critical functions	The CMD should be equipped with essential mechanisms to effectively isolate the execution of sensitive functions.	Critical services, particularly cryptographic ones, must operate in complete isolation from other software components. The reasoning behind this approach is that, in case one such service is compromised, the attack cannot propagate to different services and components, thus reducing the potential impact of the attack.
SR_16	Detection of abnormal deviations in the device behaviour	Mechanism for detecting abnormal behaviour of a CMD as part of a network.	We need to implement and deploy mechanisms, which are able to compare the configuration state of the device or the execution of a software process against a state that is known to be correct and trustworthy, so that a deviation from this state can be flagged as a potential indication of risk. Thus, the detection of an abnormal behaviour can be used in order to identify zero-day threats and new vulnerabilities.
SR_17	Integration of a Root-of-Trust to the CMDs	The Root-of-Trust will underpin all secure operations on a chip and will protect the CMDs. The RoT needs to provide a unique and unforgeable foundation. CMDs should have a RoT used for storage of keys, collection of traces and reporting of results.	A root of trust will be used to securely manage the root key material of the platform as well as to ensure secure bootstrapping of the platform, collection of traces and reporting results. This will ensure the integrity and correctness in the creation and storage of all required underlying cryptographic material, and will provide a high level of trustworthiness guarantees in the execution of all cryptographic processes.
SR_18	Secure cryptographic Key Management/Storage	The cryptographic keys used for the critical security functions need to be securely managed and stored.	The Root-of-Trust must provide capabilities for the secure storage and management of all keys required in the context of the security controls and functions employed in the context of ENTRUST (e.g., remote attestation).
SR_19	Confidentiality of SW/FW updates and security patches	SW updates should be encrypted to ensure that they remain unknown to an attacker eavesdropping transmissions.	A Malicious third party may attempt to hijack the software update process of a device, in order to obtain illicit access to the device and compromise its integrity. Thus, we should be able to prevent unauthorized access and tampering by ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of the updates, especially guarding against potential eavesdropping attacks.
SR_20	Secure security/vulnerability patching over protected	Patching vulnerabilities should be handled with secure communication and cryptographic operations.	A secure update process is needed, that enables patching vulnerabilities that have been identified by the intrusion detection mechanisms of ENTRUST following the execution of a security function (e.g., failed attestation). The integrity of the secure

	communication channels		update process should be guaranteed through the utilization of the underlying Root-of-Trust (RoT).
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4.4 Operational Requirements (Pre-Deployment)

As aforementioned, prior to the deployment and integration of a device into the operational environment of a healthcare organisation, there are several requirements that need to be fulfilled in order to ensure the secure, reliable, timely, and uninterrupted provision of healthcare services. In this context, in Table 14, we provide a detailed list of operational requirements that need to be fulfilled regarding the operation of CMDs within such organisations, particularly pertaining to actions that need to be taken by the manufacturer or the security administrator of the target organisation.

Table 14: ENTRUST operational requirements

Requirement	Name	Description	Reasoning
OR_1	User Environment Definition, Data Interface Identification and Protocol Specifications	The manufacturer defines the intended user environment (neighboring system identification) and identifies all neighboring systems that may connect to the CMD. Identifies all data interfaces and specifies protocols and standards used for each data interface. Also, defines CMD functions accessible to each role and neighboring system.	In order to perform risk assessment after a device is introduced into the network, we need to consider the network topology, number and type of assets, and asset interconnectivity. The motivation is to understand the operating environment and its potential vulnerabilities, to understand potential points of interaction, to understand all points of data transfer and ensure secure and standardized data transfer, and to manage access to CMD functionalities.
OR_2	Role List Creation and interaction role lost	The manufacturer creates a list of all roles that may interact with the CMD	It is possible that parties that fulfil different roles (e.g., patient, doctor, IT security administrator) aim to interact with the CMD. It is necessary for all such roles to be identified, in order to enable the design and implementation of access control mechanisms based on these roles.
OR_3	Unspecified User/Behaviour Risk Analysis and Risk acceptance criteria	The manufacturer analyzes risks if system is used by non-specified user or adversary, and the impact if a function of the device used by any adversary. Also, she analyzes specific risks resulting from the choice of technologies, including programming language, SOUP/OTS components and generates risk acceptance criteria based on CMD intended use and safety criteria.	Since risk is defined as likelihood times impact, we should consider these factors within the employed risk assessment methodology. The reasoning is to understand potential risks from unauthorized use (attack scenarios showing the risks), and define acceptable levels of risk
OR_4	Security Threat Modelling	The manufacturer identifies threats and vulnerabilities using threat modelling for	The motivation behind the risk assessment approach followed in ENTRUST is to identify and manage

		safeguarding CMDs. It involves delineating the scope of the CMD, creating a comprehensive overview of its architecture, and identifying critical components and examining potential threats and vulnerabilities.	potential IT security threats and impacts. Based on this, we can prioritize addressing the most impactful and critical threats, thus allowing for the implementation of targeted security controls and countermeasures.
OR_5	Overloading System Risk Investigation	The manufacturer investigates consequences of overloading system with too many requests or large volumes and defines actions	Overloading the system with too many requests may have adverse effects on the execution of software processes, including safety-critical processes and mathematical computations required for the execution of cryptographic operations. Therefore, it is necessary to identify and mitigate risks caused by system overload.
OR_6	Buffer Overflow Mitigation Measures	The manufacturer defines measures that can find and eliminate buffer overflows	Buffer overflow attacks may lead to the leakage of data, which may create vulnerabilities that can be exploited by malicious parties. Therefore, it is necessary to implement the necessary countermeasures for the prevention and mitigation of buffer overflow attacks.
OR_7	Network Availability Risk Analysis	The manufacturer analyzes consequences if network is no longer available or no longer in expected quality	Network availability issues may lead to the inability for devices and backend components to exchange safety-critical data. This may lead to the inability to execute security processes, such as attestation actions. Therefore, such issues may lead to compromises in the overall system security, and it is necessary to mitigate risks caused by network failures.
OR_8	Pre-Delivery Malicious Code Testing	The manufacturer tests software (source code and binaries) for malicious code before delivery and/or protects all components involved in software development and "CMDion" against malware. The manufacturer takes measures to ensure tools used, platforms, and SOUP/OTS components are free of malicious code	There have been various types of attacks identified in the literature based on the insertion of malicious code snippets and the installation of malware. This type of attacks is one of the most prominent threats to the security, integrity, and confidentiality of the stored data, but also the devices themselves. Therefore, it is necessary to implement the necessary measures (e.g., intrusion detection and attestation enablers) to prevent such malware infections.
OR_9	Patch Management Plan	The manufacturer documents a plan for the application and removal of patches, including development, distribution, installation, and review. The manufacturer assesses how often patches are required and how they should be installed.	It is possible that a malicious party may attempt to compromise the software update process, in order to obtain illicit access to a device and potentially install malicious code. Therefore, in order to maintain system security and stability, it is necessary to implement a secure software update process that entails verifying the correctness of the configuration state of the device before, during, and after the

			update process, as well as the integrity of the update patch itself.
OR_10	Functionality Assurance Assessment	The manufacturer assesses the functionality the medical device must guarantee in the event of cybersecurity compromise.	Since ENTRUST deals with applications belonging to the healthcare sector where it is crucial to maintain healthcare functionalities with little to no downtime, we need to implement mechanisms that enable maintaining essential functionality in the event of a breach.
OR_11	Usual Attack Vector Security Check	The manufacturer includes a security check against the usual attack vectors in the test plan.	There have been several potential threats and vulnerabilities identified in the literature for the types of devices considered in ENTRUST, as well as attacks noted in various threat intelligence databases. To this end, it is necessary to implement mechanisms that are able to check for the presence of such attacks, as well as to implement the appropriate mitigation measures for such attacks.
OR_12	Risk-Control Measures Effectiveness Check	The manufacturer has checked the effectiveness of all risk-control measures.	In order to ensure the effectiveness of the ENTRUST solution, it is necessary to validate the effectiveness of the implemented risk-control measures in a formal manner, through the use of rigorous mathematical proofs and dedicated verification tools.
OR_13	CMD Delivery Check	The manufacturer has described how it is ensured that only the exact intended artifacts (files) in exactly the intended version are delivered in the CMD or as a CMD.	Using a deprecated version of the CMD may lead to potential security risks, such as the exploitation of vulnerabilities which may have been addressed in later versions of the CMD. To this end, it is necessary to ensure that the correct and intended version of the CMD is delivered.
OR_14	Post-market Surveillance Plan	The manufacturer has created a post-market deployment surveillance plan.	Even after the ENTRUST platform has been released to the market, it is possible that new types of threats and vulnerabilities are identified, for which dedicated countermeasures and mitigation measures are required. To this end, it is necessary to keep track of the CMD's performance and issues after it has been released to the market
OR_15	Downstream Phase Information Channels	The manufacturer has described how and through which channels information is collected from the downstream phase.	In order to apply the appropriate mitigation measures and attestation enablers, it is necessary to collect information from the downstream phase of the operation of a device. Therefore, we need to ensure the effective collection of such information.
OR_16	Patch Acquisition and Installation Assurance	Defines how the customer obtains the patches, as well as how the manufacturer ensures that the patches are correctly installed.	In order to ensure that all newly identified vulnerabilities are addressed in a manner that is accessible to customers in a timely and efficient manner, we need to ensure that patches are easily and promptly

			accessible to customers, and that patches are installed properly by the customers
OR_17	Neighbouring system and topology identification	The security administrator identifies the neighbouring systems, referring to devices directly linked within a network, and the network structure itself (topology identification).	In order to effectively perform risk assessment, it is necessary to consider the interconnectivity between assets and devices belonging to the target network, to understand interconnected devices, and the structural layout of the network. Thus, it becomes possible to identify potential attack paths that may be followed by a malicious party in order to obtain illicit access to a device and compromise its integrity.
OR_18	Security Risk Evaluation	The security administrator evaluates the CMD-related risks after the deployment of the device	Following the execution of a failed attestation process, it should be possible to perform an investigation on the data used as attestation evidence in order to identify the cause that led to the failure, and to potentially identify any new zero-day vulnerability. Thus, it is necessary to regularly evaluate and manage IT security risks and identify appropriate mitigation measures.
OR_19	Regulatory Requirement Identification	The manufacturer identifies all relevant regulatory requirements in all markets.	Organisations operating within the healthcare sector are subject to various regulations pertaining to security, data integrity, etc. To this end, it is necessary to ensure compliance of all tools and security solutions provided by ENTRUST with all relevant regulations.
OR_20	Risk Acceptance Criteria Generation	The manufacturer generates risk acceptance criteria based on CMD use and state-of-the-art.	Based on the criticality of a component or an underlying software process, it is necessary to define acceptable levels of risk, and to prioritise the most prominent and impactful risks that should be addressed with the available mitigation measures.

4.5 Legal and Ethical Requirements

In Section 2.5, we provided a detailed analysis on the current legal framework with regard to ethical and legal aspects pertaining to the medical device domain. Following this analysis, we have identified the key requirements relevant to ENTRUST, i.e., the requirements that fall within the scope of the project and are related to the previously analysed framework specifications and security/operational requirements. As such, Table 15 contains the identified requirements along with the corresponding legal framework and ENTRUST requirements, as outlined in the previous Sections.

Table 15: ENTRUST legal and ethical requirements

Requirement	Description	Relevant Legal Frameworks	Corresponding ENTRUST requirements
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LR_01	Ensuring that the processing of medical device data is clearly defined and justified for legitimate healthcare purposes. Data is not collected or used for purposes that are unrelated to patient care or device functionality	Convention on the Protection of Individuals regards Automatic Processing of Personal Data (Convention 108)	[ALL FR]
LR_02	Protecting patient privacy and confidentiality	Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention) International Medical Informatics Association (IMIA) Code of Ethics for Health Information Professionals, World Health Organization (WHO) Resolution on e-Health Directive 2002/58/EC (Directive on privacy and electronic communications or ePrivacy Directive), Regulation 2016/679/EU (GDPR) Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA , Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union NIS 2	[FR_29, SR_1, SR_2, SR_7]
LR_03	Preventing attacks and incidents, while protecting the integrity of medical device systems	Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention) International Medical Informatics Association (IMIA) Code of Ethics for Health Information Professionals ISO 13606-1:2019 - International Standardization Organization (ISO) Standards for Electronic Health Records (EHRs) REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 European medical devices regulation (MDR) Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union NIS 2	[ALL SR]
LR_04	Ensuring the integrity of medical device data	Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention)	[FR_10, FR_14, FR_15, FR_17, FR_30]
LR_05	Promoting interoperability among EHR systems. ENTRUST should ensure that medical device data can be exchanged and integrated across different healthcare settings,	ISO 13606-1:2019 - International Standardization Organization (ISO) Standards for Electronic Health Records (EHRs) REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 European medical devices regulation (MDR)	[OR_1, OR_19]

	facilitating the exchange of patient information.		
LR_06	Ensuring repeatability, reliability, and performance of devices	REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 European medical devices regulation (MDR)	[FR_10, FR_14, FR_15, FR_17, FR_30]
LR_07	Definition of measures that will be implemented in case of a data security breach.	REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 European medical devices regulation (MDR)	[FR_23, OR_6, OR_9, OR_10]
LR_08	Vulnerability management: identify, assess, and address vulnerabilities in ICT products and services	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union NIS 2	[SR_6, OR_3, OR_4, OR_11]
LR_09	Patch management: apply security patches to ICT systems and software.	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union NIS 2	[SR_4, SR_20, OR_9, OR_16]

5 ENTRUST Conceptual Architecture

As aforementioned, organizations belonging to the medical and healthcare domain are subject to a wide variety of security, privacy, and trustworthiness requirements, as well as regulatory standards that aim to ensure the secure, reliable, and uninterrupted provision of healthcare services, while also preserving the security and integrity of patient-related data. The core target of ENTRUST is the design and implementation of a holistic security framework that is able to fulfil the aforementioned goal, starting from the manufacturing of the device and including not only the deployment of the device to the infrastructure of the target medical organization, but also the continuous monitoring of the correctness and integrity of the CMD.

The action workflow of ENTRUST can be split into three core phases: (i) the **Design Phase**, which includes all actions performed by the CMD Manufacturer before its deployment to the target medical organization, (ii) the **Pre-Deployment Phase**, which includes all actions performed after the CMD is deployed to the organization before its actual operation, and (iii) the **Runtime Phase**, which includes all actions performed as part of the continuous monitoring of the security and operational state of the device throughout its operational lifetime. In Figure 5, we provide a high-level visualisation of the action workflow of the ENTRUST framework comprising the three aforementioned phases, which will be elaborated throughout the remainder of this Chapter.

Figure 5: High-level description of ENTRUST action workflow

5.1 High-level Conceptual Architecture

As aforementioned, the ENTRUST architecture is divided into three major phases. Here, we provide further details on the actions performed within each individual phase as depicted in Figure 5. These will provide the basis for the sequence diagrams that will be provided for the individual operations performed as part of the ENTRUST framework.

The first phase is the **design phase** of a CMD, which involves the actual design and development by the manufacturer. This phase includes several critical processes, starting with the initial conceptualization (medical and user needs) as well as requirements assessment. It includes understanding the specific medical need the device aims to address, its intended functionalities, the environment in which it will be deployed, and the target users (see Section 4.4 - *Operational requirements* for more details). Subsequently, the phase progresses to the specification of detailed requirements. These specifications cover technical and functional aspects, including device functionalities, connectivity features, data management protocols, and adherence to medical regulations, all of which are crucial in outlining the design blueprint of the CMD. This also considers security and safety requirements based on the standards and regulations. Hence, integral to this phase is the adherence to regulatory compliance and standards, aligning the CMD design with relevant medical device standards and regulations, such as the CE marking in the EU or the FDA in the U.S. Such compliance includes various aspects, including safety, efficacy, quality control, and manufacturing processes. Furthermore, risk assessment and validation are part of this phase, aiming to identify potential risks related to device functionality and patient safety, and conducting extensive testing to ensure the device meets all necessary safety and performance criteria.

The next phase is **pre-deployment**, during which the device leaves the manufacturing floor and is delivered to the end-user. For broad applicability, the target environment is referred to as “domain” in the project, regardless of whether it is a medical organization, a hospital, or a small clinic. It is important to note that the ENTRUST architecture adopts an agnostic approach to the targeted environment, allowing for easy deployment across different settings. During this phase, a comprehensive site assessment is conducted to analyse the domain’s network capabilities and system compatibility, which are essential for supporting the CMD. At the same time, there is an emphasis on ensuring that the CMD complies with both local and national healthcare regulations, including data privacy and patient safety standards. The system administrator plays a critical role at this stage, introducing the specific network topology of the environment where the CMD will be deployed, along with other domain-specific security and requirements. This step allows for the re-evaluation and re-quantification of previously identified risks, making them more specific to the domain, and facilitates the extraction of specific security and trust controls. Integration testing before full deployment is also critical to identify potential compatibility issues or operational challenges when the CMD interacts with other systems in the hospital (e.g., when a bedside monitor is connected to the other CMDs and the centralized systems of the hospital). The establishment of robust data privacy and security measures is equally important, given the sensitive nature of medical data. This involves setting up secure data transmission channels, ensuring data encryption, and implementing strict access controls. Often, hospitals choose a controlled pilot testing phase for the CMD, allowing for real-world monitoring and evaluation on a smaller scale, which is crucial for identifying any unforeseen issues. Insights gained from pilot testing inform final adjustments and optimizations, which may include modifying device settings, hospital workflows, or enhancing staff training.

The **runtime phase** of a CMD is the period where the device is actively used in the hospital setting for patient care. This phase primarily involves continuous monitoring to ensure the CMD’s correct functioning, involving regular checks against policies (and the information included in the

Protection Profiles) and updates. This includes the continuous testing of the devices against the set of policies, which is based on level of criticality of each of the envisioned functions and services. In case of malfunctioning, the security administration can enforce specific software/firmware updates and inform the manufacturer. Rapid security issue resolution is critical to minimize patient care disruptions.

The following diagram provides an overall view of the ENTRUST high-level architecture. In the upper left side, we illustrate the design-time toolset utilized by manufacturers during the device's design phase. Next to this, in the upper right part, is the domain-specific toolset. This includes various modules targeting the deployment in the domain level, such as the domain manager that will be deployed in the hospital. It is worth noting that the domain specific tools are used during both the pre-deployment and the runtime phase. Moving to the lower left corner, we showcase the ENTRUST-enabled CMD with the integrated ENTRUST agent and its various subcomponents. This part also highlights the placement of the TC-based middleware within the system. Conversely, the lower right box focuses on the Distributed Ledger, detailing its subcomponents and their interactions. For a deeper understanding of the architecture, the next subsection delves into the actions occurring within the three major phases of the architecture. Detailed explanations of the individual functional components are provided in Section 5.2, while Section 5.3 elaborates on the sequence of actions associated with each phase of the architecture.

5.1.1 Design Phase

5.1.1.1 CMD Design and Initial Risk Assessment

During the design phase of a CMD, manufacturers begin with the initial conceptualization, focusing on the intended medical scope. This phase is crucial as designers extract specific needs and specifications, incorporating essential security and compliance requirements based on healthcare standards, legislations, and several medical safety protocols. As mentioned in the previous chapter, there is an evident lack of a harmonized list of security requirements that should be followed by the manufacturers. To this end, the project provides the first list of security requirements as part of this deliverable (Section 4.3). Given the initial design, including the device capabilities, an initial threat analysis takes place exploring the already known types of threats and vulnerabilities based on the CMD characteristics and running services (i.e., existing CVEs).

More specifically, threat analysis is a thorough examination, identifying potential threats and vulnerabilities pertinent to the device's context. This includes factors like deployment characteristics and the device's own capabilities, such as processing power and available connectivity interfaces (e.g., Bluetooth, RF). Afterwards, the Risk Assessment comes into play to quantify the risks within the CMD (based on the identified vulnerabilities and its criticality level), including both hardware and software assets. The goal here is to calculate risk scores, map out possible attack paths, and create interdependency graphs. This tool is crucial in understanding how risks and potential threats could propagate, not just within the device, but across interconnected infrastructures. Particularly in CMDs with wireless interfaces, threats can emerge from access to a specific module or due to misconfigurations, leading to widespread implications.

Following the risk quantification for each identified threat and vulnerability, the attack validation component becomes active. This stage involves thorough attack testing, validation, and resilience checks against the identified threat models and attack vectors. This is executed based on the use of a Digital Twin as a virtual, container-based environment that a digital representation of the CMD is created, including its safety-critical components and services. This environment is used to replicate identified threats and evaluate mitigation actions (through security and attestation policies) in a controlled setting. This proactive approach allows for enhanced forecasting, detection, and prevention of vulnerabilities before they are enforced in real-world scenarios.

In this context, the SW and FW analysis component plays a crucial role in identifying potential vulnerabilities and attack vectors, building upon the initial threat categorization established by the Risk Assessment. Through this process, source code and binaries undergo a thorough sanitization and mitigation procedure to fix identified vulnerabilities, ensuring that the software is ready to be deployed to the medical devices. Furthermore, the validation mechanism generates a "golden hash", representing the correct configuration parameters, which is subsequently utilized to verify the integrity of the deployed software through Code Integrity Validation (CIV) techniques. This module is also useful during runtime, especially when a bug or vulnerability is detected. Based on tracing evidence, it performs a sanitation process and develops the necessary patches and updates to maintain the device secure and functional.

5.1.1.2 Formal Models

During the design phase, a critical step involves defining formally verified trust models, which includes the cryptographic primitives and necessary operations to meet security, privacy, and trust requirements. These models fundamentally provide cryptographic and mathematical proofs detailing the CMD's required actions across various services, starting from determining the types of keys to be generated during bootstrapping (i.e., attestation keys), to ensuring secure communication and remote software updates. These verified models establish clear trust boundaries for CMD operation, offering verifiable guarantees on the correctness of their functioning. To achieve this level of verification, a combination of tools and methods is employed in ENTRUST, including cryptographic protocol verifiers such as Proverif, among others. The properties that are formally verified imply that no additional checks are needed during the device's runtime. For instance, if the secure boot process of the device, including secure key exchange, key size, and key derivation, is formally verified, further attestation of these operations becomes unnecessary. This approach streamlines the CMD's operation by pre-validating critical security aspects, ensuring a robust and trustworthy operation.

5.1.1.3 Composition of Protection Profiles

The final step of the design phase involves creating Protection Profiles by the manufacturer, which include detailed security specifications designed to address the identified risks associated with the specific functionalities of the medical device. More specifically, the ENTRUST-specific protection profile extends the Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) profiles as standardized by

the IETF in RFC 8520. These extended profiles clearly outline security objectives in terms of confidentiality and integrity, i.e., what the medical device is expected to protect against, such as unauthorized access or data leakage. To contextualize these objectives, the Protection Profiles incorporate the already identified threat model, detailing potential threats. Since the exact environment in which the device will be deployed is not precisely known to the manufacturer, several assumptions are made regarding the operating environment and the existing security policies. These assumptions are conveyed to the end-user as security recommendations, dictating rules and procedures the device must adhere to (e.g., how the device should be connected to the network of the medical organization, which interfaces should be used, user authentication processes, etc.). The core of the Protection Profiles lies in the specific security assurance requirements, including operational parameters that should be attested during runtime verification to meet the necessary level of assurance and trustworthiness.

Speaking of trustworthiness, another critical feature of the Protection Profile Composition Engine is specifying the Required Level of Trustworthiness (RTL), meaning the specific security claims that need to be exhibited per device (during runtime) to ensure the device's trustworthy state in each stage. Note that the initial RTL calculation performed during the design phase is a process that considers the risk scores identified by the Risk Assessment and the security controls of the device (based on the Manufacturer) and is deployed to the Trust Model as part of the Trust Assessment process. The goal is to characterize its critical processes from secure bootstrap and authentic communication to secure management and distribution of potential software updates, and to map these to specific security properties that need to be verified. This process requires identifying the properties that can be attested during runtime based on the device's capabilities and the criticality level of the process. For instance, a highly critical process (e.g., secure software update) demands a deeper understanding and proofs of the device's secure state. Therefore, the Protection Profiles dictate the operational assurance process to be followed during runtime, including specific security properties, attestation challenges, and sources of trust for each function. Of course, this process cannot be finalized during the manufacturer's design without considering the peculiarities of the target environment. Hence, the security administrator further specifies the protection profiles during the pre-deployment phase (see next step).

Moreover, the Protection Profile contains a description of the intended benign (normal) behaviour of the CMD when connected to a network. It specifies the types of network connections the device should make, the protocols it should use, and other types of devices and services it should communicate with (also predefined as part of the security requirements – see Section 4.3). By providing a clear description of expected behaviours, the Protection Profiles enable security administrators to configure access controls and other policies, such as setting up firewalls or other network security tools, to only allow traffic that conforms to the specific profile, effectively reducing the device's attack surface.

This process simplifies the efforts of security administrators, also eliminating potential gaps in shielding the networks. Since each CMD comes with manufacturer-defined Protection Profiles outlining its expected network behaviour, it is easier to identify and manage devices on a network. Additionally, the profile may include supplementary security measures, such as physical ones, ensuring the device's resilience to tampering and environmental factors. Lastly, it includes detailed user guidance and documentation for CMD maintenance throughout the entire lifecycle, detailing secure update mechanisms and specific end-of-life processes.

In summary, the protection profiles include specific operational parameters to be attested during runtime verification for various predefined levels of trustworthiness. They are also completely modular, dependent on the targeted network topology, and structured in layers that define which specific properties should be verified per case and level of interaction (e.g., devices from the same

manufacturer or network). In the end, the Protection Profiles are stored on the manufacturer's MUD server, available to users and deployed along with the authorization server. To ensure the integrity of the Protection Profiles and the wide applicability of the solution, the Profiles are also stored in a distributed ledger. It should be mentioned that once the device leaves the manufacturing floor, it contains two important properties: the unique ID, through which it can be authenticated in front of the manufacturer during deployment, and the MUD URL to access the server and download the specific protection profile. Further details will be provided in the next phase of pre-deployment.

5.1.2 Pre-deployment in the Domain

Once the CMD is delivered to a medical organization, there are several steps that should be carefully considered by the security administrator, who has in-depth knowledge of the targeted domain and its specific requirements. The first step involves downloading the device-specific Protection Profile, which includes all security recommendations, risk profiles, and considerations necessary for the secure deployment of the CMD. The security administrator then re-assesses the identified risks of the device, taking into account the environment where the device will be deployed, its interactions with other devices and systems, and its specific functionalities within the network. This leads to an updated risk scoring for both existing and new threats. This stage may involve updated attack testing and resilience checks against the revised threat model, utilizing the Digital Twin. At this stage, the Digital Twin serves as a digital representation not only of the CMD itself but also of the overall environment. This, coupled with the risk assessment's attack path calculation functionality, enables a more in-depth analysis of potential attack paths between devices and how vulnerabilities can propagate from one device to another. It also helps in determining specific security measures needed to ensure the safe operation of the CMD, such as disabling wireless interfaces in favour of wired connections.

When this process is completed, the further customization of the Protection Profiles is handled by the Protection Profiles Translator. This component is responsible for mapping the general properties included in the Profiles to the domain-specific needs and combining the updated risk scores and attack paths with the predefined level of trust. The output is an updated list of levels of criticality based on the specific services that the CMD will provide in the domain (updating RTL per service). Finally, this component provides a specific list of properties that need to be attested during runtime, along with the attestation challenges and sources of trust to be considered at the device level for each level of trustworthiness. This information is then stored in the Domain Manager, more specifically in the Trust Controls subcomponent, which is responsible for assessing trust within the domain and enforcing the required updates. The Domain Manager is a centralized server deployed at the infrastructure level, responsible for registering devices in the network and ensuring their secure enrolment through the authorization module. It also monitors the security levels of devices throughout their entire lifecycle. This means it encompasses the trust assessment engine, which includes the logic and controls that need to be enforced in the event of identified vulnerabilities or threats.

5.1.3 Runtime

During the CMD enrollment in the domain, a secure process is initiated. This involves verifying the device directly with the manufacturer, using its unique initial identification (UID). Critical to this process is the use of Trusted Component, particularly the PUF, which maintains a unique, integrity-protected identification number. The device, once authenticated, undergoes an initial verification check against security properties outlined in the protection profiles. This may cover aspects like boot-up traces or details about the operating system and firmware, collected during the secure boot process. Successful completion of these steps leads to the device's registration on the network, creation of domain and signing keys for essential functionalities, and operation in accordance with predefined behavioral profiles.

During runtime, the device's adherence to specified security properties is monitored through attestation challenges issued by the Trust Controls component. These challenges are sent to the CMD for execution and to confirm the device's correct configuration and security state. The Device Tracer collects relevant evidence, including specific device properties and data, as part of this attestation challenge. The traces are then forwarded to the Attestation Agent, which constructs a response to confirm the device's state accuracy. A key role here is played by the Trusted Component, which securely signs the attestation reports and encrypts the collected traces.

Additionally, the Wallet, safeguarded by the Trusted Component, facilitates secure interactions between the CMD and the ledger, particularly for secure on-chain activities like recording attestation outcomes. This process employs attribute-based encryption and access control to ensure appropriate access levels within the DLT. For example, certain traces might require specific authorization for access, such as software verification by the domain manager, while other devices in the network may only access limited details, like the verification result. The actual verification is performed on the Domain Manager side which is responsible for verifying the outcome of the attestation process. Therefore, the collection of evidence and the results of the verification are used as an input from the Trust Assessment Engine so as to quantify the Actual Level of Trust of the CMD.

5.1.3.1 Trust Assessment and Conformity Certificates

In ENTRUST, trust assessment is performed in a centralized manner at the Domain Manager level. This component aggregates evidence from devices to calculate the Actual Level of Trust (ATL). The attestation process is guided by a Protection Profile, which specifies a set of properties to be traced and evaluated for correctness. The Required Level of Trust (RTL) depends on the number of necessary properties and their criticality, while the ATL is based on the parameters verified as correct. It is important to note that various trust models could be employed depending on the network topology and the presence of multiple CMDs and entities in the network and whether it is possible to consider their network experience in the trust calculation. This aspect will be analysed in upcoming deliverables (D3.1 [122]).

Once the ATL meets or exceeds the RTL, the evidence and a signed report are recorded in the ledger. This enables issuing a signed conformity certificate for the device, based on verifiable evidence. This information is shared within the domain, informing neighbouring and interacting devices about the CMD's security status. This creates a trusted relationship between the CMDs based on the actual trustworthiness of the CMDs without any assumptions of their trusted state.

If the ATL falls short of the RTL, actions specified in the Protection Profile are initiated. These vary based on the device's criticality and safety requirements, and the potential risks involved. For instance, the SW/FW controls component might enforce secure updates or roll back to a stable version. Additionally, evidence of vulnerabilities is sent to the manufacturer via a Threat Sharing mechanism for patch development and to alert other users. Traces are also analysed for SW verification to pinpoint vulnerability origins, while raw traces are sent to the Digital Twin for simulation and forensic analysis. This helps identify the attestation failure's cause, and the DLT subsequently updates the Protection Profile with new attestation challenges to ensure the issue is resolved.

In larger networks with multiple devices, the trust model and attestation scheme may differ, requiring data collection from various entities. Here, the collected data is recorded in a distributed ledger, accessible to all network entities. The trust assessment logic then retrieves this information, calculates the ATL based on multiple devices trust opinions, and performs the final assessment using a subjective logic approach. Considering CMD processing limitations, an

advanced “swarm attestation” scheme is considered. Recall that ENTRUST recognizes two CMD types: high-end devices (capable of extensive computational, attestation, and cryptographic tasks, like medical organization gateways) and low-end devices (with minimal processing power, like wearable patient monitors). In mixed networks, trust assessment and attestation tasks are offloaded to the high-end devices, which monitor the security status of the less powerful ones.

This approach ensures continuous monitoring of CMDs in the domain and the accuracy of their security posture. Continuous verification against Protection Profile properties and the issuance of Conformity Certificates based on verifiable device-collected evidence are crucial components of this process.

5.2 Process view and High-level Sequence of Actions

5.2.1 Design-time and Pre-deployment in the Domain

In Figure 29, we provide a high-level sequence diagram comprising the actions that take place as part of (i) the design-time phase, which includes all actions taken during the manufacturing process of the device and before it is connected to the network of the target operation, and (ii) the pre-deployment phase, which includes all actions taken after the device is deployed to the network and before the actual operation of the device begins.

Figure 29: Sequence diagram of the design and pre-deployment phases of a device

Considering the above, these processes consist of the following steps:

Design phase

1. The Manufacturer provides the Threat Modelling component with information including (i) an overview of the threat landscape affecting the device, (ii) a detailed profile of the specific device characteristics (i.e., network interfaces, processing power, running software and

- other capabilities/features that need to be considered), and (iii) security and trust requirements, along with the CMD standards that must be adhered to.
2. The Threat Modelling component conducts an in-depth analysis and modelling of threats, utilizing the data provided by the Manufacturer. This process involves mapping the device characteristics with known types of threats and vulnerabilities, based on existing CVE databases and other sources. The output will be a detailed cartography of attacks and identified vulnerabilities, specifically relevant to this device.
 3. The Risk Assessment component is provided with information on device characteristics and the cartography of attacks and vulnerabilities as produced by the Threat Modelling component.
 4. The Risk Assessment performs a risk quantification process for the device, considering the identified threats and vulnerabilities. Note that this process only refers to the individual device and does not consider device interconnectivity and network topology, since at this point the device has not yet been deployed to the network.
 5. Following this analysis, the device characteristics, the identified threats and vulnerabilities, and the attack paths and interdependency graphs at a device level are forwarded to the Digital Twin.
 6. Simulations are performed on the identified threats and vulnerabilities at Digital Twin in order to perform attack validation and to evaluate the impact of these attacks on the device. The simulation results are forwarded to the Manufacturer so as to perform any required updates before launching the CMD.
 7. The calculated risk scores and impacts per identified vulnerability are forwarded to the Protection Profiles composer by the Risk Assessment.
 8. Based on the identified security and safety requirements, a formal verification of the properties of the device is performed by the Formal Methods. The results (the formally verified properties) are forwarded to the Protection Profiles Composer so that they can be included into the Protection Profile of the device.
 9. The SW/FW Verification module retrieves the software from the CMD and performs an analysis in order to verify the correctness and integrity of the software. Also, it calculated the “golden hash” of them so as it can be used during the runtime to verify the integrity and the correct state them. The result of this analysis is forwarded to the Manufacturer, who evaluates whether a redesign is needed based on this analysis.
 10. Based on the initial risk analysis and the identified vulnerabilities, the Protection Profile Composer calculates the RTL, which represents the required trust level that must be exhibited by a device through the calculation of the ATL, so that the device is deemed trustworthy ($ATL > RTL$). The RTL is deployed with the Trust Model to the Trust Assessment Framework, along with the list of evidence that should be received by the Trust Assessment to calculate the ATL. The evidence may come as different trust sources exposed by the ENTRUST security controls (e.g., attestation, Misbehavior Detection).
 11. The Protection Profiles Composer gathers the available information and constructs the Protection profile, including (i) CMD security objectives and threat model; (ii) security recommendations (rules and policies); (iii) specific security assurance requirements, including operational parameters that should be attested during runtime verification to meet the necessary level of assurance and trustworthiness (attestation challenges); (iv) RTL per service.
 12. The Protection Profile is forwarded to the MUD (Protection Profile) Server of the Manufacturer)
 13. The manufacturer assigns a unique identifier UID to each device for authentication purposes. Additionally, the MUD URL is embedded in the CMD, facilitating server access during deployment to download the specific Protection Profile (see *Manufacturing Bootstrapping* phase).

Figure 30: Pre-deployment phase

Pre-deployment phase

1. Once the device is manufactured and delivered to the medical organization for deployment and integration, the Security Administrator forwards the organization’s security and safety requirements, along with detailed information on the network topology, to the Risk Assessment module.
2. The Risk Assessment module performs the re-quantification of risk considering the network topology and the specifics of the targeted environment and generates an updated attack path calculation based on the interdependencies between the existing assets in the network and the asset cartography.
3. The Risk Assessment calculates the updated risk score, the impact per vulnerability, and the calculated attack paths, and forwards this information to the Domain Manager.
4. Following this analysis, the updated information about the network topology, and the attack paths and interdependency graphs are forwarded to the Digital Twin. This enables the validation of potential attacks and facilitates the assessment of their impact on the network infrastructure.
5. The Domain Manager retrieves the Protection Profiles and extracts the policies embedded within, i.e., security recommendations and mitigation actions.
6. The Security Administrator customizes these policies and forwards them to the Trust Controls component (Trust Assessment).
7. The Trust Controls component calculates the Required Trust Level (RTL) considering the updated information, based on the criticality of the services running on the device, as well as the safety criticality of the device in the context of the network topology of the organization.
8. Based on this, the domain-specific Protection Profile of the device is updated with the appropriate runtime assurance claims and attestation actions.
9. The updated Protection Profile is deployed to the Domain Manager.

5.2.2 Secure Enrolment

The next phase of the operational lifecycle of the device is the **secure enrolment**, which entails the actions required for the registration of the CMD into the medical organisation, including the generation of the required cryptographic material and keys for the device to be able to utilize the security enablers of ENTRUST. This includes two sub-phases: (i) the **Manufacturer Bootstrapping**, which refers to the actions on the manufacturer side for assigning and certifying the unique IDs of the device. Then we construct and deploy the Protection Profile, which is assigned to the characteristics of the specific device. (ii) The **Domain Bootstrapping** phase, which refers to the actions required for the registration of the CMD into the infrastructure of the target organisation, as well as the generation of the aforementioned cryptographic material.

Figure 31: Manufacturer Bootstrapping and Domain Bootstrapping

In the following, we provide a high-level description of the action workflow of the Secure Enrolment process:

Manufacturer Bootstrapping:

1. We consider that the CMD is equipped with the MUD URL that points to the Protection Profile of the device, as has been already constructed by the Protection Profile Composition Engine and published to the MUD Server. This URL is stored to the CMD, facilitating server access during deployment to download the specific Protection Profile during the runtime.
2. A unique identifier UID for the CMD has already been assigned by the manufacturer and is agreed upon between the CMD and the AAA Server.
3. The CMD communicates with the AAA Server in order to issue identity certificates, which are then been stored to the device.

Domain Bootstrapping:

1. The Domain Manager receives the UID and the MUD URL of the CMD and performs an authentication of these values (the authentication of the UID is delegated to the manufacturer's AAA Server).
2. Using the MUD URL that it received from the CMD, the Domain Manager retrieves the Protection Profile of the device from the public MUD Server of the manufacturer.
3. The Domain Manager customizes the Protection Profile based on the network topology and domain-specific requirements. The relevant policies are applied in the domain based on the Protection Profile. (The updated Protection Profile based on the previous stage is stored to the DLT in the domain so as it becomes available to the other entities).
4. The CMD performs the secure boot process. Afterwards, it calculates the hash of the output of the secure boot, i.e., the hash of the image that was booted in the device.
5. This image, along with other pseudo-randomized parameters originating from the PUF of the device, are provided as input to a Key Derivation Function (KDF), used by the CMD in order to construct the appropriate cryptographic primitives that can enable secure authentication with the AAA Server, with the support of the Manufacturer. It should be noted that the AAA Server is specific to the domain where the device aims to become enrolled, meaning that each domain has its own AAA Server.
6. The CMD sends a Join request to the AAA Server, who constructs the necessary security policies through the Protection Profile of the device, specifying which attestation evidence must be collected by the Domain Manager in order to check that the device is in the expected state before it is enrolled. Note that the AAA Server knows the correct and expected state of the device, since it knows both the expected output of the secure boot process, and the output of the PUF of the CMD.
7. The Domain Manager, after the creation of these policies, sends a challenge to the CMD, along with the type of assurance claims it needs from the CMD (for example, a confirmation that the CMD is able to perform Configuration Integrity Verification).
8. Upon reception of the challenge, the CMD communicates with the Privacy CA in order to initiate the Join process.
9. The Privacy CA communicates with the DLT in order to retrieve the updated Protection Profile for the specific device (as specified in step 3). It extracts the security policies from the Protection Profile and sends them to the CMD. These are key restriction usage policies, which specify that the CMD is only able to use the key if it is in a correct configuration state.
10. The CMD creates the Attestation Key (AK) binded to those key restriction usage policies, and will be certified and verified by the Privacy CA.

11. After the construction of the AK, the Privacy CA issues the set of Verifiable Credentials (VC) of the CMD containing the attributes of the device, and sends them back to the device. Note that the VCs are binded to the HW-based secret of the CMD. Depending on the capabilities of the CMD, this secret may either be its trust anchor or its PUF.
12. Upon reception of the VCs, the CMD responds to the challenge of the Domain Manager. Specifically, if the CMD is able to use the AK (created in the previous two steps) according to the key restriction usage policy, it is able to create a signature on the challenge. This signature represents the evidence required by the Domain Manager that the device is in a correct configuration state.
13. If the verification is successful, the Domain Manager sends the Device ID (DID) to the CMD, and the CMD registers the DID to its own DT.

5.2.3 Runtime (Attestation & Conformity Certificate)

During the operation of the CMD, it is possible that an attestation process will need to be executed in order to verify the correctness of the configuration state of the (**Prover**) CMD to a **Verifier**. Note that **the stakeholder acting as a Verifier depends on the use case**. Specifically, the Verifier may be the **Domain Manager**, a **gateway device**, a **different CMD**, or an **external certification/auditing body** that aims to verify the correctness of the configuration state of the device. The runtime attestation process entails not only the execution of the attestation itself, but also the generation and recording of an attestation report containing the result of the attestation to the ledger, as well as an evaluation of the result based on whether a SW update needs to be enforced in case of a failed attestation.

Figure 32: Runtime attestation and creation of Conformity Certificate

The first part of this process entails the execution of the attestation scheme itself, as well as the secure storage of the attestation report with the attestation result and the data used as attestation evidence, in a manner that enables parties with the required permissions to access the stored data afterwards. This process, which is depicted in Figure 32, consists of the following steps:

1. Note that, in order to perform a runtime trust assessment process, there are two possible cases: (i) CMDs which possess the required resources and capabilities to perform asymmetric crypto (i.e., have the capability to manage credentials and certificates), such as gateway devices, retrieve the **Protection Profile of the CMD from the ledger** and extract the types of evidence needed. (ii) Conversely, devices that do not have such capabilities (and create symmetric keys through their PUF), communicate with the **Domain Manager and collect the required types of evidence directly**.
2. In the former case, the CMD sends the MUD URL to the Domain Manager, who checks whether the corresponding Protection Profile is available on the Blockchain ledger. If yes, the DLT forwards the Protection Profile to the Domain Manager, which includes the specified attestation challenge and sources of trust for the specific CMD. In the latter case, communication with the ledger is not needed.
3. The Domain Manager sends the properties to be attested to the Trust Controls component at the Verifier, signifying the properties of the CMD that need to be traced and measured in order to perform the attestation process.

4. The Verifier initiates the attestation process by issuing an attestation challenge to the Prover CMD, specifying the attributes that need to be traced in the context of the attestation.
5. This information is forwarded to the Device Tracer, who collects the specified data and traces based on the attributes that need to be attested. Afterwards, the traces are sent to the Attestation Agent of the device.
6. Based on the key restriction usage policies constructed during the Domain Bootstrapping phase as previously analyzed, the challenge is signed using the AK of the device. Recall that, based on the key restriction usage policies, the device is only able to use the AK if and only if the specified parameters are in a correct state.
7. The signed response is sent back to the Verifier in order to verify the correctness of the Prover CMD. Based on this response, the ATL of the attested properties is also calculated by the Trust Assessment component. We further elaborate on this process in Figure 34.
8. The Verifier sends the attestation report containing the result of the attestation process and sends it to the ledger to be recorded.
9. After the verification is completed, the Prover CMD is notified about the result of the verification. In case of a failed attestation, the Prover CMD sends the raw trace data used as attestation evidence signed and encrypted, to be stored in the Off-chain Storage Facility.
10. In order to associate the encrypted raw traces with the corresponding attestation report, the Off-chain Storage Facility produces a pointer to the location of the stored data, which is afterwards forwarded to the Domain Manager.
11. The Domain Manager forwards the pointer to the ledger, where the location pointer is appended to the corresponding attestation report. Thus, any party with the appropriate privileges is able to retrieve both an attestation report and the corresponding attestation evidence. Note that access control will be designed and implemented using an Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) mechanism, based on which parties that demonstrate the required set of device attributes in the form of a Verifiable Presentation (VP) will be able to access a particular set of data. Such a VP can be constructed using a subset of attributes contained in the Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of the device, which are issued during the secure enrollment process.
12. The attestation report is sent to the Certification and Auditing component. If the attestation is successful, the Certification and Auditing component creates a conformity certificate, demonstrating the correctness of the device. Afterwards, the conformity certificate is forwarded to the DLT so that it can be stored and shared with the interacting CMDs and entities and in the network. Note that the conformity certificate is accessible to all parties with access to the particular ledger (i.e., parties operating within the domain), but is not accessible to external third parties.

Figure 33: Actions taken in case ATL < RTL

After this process is complete, in case of a failed attestation (i.e., the calculated ATL is lower than the RTL), measures need to be taken in order to identify the cause behind the failed attestation, as well as mitigation measures for any identified threats, and software patches/updates in order to address zero-day vulnerabilities. This process, which is depicted in Figure 33, consists of the following steps:

1. After the ATL has been determined to be lower than the RTL, the Trust Controls component notifies the Certification Auditing component in order to revoke the issued Conformity Certificate, so that it can no longer be claimed that the CMD is in a correct and trustworthy state. In order to create a new Conformity Certificate, the corresponding properties need to be successfully attested in a subsequent attestation process.
2. Afterwards, the DLT is also notified about the revocation request and takes all needed actions in order to revoke the stored Conformity Certificate. After this is complete, the Trust Controls component is notified about the successful revocation.
3. In order to determine the appropriate course of action in case of a failed attestation, the attestation report is sent to the Domain Manager, and more specifically to the Trust Controls, who calculates the Actual Trust Level (ATL) based on the report.
4. Next, the ATL is compared to the Required Trust Level (RTL) in order to determine whether additional actions are required based on the result of the attestation action. Specifically, recall that the attestation has been performed based on a set of properties specified by the Protection Profile, whose values were traced, and their correctness was evaluated. At a high level, the RTL is determined by the number of properties that need to be correct and the criticality of each parameter, and the ATL is determined by the parameters that were determined to be correct. Thus, if the ATL is calculated to be lower than the RTL, this indicates the need to perform a SW update in order to address the cause of the failed attestation. Based on the above, note that it is possible that it is determined that a SW update is not needed if one or more parameters were determined to be incorrect if these are classified as low priority or pose a low security risk.
5. If it is determined that an update is needed, the DLT sends the traces for SW verification to the SW Verification component.
6. The raw traces are sent to the Digital Twin in order to simulate the conditions that led to the failed attestation, by executing forensics that provide further information on the nature of the failure.
7. After these forensics are complete, the DLT updates the Protection Profile in order to include the new attestation challenge that needs to be performed to verify that the issue

has been addressed and the device is in a correct operational state. It is forwarded to the Protection Profile Composition component.

- After this process is complete, the new attestation challenge can be issued by the Domain Manager, specifying new types of collected data, security claims, and properties to be attested.

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Figure 34: ATL calculation

As aforementioned, in order to determine whether further action needs to be taken following an attestation, a Trust Assessment process needs to be performed in order to calculate the ATL of the attested properties. This process is handled by the **Trust Assessment** component, which is installed on the Domain Manager and contains the following subcomponents: the **Request Manager**, the **Trust Model Manager (TMM)**, the **Trust Sources Manager (TSM)**, the **Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine (TLEE)**, and the **Trust Decision Engine (TDE)**. This process is depicted in Figure 34 and consists of the following steps:

- The Trust Assessment Component receives the **Trust Assessment Request (TAR)**, which yields the following information: (i) **TM_ID**, which is the ID of the trust model corresponding to the attested properties, (ii) **prop_data**, which is the proposition pointing to the data whose trustworthiness should be assessed, and (iii) **RTL_data**, which is the Required Trust Level (RTL) against which the ATL will be compared.
- TM_ID and prop_data are forwarded to the TMM, while RTL_data is forwarded to the TDE, which then awaits input from the TLEE.
- Meanwhile, the TMM uses the TM_ID in order to locate the appropriate trust model, which is then forwarded to the TLEE along with prop_data.
- Based on these two inputs, the TLEE identifies all the **trust relationships TR_x** for which a trust opinion needs to be formulated based on a list of **trust sources TSL_x** extracted from the trust model. In this case, the trust sources can be considered as the collection of the appropriate traces for the attestation of a specific property.

5. Using the collected evidence, the TSM uses a pre-defined method to quantify the evidence into a set of atomic trust opinions.
6. These trust opinions are fused in order to produce a trust opinion TO_x for each trust relationship requested by the TLEE.
7. These trust opinions are then forwarded to the TLEE, which uses them in order to produce the Actual Trust Levels **ATL_x** for each property dictated by the received propositions.
8. These ATLs are forwarded to the TDE, which then compares them to the previously received RTLs, in order to produce the **Trust Decisions (TD_x)** which eventually determine whether the attestation process is successful or not.

5.2.4 Runtime (Misbehaviour Detection)

In the context of ENTRUST, Misbehaviour Detection component refers to **anomaly detection based on the analysis of network traffic data using AI-based techniques**. In other words, the Misbehaviour Detection process of ENTRUST is able to use AI-based techniques in order to detect whether the behaviour of network data deviates from behaviours which are expected and known to be correct. In the context of ENTRUST, the Network Traffic Monitor component is responsible for collecting the required network traffic data and sending it to the Misbehaviour Detection component. Then, the AI-based classification model is trained on such traffic data, considering the operational profile of the target network, including information such as typical network load and request frequency. The classification model is trained in order to classify network traffic behaviours as benign or malicious based on whether it conforms to these patterns, and a deviation from the expected operational behaviour may constitute an indication of risk.

Figure 35: AI-based Misbehaviour Detection

The misbehaviour detection process is performed as follows:

1. The Network Traffic Monitor collects network traffic data which can be used for the training of the classification model. This data may originate from the manufacturing process of the device, or from network data exchanged during the normal operation of the device. It is important to note that, due to privacy reasons related to the sensitive nature of medical data, it only collects network traces that are predefined in the Protection Profile of the CMD.
2. The Network Traffic Monitor sends the monitored data to be stored on the DLT, from where it is forwarded to the AI-based Misbehaviour Detection Module.
3. The AI-based Misbehaviour Detection Module trains the classification model that will be used in order to classify benign and malicious data, by constructing a training set containing the received data. Note that the data contained in the training set is considered benign or malicious based on the operational behaviour profile of the network. For example, if the typical network traffic load is known to lie within an expected range, a deviation from this range or a large spike in the recorded traffic volume may constitute an indication of risk. In addition, it is possible to include synthetic traces in the training set, constructed so that they emulate such malicious behaviours.
4. After the classification model has been trained, it can be used in order to perform misbehaviour detection. To this end, the Network Traffic Monitor collects the data to be

evaluated and sends it to the DLT, which forwards it to the AI-based Misbehaviour Detection module.

5. The AI-based Misbehaviour Detection module performs classification in order to identify the received data into benign or malicious.
6. If an abnormal behaviour has been detected, the Protection Profile Composer updates the Protection Profile of the device in order to contain the appropriate mitigation measures (e.g., attestation actions) to be applied in this case.
7. The updated Protection Profile is published to the local MUD Server.

5.3 Functional Components

This section is dedicated to the listing of Functional Components of ENTRUST, including information on the input/output characteristics of each component, type, component interactions, and starting/target TRL. In Table 16, we provide a high-level overview of these components, as well as the phase and layer each component can be categorized into.

Table 16: Functional Components of ENTRUST

Phase	Layers	Component Name
Design-time	Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine	Threat Modelling
		Risk Assessment
		SW verification
		Digital Twin (*cross-cutting)
	Formal Verification Toolset	Formal Models
	Protection Profiles Composer	Protection Profiles Composer MUD Server
Pre-deployment	Security Administrator Domain	Protection Profiles Translator Trust Controls
Runtime	Runtime Verification (CMD)	Trust and Attestation Agent
		Device Data and Execution Tracer
		Authorization Module
		SW/FW update agent
		Wallet
	TC Extension for CMDs	TC-based middleware
	Trust Assessment and Controls (Domain Manager)	Trust Controls (Trust Assessment)
		Network Monitoring
SW/FW controls		
Cross-cutting	DLT	DLT infrastructure
		Certification and Runtime Auditing
		Authorization and Authentication Module
		AI-based misbehavior detection
	Digital Twin	Attack Validation

5.3.1 Design-time

Component Name	Threat Modelling
Component Short Description	Responsible for threat identification , during the design phase, according to the capabilities and modes of operation of each device. During the runtime, it will perform a dynamic assessment by simulating the execution path to identify specific vulnerabilities by leveraging the attack validation component (DT).
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	LLM, Flask API, KeyCloak
Phase	Design
Input	Device capabilities (e.g., SW, processing power, network interfaces), Threat landscape, and Security and safety requirements of services.
Output	Asset catalogue and interdependencies, Detailed cartography of attacks to be considered (e.g., code injection, DOP, etc.) and identified threats/vulnerabilities (attack scenarios)
Interactions with Other Components	Risk Assessment, Digital Twin
Where does it run	Back-end
Related task	WP3/T3.2
Owner	SMNS

Component Name	Risk Assessment
Component Short Description	Risk score calculation, attack path calculation, and interdependency graphs to understand cascading effects and how a risk may propagate on interconnected infrastructures. It will include a risk benefit analysis scheme reflecting the opportunities and risks that may arise from the introduction of several novel technological and cross-cutting developments (e.g., 5G, Big Data, Mobile Edge Computing). Note that, as part of the risk assessment process carried out during the design

	phase, the device is evaluated as an individual component, and the network topology is not considered. When a device aims to connect to the network, a re-quantification of risks is performed, considering the network topology and domain specific requirements.
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 5 Expected TRL: 8
Technologies (internal components)	CVSS 3.1, Attack Path calculation based on Drools Expert System
Phase	Design, Pre-deployment
Input	Asset catalogue, further information about asset relations, interdependencies, intangible assets (e.g., SW installed on the devices or physical location of the asset) as well as attack path scenarios (from Threat Modelling); Runtime data (i.e., alerts from Tracer and outcomes from the attestation and Trust assessment)
Output	Risk scores, attack path calculation, and interdependency graphs, impact per vulnerability. Risk-benefit analysis
Interactions with Other Components	Threat Modelling, Attack Validation, Protection Profiles
Where does it run	Back-end
Related task	WP3/T3.4
Owner	UBI

Component Name	SW verification
Component Short Description	Testing the various SW and FW modules using fuzzing techniques and coverage tests to identify vulnerabilities; SW validation mechanisms through the creation of a golden hash (correct configuration) leveraging Code integrity Validation (CIV) techniques such as memory fuzzing, concolic testing, etc. During runtime, it will collect the tracing evidence to perform a sanitation (remove bugs and vulnerabilities - creating patches)
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3

	Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	Static analysis (e.g., YARA), Flask API, Keycloak
Phase	Design
Input	SW or FW running on CMDs
Output	Golden hash, Validation result, SW patches incl. the results
Interactions with Other Components	Attack Validation Component, Tracer
Where does it run	Back-end
Related task	WP3/T3.2
Owner	SMNS

Component Name	Formal Models
Component Short Description	Formally verified models of services running on devices, e.g. secure boot, attestation, software update, secure communication, onboarding. The models will provide protocol specs and all crypto primitives (e.g. keys, certificates) used in them along with assumptions/requirements about the hosting SW/HW infra. Proofs demonstrate that the chosen crypto mechanisms satisfy the identified security requirements. Limitations in the verification are clearly stated (e.g. used assumptions, bounds). Interactions are modeled and possibly verified using dedicated tools or general-purpose verification tools.
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	-
Phase	Design
Input	Security and safety requirements for services, quantified risk (T3.4)

Output	Properties, models and evidence of their correctness wrt properties
Interactions with Other Components	Trust abstractions, protection profiles (T3.3). Possibly interaction with SW verification (T3.2) since the design intention needs to be properly implemented in SW
Where does it run	Back-end
Related task	WP3/T3.1
Owner	TUE

Component Name	Protection Profiles Composer
Component Short Description	It will model the (static and dynamic execution) properties and trust indicators that need to be verified during runtime and are not covered by the formally verified models. This will lead to the creation of Modular Protection Profiles, which will contain the validation properties that need to be monitored and verified during runtime, as evidence of the trustworthiness of the target device (assurance claims verified by specific attestation schemes). The protection profiles are modular as they consider the network topology and are structured in layers that define which specific properties should be verified per case and level of interaction (e.g., devices coming from the same manufacturer, or network).
Type	.json files
Starting/Expected TRL	3/5
Technologies (internal components)	Script format
Phase	Design
Input	The formally verified trust models (crypto primitives and operations) defined in T3.1 will be taken into consideration. The defined use cases, scenarios (T6.1) and the mix-criticality services (T2.1) will also provide input for this task, along with the patient's privacy aspects from T2.4.
Output	Modular Protection Profiles containing the validation properties and assurance claims (bound to specific attestation schemes): attestation evidence and types of attestation (properties to be attested), Operational properties, runtime trust indicators (trusted boot and integrity; control- and information-flow

	properties) and RTL. The Protection profiles will be shared with the manufacturers as an extension of MUDs.
Interactions with Other Components	Threat Modelling, Risk Assessment, Runtime attestation, Certification and Auditing (to extend MUD profiles), Trust Assessment
Where does it run	Back-end
Related task	WP3/T3.3
Owner	UPRC

5.3.2 Pre-deployment phase

Component Name	Protection Profiles Translator
Component Short Description	When the device is connected to the target network (e.g. hospital), the protection profile of the device is downloaded, considering the network topology and domain-specific requirements of the application. The Protection Profiles Translator is responsible for receiving the appropriate protection profiles and translating them to attestation tasks and trust controls, that will be used throughout the operational lifecycle of the device.
Type	Component
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	-
Phase	Pre-deployment
Input	Retrieval of the protection profiles from the cloud, containing information on the network topology and domain-specific requirements.
Output	Translated protection profiles sent to the Trust Controls and Attestation Tasks module in order to generate the appropriate attestation tasks.
Interactions with Other Components	-
Where does it run	Back-end

Related task	WP3/T3.3
Owner	UBI/UPRC

Component Name	Trust Controls
Component Short Description	After the Protection Profiles Translator has completed its processing of the appropriate protection profile, this component is responsible for the definition of the trust controls and attestation tasks to be performed on the device. For example, this may include Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) in order to verify the correctness of the configuration state of the device.
Type	Component
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	-
Phase	Runtime
Input	Receive translated protection profiles from the Protection Profiles Translator module
Output	Communication with the Attestation Agent of the device to forward the appropriate attestation tasks.
Interactions with Other Components	Attack Validation
Where does it run	Back-end
Related task	WP4/T4.4
Owner	SIN

5.3.3 Runtime phase

Component Name	Runtime Attestation
Component Short Description	Verify the secure state of the devices by attesting the correct execution behavior as well as the communication patterns and their relationships.
Type	Software

Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 4 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	-
Phase	Runtime
Input	Modular Protection Profiles containing the validation properties and assurance claims (binded to specific attestation schemes) to be provided during the runtime; Traces from Device Data execution Tracer, TC-based middleware
Output	Attestation Result and Evidence
Interactions with Other Components	Protection Profiles Composer, Tracer, Wallet
Where does it run	CMD (inside the Secure World)
Related task	WP4/T4.3
Owner	SUR/UBI

Component Name	Device Data and Execution Tracer
Component Short Description	Tracing the operational properties of the device (e.g., loaded binaries and libraries during startup) and control and information flow execution paths needed by the runtime attestation enablers.
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	2/4
Technologies (internal components)	eBPF/RTOS
Phase	Runtime
Input	Operational properties and runtime trust indicators from Protection Profiles
Output	Traces (List of loaded binaries and libraries, list of executed binaries/libraries and other evidence from monitoring hooks)
Interactions with Other Components	Protection Profiles, Runtime attestation enablers, digital twin

Where does it run	CMD (inside the Secure World)
Related task	WP5/T5.4
Owner	UPRC

Component Name	Wallet
Component Short Description	Wallet for the secure management and storage of cryptographic material, such as verifiable evidence of device identity, device attributes (static attributes), verifiable credentials and attestation keys. The wallet facilitates self-sovereign identities and enables devices to self-issue verifiable presentations based on their attributes, ensuring fine-grained access control (e.g., encrypting Traces based on ABAC). The wallet communicates with the ledger to store the evidence and "download" the protection profiles (incl. the attestation tasks). In addition, the Wallet is responsible for the encryption of data using the Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE), which is able to encrypt data in a manner that enables devices to decrypt them, only if they can verifiably demonstrate possession of the required attributes through a Verifiable Presentation (VP).
Type	Component
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 4 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	-
Phase	Runtime
Input	Raw traces and attestation evidence, VCs
Output	Verifiable Presentations
Interactions with Other Components	Tracer, DLT, Attestation agent
Where does it run	As part of TC in CMD
Related task	WP5/T5.3
Owner	UBI/SUR

Component Name	TC-based middleware
Component Short Description	Hybrid Trusted Computing element of TEE enclaves and PUFs for enabling (i) secure boot considering a variety of threats (based on the risk assessment conducted in T3.4), (ii) runtime attestation, (iii) secure data access and verifiable computing of the necessary monitoring data, and (iv) device identity management and secure communication channel (PUFs)
Type	Component
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 4 Expected TRL: 6
Technologies (internal components)	SRAM-PUF or photonic PUF modules, unique key generation module, ARM TrustZone
Phase	Runtime
Input	Authorization and Authentication Module
Output	High-entropy keys for supporting ENTRUST’s cryptographic operations
Interactions with Other Components	Runtime Attestation, DLT, Trust agent
Where does it run	CMD and/ or CMD nodes
Related task	WP4/T4.1
Owner	QUBI/UBI

Component Name	Trust Assessment
Component Short Description	All attested properties will be translated into logic-based approaches (e.g., Subjective Logic) so that the trust assessment framework can reason about the monitored security claims and perform any actions in case of any newly identified risk or failed attestation (possible indication of compromise). These will be done through the newly designed domain-specific property specification language.
Type	Component
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5

Technologies (internal components)	Trust Level Expression Engine (TLEE), Trust Assessment Decision Engine (TADE), Trust Source Manager (TSM), Trust Model Manager (TMM)
Phase	Runtime
Input	Data from Trust agent (Trust Controls)
Output	Trust Assessment outcome (ATL)
Interactions with Other Components	DLT
Where does it run	back-end
Related task	WP4/T4.2
Owner	UBI

Component Name	Network Monitoring
Component Short Description	This component will collect network traffic data which will allow the training of behavioural analysis models (to identify abnormalities and malicious activities)
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	Machine Learning (e.g., Markov Chains), Messaging system (e.g., Kafka), Network Traffic Monitoring
Phase	Runtime
Input	network traffic data
Output	network traffic data
Interactions with Other Components	DLT
Where does it run	Master devices (e.g., gateways)
Related task	WP3/T3.2
Owner	SMNS

Component Name	Trust Agent
Component Short Description	This component will act as the agent at the device level to collect evidence according to the required security claims described in the Protection Profiles. It will provide input to the Trust Assessment
Type	Component
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	-
Phase	Runtime
Input	Protection Profiles (stored in DLT)
Output	Trust agent will provide input to Trust assessment as well
Interactions with Other Components	DLT
Where does it run	CMD (in TC)
Related task	WP4/T4.2
Owner	UBI

Component Name	SW/FW controls
Component Short Description	This component will manage the lifecycle of software on CMDs, from initial deployment to final retirement. Also, it ensures the auditability and the secure deployment of this type of SW or FW updates to deploy any SW or FW updates efficiently and securely to only the target CMDs that have deemed as possibly compromised (e.g. based on failed attestation).
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	Starting TRL: 2 Expected TRL: 5

Technologies (internal components)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital twin platform for fleet monitoring and management (Eclipse Ditto) - Device-side monitoring agents (Influx Telegraf) - Device-side deployment agents
Phase	Runtime
Input	Trust assessment results (T4.2) and Attack simulation results (T3.5)
Output	Possible software management commands: update, roll-back, reset, lock, etc.;
Interactions with Other Components	Trust assessment (T4.2) and Attack simulation (T3.5).
Where does it run	Digital twin platform - Back-end Monitoring and deployment agents – On devices
Related task	WP4/T4.4
Owner	SINTEF

Component Name	DLT infrastructure
Component Short Description	<p>The blockchain infrastructure that will accommodate the various blockchain-enabled services of ENTRUST. Smart Contracts: (a) recording and auditing of attestation evidence (traces); (b) deployment and enforcement of attestation policies; (c) recording and sharing of Protection profiles; (d) recording and sharing of Conformity Certificates; (d) deployment and enforcement of SW/FW updates and trust controls;</p> <p>In general, secure and privacy-preserving data sharing & recording operational data from the device-level (e.g., network traffic)</p>
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	From TRL: 2 to TRL: 4
Technologies (internal components)	Public channel, Private Channel, Off-chain Storage, developed with Hyperledger Fabric blockchain framework
Phase	Pre-deployment, runtime

Input	TC (attestation evidence and traces), Protection Profiles Composer (Protection Profiles), Conformity Certificates (Certification and Runtime Auditing), sw and trust controls
Output	pointers of the new block - data that will be stored in the ledger, pointers to the off-chain storage (traces), signature
Interactions with Other Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Attribute-based Access Control (ABAC) and CTI sharing (e.g., MUDs will be integrated with a CTI infrastructure through the Blockchain). ii) SW and Trust Controls Update for Remote CMDs (T4.4) iii) Smart contract mechanisms
Where does it run	Decentralized back-end
Related task	WP5/T5.1 & T5.2
Owner	SUITE5/UBI (SC)

Component Name	Certification and Runtime Auditing
Component Short Description	This component will manage MUD/threat MUD files. MUD files will be generated from assessment results and threat information
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	From TRL: 3 To TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	MUD Manager (developed with Python)
Phase	Pre-deployment, Runtime
Input	Protection Profiles, Attestation evidence (stored in DLT)
Output	MUD/threat MUD
Interactions with Other Components	Risk and Threat Intelligence Engine, DLT, CTI
Where does it run	Backend and repository of MUD servers
Related task	WP4/T4.3
Owner	UMU

Component Name	Authorization and Authentication Module
Component Short Description	This component includes the encryption and access control schemes (ABE/ABAC). It develops a secure and practical anonymous verifiable credential (VC) that verifies all attributes involved in a CMD system and ensures the secure on-chain interaction.
Type	Component
Starting/Expected TRL	From TRL: 3 To TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	-
Phase	Pre-deployment, Runtime
Input	TC-based middleware, Runtime Attestation, Certification and Runtime Auditing
Output	anonymous verifiable credential scheme
Interactions with Other Components	-
Where does it run	Backend
Related task	WP5/T5.3
Owner	SUR

Component Name	AI-based misbehaviour detection
Component Short Description	The AI-based behaviour analysis component is based on evidence data stored in the blockchain. This component aims to identify anomalies on the behaviour of CMDs (based on network traffic)
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	From TRL: 3 to TRL: 5
Technologies (internal components)	ML libraries for the development of the misbehaviour detection algorithms (scikit-learn, pandas, numpy)
Phase	Runtime
Input	Input from DLT about network traffic;

Output	Analysis data given to Continuous Risk Assessment and Protection Profiles component to reconstruct the attestation policies
Interactions with Other Components	i) DLT ii) Attack Validation component iii) Network Traffic Monitoring
Where does it run	Backend - running on DLT nodes (Federated Learning)
Related task	WP5/T5.5
Owner	SUITE5

Component Name	Digital Twin Attack Validation
Component Short Description	The attack validation component is part of the threat intelligence engine of ENTRUST for simulating and emulating various attack vectors based on the real-time monitored system traces. It will include a scalable testbed and a digital representation of the deployed CMDs, safety-critical components and services.
Type	Software
Starting/Expected TRL	2/4
Technologies (internal components)	Knowledge graph, Influxdb
Phase	Runtime
Input	(i) the runtime execution state of a device (T4.3), (ii) a detailed threat modelling in T3.2 that includes the exact type of sw-based attacks (e.g., code injection, data-oriented attacks), (iii) the compiled security (attestation) policies (T3.3)
Output	failed/successful attacks
Interactions with Other Components	Risk Assessment (T3.4), Threat Modelling (T3.2), SW and Trust Controls (T4.4), Trust Abstraction and Protection Profiles (T3.3)
Where does it run	Back-end
Related task	WP3/T3.5
Owner	SINTEF

6 Use Cases

Throughout this deliverable, we provided a detailed overview of the approach followed by ENTRUST with regards to the definition of all requirements (framework, security, operational, legal, and ethical), as well as the definition of the conceptual architecture of ENTRUST, including all envisioned components and methodologies to be included as part of the framework. Having defined all these core aspects, we are now able to outline the plan for the validation of the ENTRUST framework in the context of the four envisioned use case demonstrators, specifically: (i) **Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring of Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting**, (ii) **Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living**, (iii) **Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carriers**, and (iv) **Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data**.

As part of this approach, for each of the aforementioned use cases, we will define a set of **user stories** corresponding to practical scenarios that may occur during the normal operation of the demonstrators. These user stories have been selected in order to cover the entirety of the operations of ENTRUST and evaluate the efficiency and performance of each of these operations in real-world applications. In addition, we define a set of preliminary **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** for each of the use case demonstrators, providing some insight on the numerical performance targets against which the ENTRUST framework will be evaluated in the context of the experimental activities carried out as part of WP6. Note that the values provided in this deliverable are indicative and will be elaborated in D6.1 [123], where we will provide a more detailed experimentation plan in the context of the envisioned use cases.

6.1 Overview of the Use Cases

As aforementioned, four use cases demonstrators have been envisioned in order to integrate, validate, and evaluate the developed ENTRUST framework. These use cases have application to different aspects of medical domain sector and multiple scenarios are described where the project aims to test and validate the desired security functionalities. In addition, based on the security and functional requirements, use cases description and architecture is adjusted properly to the needs of Entrust project.

In the remainder of this Chapter, we will present an overview of the envisioned Use Cases, as well as a detailed description of the environment of each one that will enable us to test the components and the overall Entrust framework. Additionally, user stories will be defined in each use case, in which we will showcase the different security functionalities under various conditions and environments.

6.2 Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting

6.2.1 Current Status

Kardinerio manufactures PC Based ECG and ECG Stress Test Systems with treadmill for more than 30 years. Our actual ECG acquisition module is a Bluetooth BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy)-wireless device; KardinBlu ECG and multi-parameter monitoring system.

Ankara University Hospital- Cardiology Clinic is one of our clients where we have 3 of ECG stress test systems with treadmill in use. The systems in the hospital are connected to PACS system, where the users can see the stress testing records/reports from their computers remotely. Now, our new Bluetooth ECG device will also be used for data acquisition, with the same infrastructure and with the new version of our software, which is compatible for the BLE use.

Our multi-parameter patient remote monitoring module is also ready to use for several scenarios in the same hospital. These modules can be connected to the hospital network via our system and the records and analyses can be shared with the doctors. They are wearable devices which send the data via a mobile device; a smartphone or a tablet PC. The records made with these devices include ECG, SpO2, temperature, and acceleration. The devices and analysis server are ready to be used with simulators and dummy data, an official clinical study is planned to begin during the next year.

6.2.2 Scenario's Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST

For the home use, a smart device will be used to store and interpret data. Data will also be transmitted to and read from the cloud by this device. For hospital use, a PC equipped with a BLE dongle will replace the smart device. These are threats or requirements for such operation for both cases;

Having a MITM in the network; whether in wired or wireless connections.

The smart device or the PC in the Hospital Network or smart device Patient is using may happen to have malicious software that can steal and/or manipulate the data or cause malfunctioning.

Third-party devices are also connected to the same gateway. How is the trustworthy state of these devices ensured beyond the typical authentication schemes? How the gateway is sure about the trustworthy state of the interacting devices?

Acquisition device should ensure the integrity of commands received. Also, when the smart device or the PC receives data from the acquisition device, the integrity of the data should be ensured. When the smart device or the PC reads the data back from cloud, the integrity of the data should be ensured.

Both the acquisition device and the smart device/ PC must ensure that they are connected to targeted authorized device safely. Acquisition device OTA update should be ensured to be free of threats. Using devices or users with default or easily guessable passwords should be prevented. DDoS attacks on connected medical devices, flooding them with traffic and rendering them unavailable for use should be prevented. It should be taken measures to prevent DDoS attacks targeting connected medical devices, which inundate them with traffic and make them inaccessible for use.

Sufficient mechanisms to verify the identity and permissions of users should be established to prevent unauthorized access or privilege escalation. The data transmitted between the medical device and other systems should be properly encrypted. Proper monitoring and intrusion detection mechanisms should be developed to identify and respond to potential security breaches.

6.2.3 Threat landscape

WHO: The threat actors inclined to attack your equipment/ organisation (e.g., insiders, outsiders, etc.)

- insufficiently educated users, who may cause cybersecurity threats unintentionally by making mistakes during the use
- people to intend to get some clinical data of famous people, violating privacy of personal or sensitive data
- people to interfere with the device's operation
- potential intruders may attempt unauthorized alterations to audit logs
- manufacturer and service providers

- terrorists to destroy the clinics reputation and to cause some harm to the system

HOW: The techniques that they typically employ (e.g., MiTM attacks, ransomware, etc.)

- Interfering to the system, attacking network connection
- Reaching to computers in the system and using hacking methods to access clinical data
- Causing defects to the devices used; affecting and changing their controllable parameters
- Insufficient vendor support and updates
- Not providing regular security updates or fail to support the device and users over time, it can leave the device vulnerable to new threats

WHY: The objectives they are likely to pursue in their attacks (e.g., cybercriminals that are financially motivated to steal sensitive data)

- Criminal intentions like terrorist actions
- To blackmail famous people using their private and sensitive data
- To blackmail health institutions
- To harm people’s health
- To get financial gain

WHERE: The resources they are likely to target (e.g., critical resources; related to the points above)

- It can be either in the house or environment of the remote patient or in the hospital
- It can be directly in the hospital, via a network connected computer or a tablet used in the hospital
- Patient health record
- Hospital IT Systems
- Radiology and Imaging Systems
- Employee and Patient Data

6.2.4 “To-be” Scenario and User Stories

In the following, we provide an overview of the user stories envisioned for the evaluation of the Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring use cases. This can be split into two categories: (i) the **Secure Enrolment of ECG Monitoring Portable Devices**, and the **Compositional Security and Cooperative Execution of Safety-Critical Operations in Hospital Settings**.

6.2.4.1 Secure Enrolment of ECG Monitoring Portable Devices

- **Applicability of ENTRUST will be assessed to protect the integrity of such a lightweight device.**
- **Enforcement of a remote firmware update through ENTRUST will be demonstrated in the case of a security incident.**

This scenario, focus on the KardinBlu Bluetooth-enabled device, explores the effectiveness of ENTRUST in safeguarding the integrity of lightweight devices. The KardinBlu device is based on the Nordic Bluetooth semiconductor. While Bluetooth is a widely used and generally reliable communication method, it is not without weaknesses (even in its latest version). Existing vulnerabilities in the protocol expose it to various threats, including man-in-the-middle attacks, unauthorized pairing, impersonation, and spoofing. These vulnerabilities can compromise the confidentiality and integrity of data. Furthermore, Bluetooth’s bidirectional capability increases the risk of malicious activities like executing system commands or deploying harmful firmware updates.

The scenario's primary focus is on deploying the device within a specific domain, ensuring thorough checks during the onboarding process. It is assumed that the manufacturer has already implemented essential design-time measures, such as integrating a unique ID for authentication and a MUD URL for accessing server resources and downloading specific Protection Profiles. Additionally, the manufacturer has detailed the device's boot-up process, collecting required traces that will be used during deployment to verify the correct configuration. This is achieved by deploying an RTOS on the microcontroller, enabling the collection of necessary boot-up traces by the agents.

In the deployment of the CMD to a healthcare facility, the security administrator, with expertise in the specific domain, undertakes several critical steps. Initially, they download the Protection Profile tailored for the CMD, including all necessary security guidelines, risk assessments, and deployment strategies. Then, reassess the CMD's risks considering its operational environment, interactions with other systems, and network functionalities, leading to an updated risk evaluation. The customization of the Protection Profile is then refined by the Protection Profiles Translator. This component adapts general security measures to the specific needs of the healthcare domain, integrating revised risk scores and potential attack vectors with established trust levels. It generates a detailed list of criticality levels for the CMD's services and specifies runtime attestation requirements, including challenges and trust sources for each trustworthiness level.

This information is stored in the Domain Manager, particularly in the Trust Controls section. This component plays a critical role in maintaining domain trust and implementing necessary security updates. Overall, this process emphasizes secure CMD enrolment and domain bootstrapping, ensuring robust protection against potential threats in a healthcare setting. Extending this scenario involves enhancing security measures to mitigate possible vulnerabilities. This includes the update of the firmware to address new threats. Following any necessary updates, the device undergoes a re-evaluation using the established procedure to confirm its integrity. This reassessment uses the newly collected boot-up traces, ensuring that the device maintains its security integrity during the post-update.

User Story 1:

As a security administrator, I would like to assess the integrity of the device during the bootup.

In this user story, the domain manager authenticates the UID and MUD URL of the CMD through the manufacturer's AAA Server. It then retrieves the Protection Profile using the MUD URL and customizes it based on network and domain-specific requirements. These customized policies are applied in the domain and stored on the DLT for access by other CMDs in the domain. The CMD undergoes a secure bootup, collecting bootup traces, and derives necessary cryptographic materials. This is the most critical step as the collected information during the bootup are verified against the ones collected during the design-time to ensure that the device operated correctly.

Upon sending a join request, the domain manager issues a challenge to the CMD, and upon successful verification, assigns a DID. This DID, along with the CMD's identity and signing keys, is registered on the DLT. The Domain manager generates the VCs, stored in the CMD's Trusted Component. These VCs allow the CMD to construct VPs for accessing specific services or data sets. Lastly, the verification outcomes, including attestation results and encrypted bootup traces, are recorded in the domain's DLT for sharing with other devices, enhancing overall network security and trustworthiness. This process ensures secure integration and operation of CMDs within the domain, safeguarding sensitive medical data and operations.

User Story 2:

In the case of a security incident, I would like to enforce an action (either a fallback action to a different trusted application version, or a remote firmware update) and assess that the device operates correctly after the update.

In order to ensure the correct operation of the KardinBlu device and the integrity of the monitored medical data, we need to ensure that the ENTRUST framework has the capability to detect new vulnerabilities during runtime, as well as deploy the necessary measures for the mitigation of those vulnerabilities. Recall that the attestation enablers of ENTRUST are able to attest to the correctness of a set of device attributes based on the collection of the appropriate evidence through the Device Tracer. Afterwards, the Actual Trust Level (ATL) is calculated based on these attributes, and it is compared to the Required Trust Level (RTL), and if $ATL < RTL$, it is determined that a secure SW/FW update is required. Note that the Trust Assessment component is able to capture security incidents, but device failures (e.g., a faulty sensor) are beyond the scope of ENTRUST.

This user story includes the operations performed by the ENTRUST framework in order to mitigate vulnerabilities after a failed attestation. Specifically, the Trust Controls component first notifies the Certification and Auditing component so that it can revoke the Conformity Certificate of the CMD, so that it can no longer be considered trustworthy. This certificate is also revoked from the ledger so that it cannot be accessed by external parties. Afterwards, the Software Enforcement component is notified about the failure of the attestation so that the SW/FW update process can be initiated. In this regard, the traces that led to the failed attestation are sent to the SW Verification component, as well as the Digital Twin of the device so that the attack can be simulated. Based on this simulation, the cause of the failure is identified and the Protection Profile of the CMD is updated by the Protection Profile Composition Engine, including any new attestation challenge that is needed in order to attest to the correctness of the state of the device.

User Story 3:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure that the CMD is continuously assessed, issues conformity certificates and enforces any necessary security measures.

As previously outlined, this use case entails the provision of operational assurance for the KardinBlu Bluetooth-enabled device, which is based on the Nordic Bluetooth semiconductor. However, while Bluetooth is a robust and mature communication protocol, it is still possible for vulnerabilities to be identified and exploited, thus leading to the compromise of the normal operation of the device or the integrity of medical data. In this regard, ENTRUST provides continuous assessment mechanisms that attest to the correctness of the configuration state of the device.

Specifically, this User Story entails the execution of an attestation operation, specifically Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV), aiming to attest to the correctness of a number of device parameters, as dictated by the Protection Profile of the device. This process includes issuance of the attestation challenge by the Trust Controls component to the Attestation Agent of the CMD, who then collects the required data based on the properties to be attested using the Device Data, and sends the response to the attestation challenge so that it can be verified. This process also includes the creation of the attestation report and its storage on the ledger, as well as the encryption of the attestation raw data using Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) and their storage on the Off-Chain Storage Facility. Note that the attestation report and the encrypted data are

associated through a location pointer to the stored data, so that a certification authority with the appropriate permissions is able to access the report and the data. If the attestation is successful, a Conformity Certificate is also issued, which can be retrieved by a certification authority in order to verify that the device is in a correct and expected state.

Table 17: Tested functionalities and components for Secure Enrolment of ECG Monitoring Portable Devices use case

User Story	Tested Functionalities	Components	Motivation	Description
1	Pre-deployment, Manufacturer Bootstrapping, Domain Bootstrapping	MUD Server, AAA server, DLT, Domain Manager, Trusted Component, Protection Profile Composer	The onboarding of the KardinBlu device within a specific domain and its deployment should be secured according to the specific needs of the healthcare domain.	The integrity of the device during bootup is assured with the creation and storage of the Protection Profile, the attestation of the secure bootup and the creation of the Verifiable Credentials.
2	Runtime attestation, Measures for failed attestation	Trust Controls, Certification and Auditing, Software Enforcement, SW Verification, Digital Twin, Protection Profile Composition Engine	The correct operation of the KardinBin device and the integrity of the monitored medical data must be assured. Also, the capability to detect new vulnerabilities and deploy the measures for their mitigation is necessary.	The enforcement of remote firmware updates and the assessment of the correct operation of the device after the update is achieved with the revocation of the Conformity Certificate, the update process, the DT simulation and the creation of new certificate and challenge.
3	Runtime attestation	Domain Manager, Trust Controls, Attestation Agent, DLT, Device Data and Tracer, Wallet, DLT, Off-Chain Storage, Certification Auditing	The provision of operational assurance for the KardinBlu device must be ensured.	Operational assurance is provided by the continuous assessment mechanisms that attest to the correctness of the configuration state of the device.

6.2.4.2 Compositional Security and Cooperative Execution of Safety-Critical Operations in Hospital Settings

- **Safeguard the communication in CMDs in safety-critical conditions through trust assessment, and at the same time prevent the propagation of vulnerabilities from one device to another.**

This particular use case will take place in the Cardiology Clinic of the Ankara University, where several high-end devices are deployed in an operating room, such as GE and Siemens catheterization labs, Siemens angiography systems, GE, Philips and ESAOTE echocardiography devices (fleet of devices). Currently, the deployed MDs are connected to each other and exchange messages through an intermediate hub, allowing real-time cooperation. The objective of this scenario is to assess the trustworthiness of the devices in real-time and under safety-critical conditions, and at the same time to prevent the propagation of vulnerabilities from one device to another, jeopardizing patient safety, data confidentiality, or service availability if it were to be exploited by an adversary.

This scenario will be used in combination with the already deployed device coming from Kardinero and with the use of high-end gateway and a domain manager. The domain manager, a centralized server, is crucial in this setup. It plays a dual role: firstly, as the registration authority for new devices, ensuring secure enrolment through an advanced authorization module, and secondly, as a continuous monitor of device security levels throughout their lifecycle. Its core component, the trust assessment engine, is designed to identify vulnerabilities and threats, and enforce appropriate logic and controls. This centralized trust assessment capability is crucial for maintaining the integrity and security of the network. The domain manager's ability to enforce necessary updates and maintain a secure and trustworthy environment extends the resilience of the medical network, safeguarding critical healthcare operations against evolving cybersecurity threats.

In this use case, we aim to validate ENTRUST's security frameworks and trust assessment capabilities over BLE communications, particularly in a setup involving a network of collaborative devices. We will focus on evaluating the efficiency and resilience of ENTRUST's attestation mechanisms under strict security conditions, ensuring the integrity of command exchanges. A TC-based middleware will facilitate advanced cryptographic operations necessary for remote attestation, maintaining control flow integrity and assuring secure communications among ECG and stationary devices. This will enable real-time detection and analysis of potential attacks. Additionally, we plan to verify the issuance of conformance certificates, a crucial step that allows external stakeholders to confirm the devices proper functioning and compliance with security protocols. This comprehensive evaluation will not only test the robustness of ENTRUST's security features but also enhance the overall trustworthiness and reliability of the connected medical device ecosystem.

User Story 4:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure that CMDs are continuously assessed against their predefined behaviour, calculates its level of trust and enforces any necessary security measures.

In large-scale hospital settings, it is imperative to ensure that all connected CMDs are continuously monitored and assessed, in order to ensure that they are in a correct configuration state, and they have not been compromised by a malicious third party. In this regard, as previously outlined, the CIV scheme is able to attest to the correctness of these devices based on a set of properties defined in the Protection Profile of each device. In addition, since the deployed CMDs are connected to a communication hub in order to allow real-time collaboration, this defines a tree-like network structure of parent hub devices and low-level children CMDs. Therefore, as part of this User Story, the Swarm Attestation scheme is evaluated based on its ability to attest to the configuration integrity of all these devices in a manner that is more efficient than attesting each device individually.

In addition, the Misbehaviour Detection mechanism is able to utilize AI-based techniques in order to assess the network behaviour of the device in order to detect whether the network behaviour of the device is as expected, or whether unexpected behaviors are observed, such as unusual network load and request frequency. Specifically, this process consists of two phases: (i) Training of the AI model, which includes the collection and recording of traffic data, and the training of the model based on both collected and synthetic data. (ii) The Misbehavior Detection phase, which includes the collection of network traffic data for evaluation, their classification as benign or malicious based on the previous training of the model, and the update of the Protection Profile of the CMD with new mitigation actions depending on the result of the classification.

Table 18: Tested functionalities and components for Compositional Security and Cooperative Execution of Safety-Critical Operations in Hospital Settings use case

User Story	Tested Functionalities	Components	Motivation	Description
4	Runtime attestation, Misbehavior Detection	Domain Manager, Trust Controls, Attestation Agent, DLT, Device Data and Tracer, Wallet, DLT, Off-Chain Storage, Certification Auditing, Network Traffic Monitor, AI-based Misbehavior Detection, Protection Profiles Composer, MUD Server	The continuous monitoring and assessment of all connected CMDs in a hospital environment must be ensured.	The evaluation of the Swarm Attestation scheme alongside with the AI-based Misbehavior Detection mechanism will be tested in order to assure the correct state of the CMDs

6.2.5 Metrics of success

In Table 19, we provide an indicative set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) against which the various operations and components of ENTRUST will be evaluated, as outlined in the User Stories. Note that, in this and all subsequent use cases, the values provided for the KPIs are indicative, and will be refined and revised in the context of D6.1 [123].

In addition, it is important to note that in the timings provided for the KPIs in this Section, as well as for all subsequent use cases (Sections 6.3.5, 6.4.5, and 6.5.5) we consider that **the security controls of ENTRUST are not considered to be instantiated as part of a Trusted Execution**

Environment (TEE). In case we consider instantiation in a TEE, we consider that a **25% to 35% overhead is induced in each of the denoted performance timings.**

Table 19: KPIs for Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Use Case

KPI	Description and Values
Time needed for device onboarding	As the device onboarding operation is performed offline (i.e., before the actual operation of the device), it is not subject to strict timing requirements. Therefore, it is possible to consider a large timeframe for this process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time required for domain bootstrapping: ≤ 10 min
Key hierarchy construction	Note that this phase is included in the device onboarding process, but is also denoted separately because it may need to be executed again in case the key hierarchy needs to be updated during runtime: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiency of key hierarchy construction and verifiable key restriction usage policies: ≤ 150ms
Time required to perform the integrity check throughout the lifecycle of the CMD	≤ 200 ms
Time needed for the construction of Conformity Certificates	≤ 900 ms
Evaluation of Trust Assessment	This KPI refers to all aspects related to the performance/latency of the calculation of the ATL in the context of the runtime security enablers of ENTRUST. This depends on multiple dimensions, each one of which we have defined different KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≥ 3 different trust models of varying sizes. A trust model comprises all possible trust relationships capturing the interactions between the different CMDs. ≤ 300ms latency of ATL calculation. If $\geq 70\%$ of attacks are successful, this translates to a failure of the “ATL > RTL” test. Recalculation of RTL considering the identification of new risks: ≤ 3s.
Dynamic risk assessment based on the identification of new threats	≤ 2 s
Fallback firmware update duration	Overhead in the latency of the SW/FW process induced by the integrity verification performed by ENTRUST (i.e., the CIV attestation that verifies that the update has been performed correctly): ≤ 600 ms. Note that this does not refer to the firmware update itself, but to the latency induced by the ENTRUST security enabler verifying the correctness of the firmware update (e.g., CIV).
Accuracy of AI-based Misbehavior Detection mechanism	The accuracy level should be $\geq 70\%$. Detection accuracy should have an improvement in the order of 10% when it operates in tandem with the Trust Assessment. In this

	context, if the AI-based Misbehavior Detection flags something as an attack, all subsequent packets are considered as part of the attack and are dropped. However, the Trust Assessment will consider this as a data point, and as such will not drop subsequent packets. Thus, this leads to an increase in detection accuracy.
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6.3 Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living

6.3.1 Current Status

This pilot is focusing on the TelluCare Remote Patient Monitoring system, which facilitates remote assistance to follow up on patients suffering from chronic diseases such as diabetes and COPD, or other diseases where patients at least partly can stay in their own home, such as Covid-19. In general, the system enables patients to stay home during treatment and care, and to foster self-care. This allows health services to utilize the trained medical personnel more efficiently.

The pilot revolves around the **Tellu Personal Health Gateway (PHG)**, which is an IoT gateway device deployed in a patient's home. The PHG is responsible for collecting data from various medical sensors and sending them to the cloud platform TelluCare for further processing. The TelluCare service allows health personnel to access the data to perform remote patient monitoring, and to record the data and events in the patient's electronic health journal. The platform also normalizes the data according to standard eHealth ontologies to allow analysing the data in various ways and to easily integrate with other eHealth actors.

Figure 5 TelluCare Remote Patient Monitoring architecture and workflow

As the figure above indicates, the pilot executes across the IoT edge and cloud space. Medical devices and sensors on the IoT level is connected to the PHG which forwards events and measurements from the devices to the TelluCare platform. The health personnel can then access the provided data and follow up the patient based on provided measures.

The PHG itself has two isolated environments, the management environment and the application environment. In the administration environment the PHGs underlying software and configuration is updated and managed. The application environment is responsible for the handling of the patient data, as well as managing the application specific components that access this data. This is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 6 The Management (right)- and Administration (left) environments of the PHG

The Tellu PHG applies an industrial gateway built on IOT-GATE-iMX8 - Industrial IoT Gateway from Compulab. This is a powerful ARM-based gateway that supports several possibilities for connections and data communication. In particular, the gateway has a modular architecture that allows it to be configured to support many different types of standardized and proprietary connections. It can, for example, integrate medical technical equipment with both standard protocols like BLE and with more proprietary protocols and equipment that can only be connected via USB port, serial port, Ethernet, Wifi etc.

Figure 7 Tellu PHG - IOT-GATE-iMX8

The physical gateway comes as standard with 3 USB, 2 Ethernet ports and a serial port (which can be set up according to either RS232 or RS485). You can connect both USB and Ethernet hubs so that you can have many PHGs connected via USB and or Ethernet. Furthermore, the physical unit can be expanded to set up several simultaneous serial ports (RS485 and or RS232) for connecting the medical device. As mentioned, the physical unit is modular and has a

set of available modules that provide a further wide range of I/O support. This is summarized in the list below:

- PCI Express (Primary mini-PCIe socket)
- USB (USB2.0 ports, type-A connectors)
- I/O for Debugging (serial console via UART-to-USB bridge, micro-USB connector)
- Serial (RS485 (2-wire) / RS232 port, terminal-block)
- Analog 4–20mA input
- Digital I/O: 4x digital outputs + 4x digital inputs 24V, støtter EN 61131-2, (isolated, terminal block connector)
- PoE, extra 100Mbps Ethernet port with PoE capacity (powered device)
- Expansion connector for add-on boards: 2x SPI, 2x UART, I2C, and 12x GPIO (General purpose I/O, that can be applied for more proprietary connections)

A more elaborate specification of the hardware is provided on the Compulab website here: <https://www.compulab.com/products/iot-gateways/iot-gate-imx8-industrial-arm-iot-gateway/#specs>

For Bluetooth, see supplementary list here: <https://www.compulab.com/products/iot-gateways/iot-gate-imx8-industrial-arm-iot-gateway/#ordering>).

The most common medical device models we support are described in the table below.

Device type	Model
Pulse oximeter	Nonin Pulse Oximeter 3230
Blood pressure monitor	A&D Blood pressure monitor UA651BLE
Scale	A&D Medical precision health scale UC352BLE
Thermometer	A&D Medical precision digital thermometer UT201BLE
Blood glucose meter	Contour Next One NEXT
Fitness wearable	Fitbit

6.3.2 Scenario’s Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST

In general, it is expected that as the ENTRUST project progresses, the concepts and solutions that are shared from the experts in the project will influence future developments in the TelluCare ecosystem.

More specifically, Tellu wants to use the ENTRUST project to explore improvements in authentication, scalability, trust, and security in relation to the gateways and the related cloud services in the TelluCare Remote Patient Monitoring system. The aspects are listed below.

Automatic onboarding and authentication of gateways, sensors, and external services

- The initial onboarding of new gateways onto the TelluCare platform requires physically accessing the gateways. This is a somewhat manual, time consuming and complex process that does not scale well as our customer base grows.

- Tellu currently supports a predefined set of Bluetooth sensors due to differences in implementation of Bluetooth protocols. As the industry develops the Bluetooth protocols for medical devices are expected to mature, and Tellu wants to support health actors and patients to use their own devices. This requires that Bluetooth sensors can be onboarded and authenticated without knowing the specifics of the device itself.
- During an emergency situation, sensors and cameras installed in a home or institution could provide life-saving information to emergency services. Tellu wants to explore granting such services temporary access to the sensors and cameras in an autonomous and dynamic fashion.
- An issue that needs to be investigated is the type of communication channel to be used for the communication between the PHG and the Domain Manager in the context of the secure enrolment protocol. As there may be limitations in the BLE protocol with regard to the types of messages that can efficiently be exchanged, there may be limitations regarding the amount of data that can be transmitted (e.g., the bytes available for the security headers and the exchange of the necessary certificates). Therefore, we will investigate the interplay of security and performance of ENTRUST's advanced onboarding and secure enrolment schemes through varying communication interfaces including Bluetooth, Wireless, etc. so as to identify any limitations that they may pose on the type of security primitives to be exchanged and the impact on the operational profile of the target devices. This will allow for a detailed benchmarking on commodity protocols proposed in the standards.

Fleet management of gateways – monitoring and software deployment

- The monitoring of the gateways as-is is based on pinging the gateways to see connection status, as well as sending some simple metrics through the MQTT broker in the application environment. Gateways are sold or leased to a customer, and depending on the customer's use case the gateways might be stowed away for long periods at a time without possibility to report back to TelluCare. It is a manual task to overview of the configuration of the different gateways in the fleet. It is therefore of interest to get a more complete overview of the fleet of gateways, their current configuration, and metrics like connection history etc. that may provide insights on usage, device health and possible risks/threats.
- Another aspect that will be explored is how to ensure secure, scalable, and trustworthy deployment of software to a large fleet of gateways. Due to the possibly long periods without connectivity, the gateway may be missing vital security- and software updates when the customer brings it online again. It is important that a gateway then receives the published updates as soon as possible. Secondly, it is important to be able to trust and verify the software updates that are to be deployed. Finally, due to the growing number of gateways deployed at customers, there is a need to handle this in a scalable way where the administrator has control and overview.
- Automated attack simulations may expose weaknesses in the platform or devices. Regular testing or simulations of familiar and unfamiliar attack patterns could improve the trustworthiness and robustness of the fleet of devices.

Compliance with certification requirements, laws, and regulations

- The health technology domain is subject to laws and regulations that may differ between countries. Tellu operates in multiple countries and therefore needs to make sure the services comply with the local rules and regulations. Since TelluCare is an ecosystem with multiple actors involved, this makes it necessary to continuously ensure that all actors involved are trustworthy and secure and in compliance. Through the ENTRUST project

we will explore how the solution could monitor and manage the trustworthiness and security of the services and different actors involved.

- Tellu is currently investigating certifying the TelluCare platform and services as a Medical Device. As part of this it is also of interest to explore how ENTRUST could help to efficiently maintain such a certification over time, for example to be able to trace evidence of required controllers.

6.3.3 Threat Landscape

WHO: The threat actors inclined to attack your equipment/ organisation (e.g., insiders, outsiders, etc.)

- Employees
- Consultants
- Administrators on the customer side
- Partners
- Suppliers
- Manufacturers
- Hackers
- Terrorists

HOW: The techniques that they typically employ (e.g., MiTM attacks, ransomware, etc.)

- Human errors
- Unintentional unauthorized user activities due to low awareness
- Intentional unauthorized user activities
- System intrusion
- Man-in-the-middle in data transfers
- Denial-of-service
- Hardware design weaknesses or misconfiguration
- Software design weaknesses or misconfiguration

WHY: The objectives they are likely to pursue in their attacks (e.g., cybercriminals that are financially motivated to steal sensitive data)

- Attack Norwegian welfare services with malicious intent
- Weaken the Tellu's brand
- Financial gain
- Personal gain/interests

WHERE: The resources they are likely to target (e.g., critical resources; related to the points above)

- Patient health data in Tellu SaaS
- Tellu's and suppliers' SaaS incl. APIs, front and back end
- Tellu's and suppliers' infrastructure
- Tellu's and suppliers' endpoints
- Tellu's and suppliers' network
- Tellu's and suppliers' developer tools
- IoT devices
- Tellu's and suppliers' developers
- Tellu's and suppliers' deliver and support personnel
- Tellu's and suppliers' operational monitoring and support tools
- Tellu's and suppliers' documentation repositories (procedures, checklists, DRs etc.)

6.3.4 “To-be” Scenario and User Stories

Assistive Healthcare and Remote Patient Monitoring Gateway

- ***Trust aware authorisation, authentication and trustworthy communication between different domains comprising of heterogeneous devices based on VCs***
- ***ENTRUST’s TC based middleware will support the advanced crypto operations required for remote attestation and communication assurance.***
- ***The applicability and the impact of the TC based middleware in such heterogeneous environment will be evaluated.***
- ***Auditability over the update process will be guaranteed using the Blockchain and the stored Protection profiles.***

The remote patient monitoring system for home use integrates a Personal Health Gateway and a patient app to facilitate secure, cloud-based communications. This system handles automatic health data transfer from medical devices and supports interactions like chat and video consultations with health professionals. On the healthcare side, it enables patient monitoring, communication, and personalized care plan execution. Focusing on trust-aware authorization, authentication, and communication across various device domains, this setup employs VCs to depict each device’s operational state. ENTRUST's TC-based middleware will enhance crypto operations for remote attestation and communication assurance at the gateway level. The impact of this middleware in a diverse environment will be assessed, ensuring auditability of updates via the ENTRUST Blockchain and the protection profiles. This extension addresses the need for trustworthy, efficient communication in healthcare, emphasizing the importance of advanced security measures in remote patient monitoring.

User Story 1:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to automate the onboarding and authentication of gateways.

As aforementioned, one of the core challenges with regard to the onboarding and authentication of the PHG is the need for physical access to the gateway by an employee who would be responsible for the deployment of the device to a patient’s residence. While this may be feasible for a small number of clients, it will require a large number of financial resources and will be cumbersome and inefficient for a large number of clients. In this regard, ENTRUST will explore the possibility of automating the onboarding and authentication process, so that it can be performed in an automated and efficient manner, without the need for the presence of a company representative. This user story evaluates the secure enrollment and bootstrapping of the PHG to the TelluCare platform, in a manner that enables its secure interactions with all medical sensors in the patient’s residence, as well as the eHealth platform.

Specifically, as outlined in Section 5.3.1, the Secure Enrollment process of ENTRUST consists of two phases, namely Manufacturer Bootstrapping and Domain Bootstrapping. The former phase includes the installation of the MUD URL of the device by communicating with the MUD Server, the publishing of the Protection Profiles of the device, the installation of the UID of the device, and the issuance of identity certificates. The latter phase entails the creation and verification of all cryptographic material that will be used in the subsequent execution of security enablers. Specifically, it involves the collection of bootup traces that will be used to determine the expected operational state of the CMD, as well as the derivation of cryptographic and signing keys that will

be used for attestation operations and the establishment of secure channels. It also includes the issuance of Verifiable Credentials (VCs) containing the totality of verifiable device attributes, based on which the device can construct a Verifiable Presentation (VP) containing a subset of attributes, which can be used in order to access a set of data or service that requires the demonstration of those attributes.

User Story 2:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure the secure onboarding of third-party CMDs at the gateway level

As aforementioned, the PHG is a device that implements a modular architecture which enables it to support multiple types of standardized and proprietary connections, thus enabling it to establish connections with several different types of devices with various types of communication interfaces, such as USB, serial ports, Ethernet, and Wi-Fi, while also providing a further wide range of I/O support in a modular manner. Therefore, it needs to be ensured that all types of devices connected to the PHG are able to be securely onboarded to the ENTRUST framework, regardless of their type, their I/O specifications, and their computational capabilities.

As part of this User Story, the capability for such devices to be onboarded to the ENTRUST framework will be evaluated. Note that the secure enrolment process has been outlined in User Story 1, which needs to be evaluated for the types of devices typically connected to a PHG, in order to verify the efficiency and performance of the bootstrapping process. In addition, it needs to be considered that different devices may be subject to different types of requirements, which should be reflected in the Protection Profile of the device specifying the types of policies to be applied (e.g., attestation and access control policies). Also, when a CMD is connected to the gateway, the Risk Assessment module needs to recalculate the risk graph and perform attack path calculation, considering the changes in the network topology and the interconnectivity of the devices.

User Story 3:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to manage the fleet of gateways, assess its trustworthy state during runtime and enforce updates if needed.

Recall that the “as-is” scenario of the TelluCare Remote Patient Monitoring System involves the deployment of a gateway device (PHG) to the residence of each patient, so that it can be connected to each medical sensing device that collects health information from the patient. All such PHGs are responsible for transmitting the received information to the TelluCare eHealth platform, where it can be evaluated by healthcare professionals for the remote evaluation of the health status of the patient. It follows that this configuration defines a tree-like network structure, starting from the TelluCare server and reaching each low-end medical monitoring and sensing device. As the scope of this network expands through the introduction of additional patients, a method is needed for the fast, efficient, and trustworthy verification of the correctness of each gateway device, as well as the deployment of secure updates in case an indication of risk is identified.

In this regard, ENTRUST offers the Swarm Attestation enabler, which aims to attest to the correctness of the configuration state of devices in a tree-like structure, in a manner that is much more efficient than attesting to each of these devices individually. This User Story entails the

evaluation of the Swarm Attestation scheme dynamically during runtime, and its capability to identify compromised gateway devices in a fast and efficient manner. In addition, in case a gateway has been deemed to be compromised, the scope of this User Story also includes the deployment of a secure update to the PHG in order to address the identified vulnerabilities.

User Story 4:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime and issue Conformity Certificates based on the collected verifiable evidence

In order to perform a remote attestation operation, such as Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV), the Protection Profile of the CMD specifies the specific device attributes that need to be attested in order to assess the correctness of the configuration state of the device. For the assessment of each attribute, different types of attestation evidence are required, which are collected appropriately by the Device Tracer. This user story entails the execution of such an operation on the PHG based on a defined set of attributes. Note that this process also includes the calculation of the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the selected attributes, and its comparison with the Required Trust Level (RTL) in order to verify whether the CMD can be considered to be in a trustworthy state.

In addition, in case the CMD is deemed to be trustworthy, this User Story entails the issuance of the Conformity Certificate of the device, which can be accessed by auditors and certification bodies in order to verify the correctness of the device. Note that this certificate is created by the Certification and Auditing component, which receives the attestation report containing the result of the attestation. Afterwards, the certificate is forwarded to the ledger where it is stored, in a manner that enables parties with the appropriate permissions to access it.

Table 20: Tested functionalities for Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System Use Case

User Story	Tested Functionalities	Components	Motivation	Description
1	Manufacturer Bootstrapping, Domain Bootstrapping	MUD Server, AAA server, DLT, Domain Manager, Trusted Component, Protection Profile Composer	The onboarding and authentication of the PHG is challenged by the need for physical access to the gateway by an employee responsible for deploying the device to a patient's residence.	ENTRUST will explore the possibility of automating the onboarding and authentication process, so that it can be performed in an automated and efficient manner, without the need for the presence of a company representative.
2	Manufacturer Bootstrapping, Domain Bootstrapping	MUD Server, AAA server, DLT, Domain Manager, Trusted Component, Protection Profile Composer	It needs to be ensured that all types of devices connected to the PHG are able to be securely onboarded to the ENTRUST framework, regardless of their type, their I/O specifications,	The secure enrollment process will be evaluated for the types of devices typically connected to a PHG, in order to verify the efficiency and performance of the bootstrapping process.

			and their computational capabilities	
3	Runtime attestation, Measures for failed attestation	Trust Controls, Certification and Auditing, Software Enforcement, SW Verification, Digital Twin, Protection Profile Composition Engine	A method is needed for the fast, efficient, and trustworthy verification of the correctness of each PHG, as well as the deployment of secure updates in case an indication of risk is identified.	In this regard, ENTRUST offers the Swarm Attestation enabler, which aims to efficiently attest to the correctness of the configuration state of devices, and the method for a secure update to the PHG to address possible identified vulnerabilities.
4	Runtime attestation	Domain Manager, Trust Controls, Attestation Agent, DLT, Device Data and Tracer, Wallet, DLT, Off-Chain Storage, Certification Auditing	The trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime must be assured.	CMD trustworthiness is provided by the continuous assessment mechanisms that attest to the device's correctness of configuration state.

6.3.5 Metrics of Success

In Table 21, we provide an indicative set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) against which the various operations and components of ENTRUST will be evaluated, as outlined in the User Stories. Note that, as previously mentioned, the values provided for the KPIs are indicative, and will be refined and revised in the context of D6.1 [123].

Table 21: KPIs for Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System Use Case

KPI	Description and Values
Time needed for device onboarding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboarding of PHGs: <=6 min Onboarding of medical device sensing components to the PHG (acting as the MUD profiles of the devices): <=1000 ms
Key hierarchy construction	<p>Note that this phase is included in the device onboarding process, but is also denoted separately because it may need to be executed again in case the key hierarchy needs to be updated during runtime:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiency of key hierarchy construction and verifiable key restriction usage policies: <=150ms
Fallback firmware update duration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overhead in the latency of the SW/FW process induced by the integrity verification performed by ENTRUST (i.e., the

	<p>CIV attestation that verifies that the update has been performed correctly): $\leq 600\text{ms}$. Note that this does not refer to the firmware update itself, but to the latency induced by the ENTRUST security enabler verifying the correctness of the firmware update (e.g., CIV)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upgrading a function/application in the PHG device: $\leq 750\text{ms}$ (considering the update of the application running in a TEE, i.e., secure upgrade).
Time required to perform the integrity check throughout the lifecycle of the CMD	$\leq 200\text{ms}$
Attestation and integrity verification of a fleet of devices	Time required to perform a Swarm Attestation operation $\leq 900\text{ms}$
Time needed for the construction of Conformity Certificates	$\leq 400\text{ms}$

6.4 Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers

This use case addresses the cybersecurity challenges associated with the growing use of health digital solutions (connected devices, digitalized information systems, healthcare data repositories) in the delivery of care, as well as the dwelling reality of a hybrid ICT infrastructure, combining new computers, devices, and networks with outdated and legacy firmware with different operating systems, and presenting a high number of vulnerabilities or risks.

Two different scenarios have been defined:

- Scenario 1: Smart Ambulance.
- Scenario 2: Ensure Trust across Legacy Systems in an Emergency Care Unit.

Scenario 1: Smart Ambulance

Considering the European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA) 2015 Report [124] and the specific context of the ENTRUST Project, the Scenario 1 relates directly to Mobile health (mHealth) and the use of remote patient monitoring platforms in ambulance transportation.

mHealth and Remote Patient Monitoring Platforms

Mobile health (mHealth) supports the delivery of healthcare via remote access medical devices, IoT-based health devices (the Internet of Medical Things or IoMT) and mobile applications that connect to healthcare IT systems through computer networks, empowering the sharing of health and wellbeing information, enabling the shifting of healthcare to a more preventative care outside of the hospital environment, giving rise to services such as telehealth (video appointments and consultation) and remote patient monitoring platforms, and delivering high-quality healthcare.

Experts estimate that there will be more than 64 billion IoT devices by 2025 [125] and a significant portion of these will be medical devices, from heart monitoring implants and pacemakers to infusion pumps, mobile medical workstations, in-home monitors and personal fitness devices or

wearables. According to a study conducted by the McKinsey Global Institute, spending on the Healthcare IoT solutions will reach \$1 trillion by 2025 [126]. Currently, 3 million patients worldwide are connected to a remote monitoring device that performs routine tests – such as checking glucose levels for patients with diabetes or checking blood pressure for patients receiving cardiac care – and sends personal medical data to their healthcare provider [127].

With mHealth tools and platforms, telehealth and remote patient monitoring platforms have the potential to extend care management and coordination outside the healthcare organisation, namely into ambulances and patient transportation vehicles. In addition, the increase of available connected devices at the hospital and in ambulance environments provides the opportunity to deliver personalised, accessible, and on-time healthcare services, capable of delivering medical assistance where and when needed, reducing decompensation episodes, and significantly improving health outcomes.

Indeed, healthcare organisations recognise the added value of mHealth, connected medical and health devices and telehealth and remote patient monitoring platforms to the successful implementation of digitally connected coordination of care. Nevertheless, in a highly complex environment, these trends stretch the boundaries of cybersecurity, while creating new, often insecure, entry points for hackers and rising data security and liability risks.

Not only medical and health remote monitoring devices may be vulnerable to viruses and malware that can compromise its effectiveness (device failure or malfunction), the patients' privacy and the healthcare organisations' ICT ecosystem, but also the transmission of patient data enabled by those devices represents a risk of data breach if the information is not properly secure. Since these devices are within ambulances and vehicles used by patient transportation services, and thus outside the healthcare organisation's control, there is also a lack of visibility and control over the devices, as well as the absence of awareness of these devices' vulnerabilities that attackers could take advantage of. As healthcare systems become interconnected, especially as numerous wireless medical devices start connecting to web-enabled IT systems, they become increasingly vulnerable. From a cybersecurity perspective, healthcare organisations need to rethink medical and health device management and consider all the variables this mobile technology introduces.

6.4.1 Current Status

The transfer of patients in critical status to healthcare institutions where they can receive proper care is one of the most vital services offered by healthcare service providers. In this process, ambulances and patient transportation vehicles host several connected medical devices to closely monitor the patient's status until the patient's hand-out to the hospital is performed effectively. The connected medical devices in the ambulance continuously monitor the patient's vital signs, collecting data that is valuable for providing adequate medical assistance en-route. In addition, the ambulance's emergency medical technicians (EMTs) collect medically-relevant information on the patient's condition. Today, this data is only available at the ambulance for the EMTs to monitor the patient's status and stability during transport.

Improved connectivity promises to revolutionise time-constraint emergency medical services, by utilising information to improve transportation safety and ensure zero-error patient hand-out. In this new context, it is expected that, during the transport route, collected health-related information is uploaded to remote patient monitoring systems (RPMS) and be viewed and analysed by the medical team at the point-of-care (e.g., the destination hospitals), so that the medical team is apprised of the patient's status at all times and even is able to provide valuable guidance to the EMTs if any issues arise in the patient's condition. In addition, the ability to understand the current medical condition of transported patients while en-route to the hospital, improves the hospital's response capability, concerning the planning of resources and logistics, so as to ensure that

adequate human resources, materials and equipment are available and in place to support the hospital’s medical intervention and early diagnosis of the incoming patient to the hospital’s emergency unit.

The following image depicts the different spaces addressed in Scenario 1, namely the untrusted/public ambulance space and the trusted destination hospital space.

Within the ambulance or patient transport vehicles, the connected devices comprise the:

- “Bed” monitors;
- Victim’s wearables;
- Smartphone; and
- PARTICLE MONITOR App.

At the hospital, the following critical devices are in place:

- EHR server;
- PARTICLE MONITOR server;
- Video-call server;
- Administrative servers;
- Workstations.

Furthermore, in the context of the Smart Ambulance scenario, PARTICLE will provide a set of mobile wearable sensors that will be connected to the HESE Hospital’s Patient Monitoring System through a gateway.

6.4.2 Scenario’s Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST

The Smart Ambulance scenario presents a dedicated process and data sharing workflow that highlight the specific cybersecurity challenges and needs to be addressed by the ENTRUST technologies. Within the workflow, it is important to note the following phases and their associated challenges:

- Before transport
 - Register a patient;
 - Triage a patient;
 - Monitor and track a patient using IoT and medical devices;
 - Optional: Doctors connect remotely (video call) to assess the patient’s status and provide remote assistance to the EMTs.
- During transport (on-the-move):
 - Track ambulance (calculate ETA) using IoT and medical devices and a Mobile App;

- Monitor and track a victim (update triage status) using IoT and medical devices;
- Destination hospital: receive patient information including latest triage status [transport-> hospital systems];
- Optional: Doctors connect remotely (video call) to assess the patient’s status and provide remote assistance to the EMTs.
- Destination Handover:
 - Transfer patient data to hospital [transport-> hospital systems].

Based on this workflow, the Smart Ambulance scenario illustrates the following cybersecurity challenges in healthcare delivery:

- To deal with untrusted environments and devices;
- To deal with remote healthcare services (at ambulance care), benefitting from remote patient monitoring platforms and telehealth systems;
- To deal with the integration of IoT-enabled medical and health devices in the healthcare organisations’ networks;
- To deal with the sharing and exchange of healthcare and patient data;
- To deal with the availability, integrity and confidentiality of healthcare and patient data;
- To deal with the users’ authentication and profile management.

In this scenario, the attack vector is considerably large, considering the destination hospital’s systems, the mobility of the connected devices in the ambulance and the need to connect to different cellular and wireless networks to transmit the necessary information from the ambulance’s devices to the destination hospital’s medical systems and cloud services. For instance, a malicious actor can impersonate a device carried by ambulance and feed inaccurate information to the hospital services, causing them to miscalculate the medical status of the victim, which is critical for the medical intervention upon the ambulance’s arrival at the emergency unit.

Aside from the exploitation of cybersecurity aspects associated with the real-time exchange of patient data between an unsecure space (i.e., public communications network) and the secure hospital IT infrastructure, this use case scenario will address the security vulnerabilities associated with connected medical devices and the protection of the availability, integrity and confidentiality of patient data.

6.4.3 Threat Landscape

As key references for the Smart Ambulance scenario in Use Case 3, the ENTRUST partners HESE, POLARIS and PARTICLE abide to the approach set forth by ENISA on attack scenarios and eHealth use cases:

- ENISA Smart Hospitals - Security and Resilience for Smart Health Service and Infrastructures. November 2016;
- ENISA Security and Resilience in eHealth - Security Challenges and Risks. 2015.

Concerning cybersecurity taxonomies, the following sources are used:

- ENISA Reference Incident Classification Taxonomy - Task Force Status and Way Forward. January 2018;
- Malware Information Sharing Platform (MISP) Taxonomy, which compiles several taxonomies including ENISA's Threat Taxonomy.

ENTRUST deals with developing a trusted environment for connected devices in the healthcare domain, looking into highly connected ecosystems and concepts involving the future of healthcare. Thus, the ENISA report on smart health service and infrastructures^[1] is used as main reference for the definition of critical healthcare assets, threat taxonomy, threat actors, attack vectors and the associated negative impact, as follows:

- **WHO:** The involved threat actors or malicious agents would be:
 - **opportunistic attackers** who are amateur criminals;
 - **professional remote attackers** that, while not physically present at the healthcare organisation's facilities, are able to exploit vulnerabilities within the healthcare service provider's interconnected health ecosystem and gain access to the overall ICT system to disrupt the healthcare service;
 - **insider attackers**, operating within the organisation, who are typically actors with direct access to sensitive data but also with the knowledge about internal operations and processes. On top of that, their activity is much less likely to trigger a red flag within the network and various tools network intrusion tools, like firewalls, are ineffective against inside threats.
- **HOW:** The techniques the attackers would typically employ are associated with malicious actions and include Malware, Ransomware, Man-in-the-middle attacks, Hijacking, Medical device tampering, Social engineering, Device and data theft, Denial of Service (DoS)/Distributed DoS (DDoS). To implement these attacks, the attack vector employed, that is, the path or means by which the threat agent would explore the assets' vulnerabilities, would preferably be the **physical interaction with IT assets**, when insider attackers are able to handle directly the existing devices and systems they have access to, and the **wireless communication with IT assets**, by which remote attackers may gain access to the healthcare service provider's IT assets through the use of wireless technologies, including identification systems or mobile devices.
- **WHY:** The opportunistic attackers or amateur criminals, often referred to as script kiddies, are usually driven by the **desire for notoriety** and they may become legitimate security researchers trying to help organisations find and close security vulnerabilities, or even professional hackers looking to profit from finding and exposing flaws and exploits in network systems and devices; the professional remote attackers will disturb the delivery of care for **profit** (financial gain from selling patient data) and/or **personal notoriety** (as references for the curriculum); and the insider attackers are mostly disgruntled employees or ex-employees looking for **revenge** or **financial gain**.
- **WHAT:** The critical healthcare resources that are likely to be targeted are:
 - the **Healthcare information systems**, that is, the digital administrative and clinical systems, applications and services supporting the activity of the healthcare service provider, both stored locally and accessed remotely (for example, the Remote Patient Monitoring System and the Telemedicine System);
 - the **Networked medical devices**, the set of medical equipment integrated in the healthcare service provider's IT network to support the delivery of care;

- the **IT and networking equipment**, namely the infrastructure components enabling access to healthcare information systems (e.g., desktop computers and servers) and providing the connectivity backbone that connects them (e.g., routers and gateways);
- the **Healthcare data**, the informational resources at the centre of all medical decision-making processes to support high-quality healthcare services.

Any security incident affecting critical assets cause severe impact in the regular functioning of systems, services and applications, to the benefit of society. In the healthcare domain, the systems’ availability, interoperability, access control and authentication, as well as the high privacy and confidentiality requirements of healthcare data represent key security challenges that, in case of failure to deliver adequate security, disrupt the overall healthcare service delivery to the general population. In ENTRUST, the following impacts are considered:

- **Loss of availability:** the absence of access to (classified) healthcare information or to application services or to information exchange between point of care sites;
- **Data integrity violation:** the absence of quality, accuracy and consistency of the data stored and exchanged for clinical and administrative purposes;
- **Data confidentiality violation:** the unmonitored or illegal access to or misuse of sensitive healthcare information.

These service outages affect significantly the healthcare service delivery, the trust in the healthcare industry and the safety of patients, leading to unnecessary duplication of tests and exams and the increase of healthcare service delivery costs, as well as to serious distress to society.

The following table summarises the threat landscape associated with the Smart Ambulance scenario in UC3: Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers:

Table 22: Use Case 3 | Scenario 1: Smart Ambulance

Use Case 3 Scenario 1: Smart Ambulance	
Scope	
Application Scenario	mHealth and Remote Patient Monitoring Platforms
Attack	
Threat Type	Malicious action – Malware; Ransomware, Man-in-the-middle attacks, Hijacking, Medical device tampering, Social engineering, Device and data theft, Denial of Service (DoS)/Distributed DoS (DDoS)
Threat Actor(s)	Remote Attackers – Opportunistic; Professionals Insider Attackers
Attack Vector(s)	Wireless communication with IT assets Physical interaction with IT assets
Vulnerability and Exploitation	
Exploited Vulnerability(ies)	Wireless connectivity Connected devices Poor cyber security practices
Critical Healthcare Assets	
Affected Asset(s)	IT and networking equipment; Healthcare information systems; Healthcare data
Criticality of Affected Asset(s)	Highly critical

^[1] ENISA Smart Hospitals - Security and Resilience for Smart Health Service and Infrastructures. European Union Agency for Network and Information Security. November 2016.

6.4.4 “To-be” Scenario and User Stories

Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Well-being of Patients and Carers

Smart Ambulance:

In the ambulance case, the attack vector is expanded considering the mobility of the devices and the need to connect to different cellular and wireless networks to transmit the necessary information to medical systems and cloud services.

User Story 1

As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure the secure onboarding of third-party CMDs at the ambulance.

As aforementioned, while transporting a patient, the ambulance operates within a public/untrusted space. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to ensure that all devices operating within the ambulance are in a correct and trustworthy state. In addition, during the transport route, it is necessary to collect health information from the patient and upload it to the Remote Patient Monitoring System (RPMS), so that it can afterwards be viewed and analyzed by the medical team at the destination hospital. Therefore, it is necessary for each device to be securely enrolled to the hospital’s network infrastructure, in order to generate the required cryptographic material enabling the device’s configuration state to be verified dynamically during runtime, but also to ensure that a secure communication channel is established between the ambulance and the hospital. In this enrolment process, it is also critical to ensure that the device functions operate as intended by the manufacturer, identifying any unauthorized alterations or tampering.

Considering the above, this user story entails the execution of the Domain Bootstrapping process for each of the CMDs operating within the ambulance (e.g., patient wearables, PARTICLE MONITOR, and ambulance monitors) prior to the transportation of the patient in the ambulance. Note that ambulance CMDs are connected to the PARTICLE gateway, and it is possible to use a Kardinero device as a CMD (as outlined in Section 6.2). In this process, the Domain Manager receives the UID and MUD URL of the CMD and performs an authentication of these values (recall that the authentication of the UID is delegated to the AAA Server of the Manufacturer). During this process, the CMD (more specifically, the connecting gateway acting as a proxy to the CMD) also derives the signing keys and the Attestation Key (AK). These keys are verified by the Domain Manager, who also updates the Protection Profile of the device, in order to contain the appropriate attestation challenges and assurance claims associated with the device.

User Story 2:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime and issue Conformity Certificates based on the collected verifiable evidence

During the transportation of a patient in the ambulance, it is important to ensure that all devices operating within the ambulance are in a correct configuration state, therefore attesting to the correct operation of these devices, as well as to ensure the correctness and integrity of the data transmitted to the destination hospital. This may include location tracking data to monitor the position of the ambulance, but also the patient's health data collected from the ambulance monitors so that they can be remotely analysed by the medical staff at the hospital. Moreover, given the high mobility nature of this scenario, there are additional security risks resulting from having a dynamic network topology - between the ambulance and the destination hospital -, for the network access components might change during the ambulance's trajectory. In User Story 1, the required cryptographic material has been created through the Secure Enrolment and Domain Bootstrapping process of ENTRUST. In this User Story, this cryptographic material is leveraged so as to remotely monitor the correctness of these devices during runtime.

Specifically, this user story entails the execution of a remote attestation scheme involving one or more of the devices operating within the ambulance, considering a dynamic network topology. Recall that, in order to initiate this process, the CMD (more specifically, the connecting gateway acting as a proxy to the CMD) sends the MUD URL to the Domain Manager, who checks whether the corresponding Protection Profile is available on the ledger. If yes, the Domain Manager initiates an attestation challenge to the CMD, which collects the required attestation evidence using its Tracer, including information corresponding to the device parameters to be attested. Afterwards, the CMD sends its response to the Domain Manager, who verifies the correctness of the response. If the attestation is successful, a Conformity Certificate is created, which is sent to the ledger to be stored, allowing it to be accessed by certification or auditing parties. In the context of ENTRUST, there can be various types of remote attestation, such as Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) for ensuring the correctness of the configuration of a device, and Swarm Attestation (SA) for ensuring the correctness of multiple devices simultaneously. Given the dynamic network topology that includes external/untrusted network components (i.e., public network), all involved steps also need to comply with security requirements, like domain verification and end-to-end encryption.

User Story 3:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthy state of the gateway and enforce a SW update in case of a security incident.

In the context of the Smart Ambulance scenario, a set of mobile wearable sensors are provided by PARTICLE's solution, which collects information from the patient in the ambulance and transmit it to the HPSC through a gateway. In order to ensure the integrity of the patient's data, we need to perform a remote attestation operation on the gateway itself. In this regard, this user story will entail the execution of a CIV process to verify the correctness of the configuration state of the gateway, considering a dynamic network topology involving external/untrusted network components, as outlined in User Story 2.

As part of the attestation process, the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the specified parameters is computed and compared against the Required Trust Level (RTL) in order to determine if further action is required following the completion of the attestation process. As part of this User Story, if $ATL < RTL$, this signifies the need for the revocation of the Conformity Certificate of the CMD, and also indicates that a SW update is needed in order to address the cause of the failed attestation. To this end, the DLT sends the traces used as attestation evidence to the SW Verification component. Afterwards, the traces are sent to the Digital Twin in order to simulate the conditions that led to the failed attestation. Finally, the DLT updates the Protection Profile of the

CMD in order to include the new attestation challenge that verifies that the issue has been successfully addressed.

Table 23: Tested functionalities and components for Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers Use Case

User Story	Tested Functionalities	Components	Motivation	Description
1	Domain Bootstrapping	MUD Server, AAA server, DLT, Domain Manager, Trusted Component, Protection Profile Composer	It must be ensured that all devices operating within the ambulance are in a correct and trustworthy state and securely enrolled to the hospital's network infrastructure, considering a highly mobile scenario and dynamic network topology.	The trustworthiness and the secure enrolment of all devices is achieved by the creation of the updated Protection Profile of the devices. The gateway operates as a proxy to the CMDs.
2	Runtime attestation	Domain Manager, Trust Controls, Attestation Agent, DLT, Device Data and Tracer, Wallet, DLT, Off-Chain Storage, Certification Auditing	The trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime must be assured, considering a highly mobile scenario and dynamic network topology.	This is achieved by the ENTRUST framework with the appropriate attestation scheme. The gateway operates as a proxy to the CMDs.
3	Runtime attestation, Measures for failed attestation	Trust Controls, Certification and Auditing, Software Enforcement, SW Verification, Digital Twin, Protection Profile Composition Engine	The correct operation of the gateway and the integrity of the monitored patient data must be assured.	The enforcement of remote SW updates and the assessment of the correct operation of the device after the update is achieved with the revocation of the Conformity Certificate, the update process, the DT simulation and the creation of new certificate and challenge.

Ensure trust across legacy systems in an emergency care unit

How modern cybersecurity threats targeting highly interconnected, legacy-based connected MDs can be identified, evaluated, and treated on time?

User Story 1:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the network of the medical organization to identify threats and vulnerabilities related to the interconnected nature of the devices.

The Risk Assessment approach of ENTRUST includes two core phases. The first is performed during the Design Phase at the side of the device Manufacturer, who provides the Threat Modelling component with information such as the threat landscape affecting the device and a detailed profile of device characteristics (such as network interfaces, running software, and other features that need to be considered). However, note that this phase only considers the CMD as an isolated device, without taking into account the network topology where it will be used.

This User Story is concerned with the Risk Assessment process executed during the Pre-Deployment phase, where the CMD has been deployed to the network infrastructure of the target medical organization. In this process, the Security Administrator forwards the security and safety requirements of the organization to the Risk Assessment module, along with detailed information on the network topology. Then, the Risk Assessment module performs a re-quantification of risk, and generates an attack path calculation depending on the interdependencies between existing assets in the network and asset cartography. Then, the Risk Assessment module calculates the risk score, the impact per vulnerability, and the attack paths, and forwards this information to the Domain Manager. The validation of potential attacks is performed by the Digital Twin, which facilitates the assessment of their impact on the network infrastructure.

User Story 2:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthy state of the legacy device and enforce any required security measures.

As previously outlined, the ENTRUST framework includes a number of attestation schemes, namely CIV and Swarm Attestation, to assess the trustworthiness of devices and identify whether additional measures need to be taken, such as the deployment of a secure software update or the issuance of new attestation challenges. However, it should be noted that medical organizations typically consist of heterogeneous devices from different manufacturers with varying computational capabilities. In this regard, this User Story entails the evaluation of the attestation enablers of ENTRUST in the context of legacy devices with limited computational capabilities, in order to assess their capability to operate with various types of devices.

Note that, to support those attestation enablers, ENTRUST envisions the use of a hybrid approach with regard to the Trusted Component, consisting of a PUF and a TEE. This User Story entails the evaluation of the effectiveness of this approach in tandem with the aforementioned attestation schemes by measuring the performance of the underlying crypto operations.

User Story	Tested Functionalities	Components	Motivation	Description
1	Risk Assessment during Pre-Deployment	Risk Assessment, Digital Twin	Apart from the manufacturing, the Risk Assessment must be also performed into a	The combined use of the Risk Assessment and Digital Twin modules while

			specific network topology of the domain.	considering the domain's specifics.
2	Runtime attestation	Domain Manager, Trust Controls, Attestation Agent, DLT, Device Data and Tracer, Wallet, DLT, Off-Chain Storage, Certification Auditing	Since medical organizations typically consist of heterogeneous devices from different manufacturers with varying computational capabilities, the evaluation of the attestation enablers of ENTRUST in the context of legacy devices with limited computational capabilities, in order to assess their capability to operate with various types of devices, is necessary.	The use of a hybrid approach with regard to the Trusted Component, consisting of a PUF and a TEE will be evaluated on legacy devices.

6.4.5 Metrics of Success

In Table 24, we provide an indicative set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) against which the various operations and components of ENTRUST will be evaluated, as outlined in the User Stories. Note that, as previously mentioned, the values provided for the KPIs are indicative, and will be refined and revised in the context of D6.1 [123].

Table 24: KPIs for Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers Use Case

KPI	Description and Values
Time needed for device onboarding	<p style="text-align: center;">BEST: less than 30 seconds ACCEPTABLE: less than 5 minutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Note: Values apply for each device. The CMD onboarding process is performed by the gateway (CMD proxy).
Key hierarchy construction	<p>Note that this phase is included in the device onboarding process, but is also denoted separately because it may need to be executed again in case the key hierarchy needs to be updated during runtime:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiency of key hierarchy construction and verifiable key restriction usage policies: <=150ms
Time required to perform the integrity check throughout the lifecycle of the CMD	<=200ms
Time needed for the construction of Conformity Certificates	<=900ms

Evaluation of Trust Assessment	<p>This KPI refers to all aspects related to the performance/latency of the calculation of the ATL in the context of the runtime security enablers of ENTRUST. This depends on multiple dimensions, each one of which we have defined different KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥ 4 different trust models of varying sizes. A trust model comprises all possible trust relationships capturing the interactions between the different CMDs. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\leq 300\text{ms}$ latency of ATL calculation. • If $\geq 70\%$ of attacks are successful, this translates to a failure of the “ATL > RTL” test. • Recalculation of RTL considering the identification of new risks: $\leq 3\text{s}$.
Dynamic risk assessment based on the identification of new threats	$\leq 2\text{s}$
Fallback firmware update duration	Overhead in the latency of the SW/FW process induced by the integrity verification performed by ENTRUST (i.e., the CIV attestation that verifies that the update has been performed correctly): $\leq 600\text{ms}$. Note that this does not refer to the firmware update itself, but to the latency induced by the ENTRUST security enabler verifying the correctness of the firmware update (e.g., CIV).
Attack Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emulate and analyze impact of at least 3 attacks on the overall system.
Establishment of secure and authenticated channels between ambulance and backend	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key Establishment Rate (KER) of 1 different key per 5s <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $\leq 450\text{ms}$ for key establishment

6.5 Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data

6.5.1 Current Status

Sentio Labs develops precision biomarkers and digital therapeutics to change the way diagnosis, management, and care are provided for Mental Health. This is achieved by using a combination of technology and evidence-based techniques to help people gain emotional intelligence and develop coping mechanisms to change the way they think and behave. Emotion recognition is performed through the continuous monitoring of physiological signals such as a) Sweat, b) Heartbeat, and c) Skin Temperature. To achieve emotion recognition, Sentio offers a combination of various technologies, including a) Feel Emotion Sensor (FES), b) Feel Proprietary Algorithms, and c) Real-Time Notifications.

Specifically, the Feel Emotion Sensor (FES) is a wearable wristband that continuously monitors physiological signals using various sensors. Sentio analyses these physiological signals collected through the FES with proprietary algorithms to detect when a patient experiences an emotional moment. Through the Feel mobile application to which the FES is connected, the patient can receive real-time notifications about emotional moments, track their sleep, log their emotions, and ultimately enhance their emotional awareness.

To monitor a patient's emotions through Sentio, the user must obtain an FES and have a mobile phone with the Feel Application installed. The transmission of physiological signals/data from the FES to the Feel Application is achieved through the BLE communication protocol. In the context of security and privacy, Sentio's primary goals are maintaining data integrity, system data security, user authentication, and ensuring secure firmware updates.

6.5.2 Scenario's Challenges and Needs from ENTRUST

The sensitivity of patient physiological and mental health-related data is a critical concern in the context of the large-scale deployment of Feel Emotion Sensor (FES) devices. This sensitivity necessitates the implementation of several key safeguards to protect both the integrity and privacy of this data:

- **Maintaining Data Integrity:** The transmission of data from the FES to the mobile device includes a multitude of different data measurements, accompanied by various indexes and metrics. Any deviation will render the respective data package either useless or highly inaccurate. This is considered critical when it comes to the high-sampling real-time environment and health-related solutions, where the impact of inaccurate data may feed an inaccurate medical decision.
- **System Data Security:** The highly sensitive nature of the collected personal health data necessitates the privacy-preserving nature of the transmission during the entire data journey (i.e., sensor, mobile, cloud processing infrastructure, and back). In the scope of the project, this refers to the transmission of the collected sensor data from the FES device to the mobile phone, which could be achieved by securing the connection between them using encryption and device authentication (Just Works with Fixed Passkey)
- **User authentication:** Since all data-processing (Machine-Learning-based) models are personalized, while all extracted metrics and decisions refer to a specific individual and inform health-related decisions, it should be ensured that the same individual is using the sensor. This refers to authenticating that a specific user is using a specific device with a specific S/N.
- **Secure Firmware updates:** The device should have a secure update mechanism to ensure that firmware and software updates are authenticated and free from tampering. This helps protect against potential vulnerabilities or exploits.

To achieve those goals, the flow of data needs to be modified. Specifically, the existing process involves the transfer of data directly from the wearable to the mobile device, followed by its transmission to cloud services for processing, and ultimately looping back to the wearable. In ENTRUST, we modify this flow by adding a gateway device that acts as a Bluetooth-connected middleware between the FES wearable and the mobile app. The motivation behind the addition of the gateway device is to be able to support the execution of the security enablers of ENTRUST, such as the remote attestation schemes, and to achieve the secure and trustworthy exchange of data in a manner that ensures the integrity of the data. To this end, the gateway will be equipped with a hybrid TC consisting of a PUF and TEE and will be responsible for executing all the cryptographic operations needed for the assurance of the integrity of all data in the chain.

6.5.3 Threat Landscape

The threat landscape for medical devices is constantly evolving, with new threats emerging all the time. However, there are a few threat actors that are consistently inclined to attack medical devices like this of Sentio Labs:

Financially motivated cybercriminals: Healthcare companies are a prime target for financially motivated cybercriminals because of the sensitive and valuable data they store, such as patient records, financial information, and intellectual property.

Insider threats: Employees with access to sensitive data and systems may be tempted to sell this information to other companies, criminals, or use it for their own personal gain. Insider threats are difficult to detect and prevent, as they often come from within the company.

Hactivists: Are groups or individuals who hack into computer systems for political or ideological reasons. Healthcare companies may be targeted by hactivists because of their perceived role in the healthcare system, or because of their views on certain issues. Hactivist attacks can be disruptive and costly and can damage the reputation the company.

The techniques employed for cyber-attacks that are more concerning for our use case are those that compromise the protection of the health-related data collected by our device. These are:

MiTM attacks: Man-in-the-middle attack is a cyberattack where the attacker secretly relays and possibly alters the communications between two parties who believe that they are directly communicating with each other, as the attacker has inserted themselves between the two parties.

Data breaches: Data breaches occur when unauthorized individuals gain access to sensitive data. In the context of healthcare devices, this could involve an attacker gaining access to a device's database of patient records, or to a cloud server where patient data is stored.

Ransomware: is a type of malware that encrypts a victim's files and demands a ransom payment in exchange for the decryption key. In the context of healthcare devices, this could involve an attacker encrypting a device's database of patient records or a cloud server where patient data is stored.

Malware: is any type of malicious software, including viruses, worms, and Trojan horses.

DDoS: Denial-of-service attacks occur when an attacker floods a target system with traffic, making it unavailable to legitimate users. In the context of healthcare devices, this could involve an attacker flooding a device's network interface with traffic, or flooding a cloud server where patient data is stored with traffic.

The objectives of threat actors in carrying out attacks against healthcare devices are varied, but some of the most common objectives include:

- Financial motivation
- Damaging the opinions or reputation of the company
- Ideological motivation
- Pursuing publicity
- Resources that are likely to be targeted by threat actors in healthcare devices are:
- Confidential patient data is valuable - While a medical device might not store significant amounts of patient data, they can be vulnerable entry points for attackers to access data-rich servers.
- Leaking or accessing confidential data with the purpose of damaging opinions or reputation of the company. Causing patients to doubt whether their data is secure, or their care is in good hands when a healthcare provider can't even protect its own network. Leading to untold indirect costs for an unspecified amount of time.
- Intellectual Property and various other valuable business information about the compromised system.

6.5.4 “To-be” Scenario and User Stories

User Story 1:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to ensure the secure onboarding of the gateway device.

As already discussed, the FES transmits a multitude of data measurements, indexes, and sensor data to the mobile device, in order to enable the provision of Mental Health diagnosis, management, and care services. This type of data is highly sensitive, thus highlighting the need for the secure communication between the gateway device and the mobile device where the FES application is installed, as well as the runtime operational assurance of the device. In this regard, the gateway device needs to be securely enrolled in the network infrastructure in order to generate the required cryptographic material that will be used in the context of the security enablers of ENTRUST (e.g., remote attestation to verify its configuration state during runtime), as well as the establishment of secure communication channels.

As such, this user story entails the execution of the Secure Enrolment process, including the Manufacturer and Domain Bootstrapping phases, prior to its normal operation. Recall that the Manufacturer Bootstrapping entails the installation of the MUD URL on the CMD, the installation of the UID, and the issuance of identity certificates. The Domain Bootstrapping phase includes the derivation of the required signing and Attestation keys, in collaboration with the Domain Manager. Afterwards, the Domain Manager will update the Protection Profile of the device to contain the appropriate attestation challenges and assurance claims associated with it.

User Story 2:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to assess the trustworthy state of the gateway device during its entire lifetime and to ensure its integrity.

As aforementioned, the wearable FES module is responsible for the collection and transmission of highly sensitive data to the gateway device. Therefore, any compromise in the integrity of this data may lead to an inaccurate assessment of the Mental Health state of the patient and, by extension, an erroneous medical decision. Therefore, after the secure onboarding of the gateway, the ENTRUST platform must be able to assess the trustworthiness and the correctness of the configuration state of the gateway during runtime throughout its operational lifecycle, in order to ensure the integrity of the diagnostic process.

In this context, this use case entails the execution of runtime attestation processes that are able to ensure the integrity of the gateway device. Specifically, the Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) scheme is able to ensure the integrity of a set of parameters, as specified by the Protection Profile, also considering the types of data collected from the FES module. In this context, the Domain Manager extracts the corresponding attestation challenge from the Protection Profile, which is then issued and received by the Attestation Agent of the gateway. Afterwards, the Device Tracer collects the required data as attestation evidence for each of the attested parameters. Afterwards, the device sends back the response to the attestation challenge signed using its Wallet, and encrypts the traces collected as attestation evidence. Note that the calculation of the ATL and its comparison with the RTL is necessary for the decision whether the device is in a trustworthy state. If $ATL > RTL$, a Conformity Certificate for the device is issued. Afterwards, the certificate is forwarded to the ledger where it is stored, in a manner that enables parties with the

appropriate permissions to access it. This use case also includes the creation and storage of the attestation report containing the result of the attestation operation on the ledger, as well as the encrypted traces on the Off-chain Storage Facility. These are associated between them through a location pointer to the encrypted traces, which is appended to the corresponding attestation report.

User Story 3:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to enforce a remote FW update in case of a security incident.

As aforementioned, in order to provide runtime operational assurance of the gateway that collects data from the FES wearable module, the ENTRUST framework implements attestation mechanisms that are able to attest to the correctness of the configuration and operational state of the device during runtime. After the execution of an attestation as it was outlined in User Story 2, if $ATL < RTL$, this constitutes an indication of risk and signifies the need for the detection of the root cause behind the failed attestation, as well as the implementation of mitigation measures to address any identified vulnerabilities.

In this context, this user story includes the actions to be performed following a failed attestation. Specifically, the Trust Controls module first will notify the Certification and Auditing module so that it will revoke the Conformity Certificate of the gateway. The certificate will also be revoked from the ledger for it to be inaccessible from outside parties. Then, the Software Enforcement component will be notified about the failed attestation for the FW update process to be initiated. In addition, the traces that were collected during the failure of the attestation will be fed to the Verification component and the Digital Twin. After the simulation of the attack from the DT, the identified cause of failure will cause the update of the Protection Profile of the FES by the Protection Profile Composition Engine. Any new required attestation challenge will also be included.

User Story 4:

As a Security Administrator, I would like to calculate the trustworthiness of data produced and exchanged throughout the entire chain of the medical stakeholders, given multiple trust sources.

To ensure the trustworthiness and the integrity of all data produced and exchanged throughout the entire communication chain including the FES module, the gateway, and the mobile device where the FES app is installed, in addition to the secure onboarding, attestation and updates described in the previous user stories, this user story entails the detection of anomalies in the exchanged data.

The Misbehaviour Detection mechanism utilizes AI techniques and assesses the network behaviour of the devices. It detects whether the network behaviour of the devices is as expected or whether unexpected behaviour is detected. In order to do so, after the training of the model on collected and synthetic network traffic data, the network is being constantly observed by the Misbehaviour Detection mechanism. Network data are then classified as malicious or benign. In case of the detection of malicious activity, the Protection Profile of the CMD is updated and new mitigation actions are formulated.

This use case also includes the Trust Assessment which, in the context of ENTRUST, is based on the consideration of multiple trust sources. In this user story, we consider the following trust

sources: (i) Attestation enablers (e.g., CIV), and (ii) AI-based Misbehaviour Detection. Therefore, in assessing the trustworthiness of the data produced and exchanged throughout the entire chain of medical stakeholders, the assessment will be performed based on at least two trust sources.

Table 25: Tested functionalities and components for Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring Use Case

User Story	Tested Functionalities	Components	Motivation	Description
1	Domain Bootstrapping	MUD Server, AAA server, DLT, Domain Manager, Trusted Component, Protection Profile Composer	It must be ensured that the FES is in a correct and trustworthy state and to be securely enrolled in the network.	The trustworthiness and the secure enrollment of the wearable is achieved by the creation of the updated Protection Profile of the devices.
2	Runtime attestation	Domain Manager, Trust Controls, Attestation Agent, DLT, Device Data and Tracer, Wallet, DLT, Off-Chain Storage, Certification Auditing	The trustworthiness of the FES during runtime must be assured.	This is achieved by the ENTRUS framework with the appropriate attestation scheme.
3	Runtime attestation, Measures for failed attestation	Trust Controls, Certification and Auditing, Software Enforcement, SW Verification, Digital Twin, Protection Profile Composition Engine	The correct operation of the FES and the integrity of the monitored medical data must be assured.	The enforcement of remote FW updates and the assessment of the correct operation of the device after the update is achieved with the revocation of the Conformity Certificate, the update process, the DT simulation and the creation of new certificate and challenge.
4	Misbehavior Detection, Calculation of trust level from	Network Traffic Monitor, DLT, AI-based	The trustworthiness and the integrity of all data produced and exchanged throughout the entire chain	This is achieved by the Misbehavior Detection mechanism during runtime. In case of the detection of

	multiple trust sources	Misbehavior Detection, Protection Profiles Composer, MUD Server	must be assured. The existence of multiple trust sources that can be combined to calculate the trust level must be tested.	malicious behavior in the network data, the appropriate mitigation actions are performed. The decisions of this mechanism form another trust source.
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6.5.5 Metrics of Success

In Table 26, we provide an indicative set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) against which the various operations and components of ENTRUST will be evaluated, as outlined in the User Stories. Note that, as previously mentioned, the values provided for the KPIs are indicative, and will be refined and revised in the context of D6.1 [123].

In addition, note that in the Table, two values are provided for timing and performance related KPIs. This is because, in the instantiation of the gateway device, it is possible to either use a **Tellu Personal Health Gateway (PHG)** device (as outlined in Section 6.3), or with a different, more resource-constrained RPI-based solution. Therefore, we provide KPIs for both these alternatives.

Table 26: KPIs for Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring Use Case

KPI	Description and Values
Time needed for device onboarding	In case RPI-based gateway is used: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Domain bootstrapping: <=10 min In case PHG is used: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboarding of PHGs: <=6 min Onboarding of medical device sensing components to the PHG (acting as the MUD profiles of the devices): <=1000 ms
Key hierarchy construction	Note that this phase is included in the device onboarding process, but is also denoted separately because it may need to be executed again in case the key hierarchy needs to be updated during runtime: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiency of key hierarchy construction and verifiable key restriction usage policies: <=150ms
Time required to perform the integrity check throughout the lifecycle of the CMD	<=200ms
Time needed for the construction of Conformity Certificates	<=900ms
Evaluation of Trust Assessment	This KPI refers to all aspects related to the performance/latency of the calculation of the ATL in the context of the runtime security enablers of ENTRUST. This depends on multiple dimensions, each one of which we have defined different KPIs:

	<p>≥ 3 different trust models of varying sizes. A trust model comprises all possible trust relationships capturing the interactions between the different CMDs.</p> <p>≤ 300ms latency of ATL calculation.</p> <p>If $\geq 70\%$ of attacks are successful, this translates to a failure of the “ATL > RTL” test.</p> <p>Recalculation of RTL considering the identification of new risks: ≤ 3s.</p> <p>Number of trust sources ≥ 3. Attestation, Anomaly/Misbehavior Detection, Safety/Certification of devices.</p>
<p>Dynamic risk assessment based on the identification of new threats</p>	<p>≤ 2s</p>
<p>Fallback firmware update duration</p>	<p>Overhead in the latency of the SW/FW process induced by the integrity verification performed by ENTRUST (i.e., the CIV attestation that verifies that the update has been performed correctly): ≤ 600ms. Note that this does not refer to the firmware update itself, but to the latency induced by the ENTRUST security enabler verifying the correctness of the firmware update (e.g., CIV).</p> <p>In case PHG is used: Upgrading a function/application in the PHG device: ≤ 750ms (considering the update of the application running in a TEE, i.e., secure upgrade).</p>
<p>Accuracy of AI-based Misbehavior Detection mechanism</p>	<p>The accuracy level should be $\geq 70\%$.</p> <p>Detection accuracy should have an improvement in the order of 10% when it operates in tandem with the Trust Assessment. In this context, if the AI-based Misbehaviour Detection flags something as an attack, all subsequent packets are considered as part of the attack and are dropped. However, the Trust Assessment will consider this as a data point, and as such will not drop subsequent packets. Thus, this leads to an increase in detection accuracy.</p>

7 Conclusions

As previously outlined, the core vision of ENTRUST entails the *design and implementation of an end-to-end trust assessment framework for providing operational assurance to Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), as well as the medical networks they are deployed to, throughout their operational lifecycle, in accordance with the latest standards and regulations.* In this deliverable, we provided a detailed overview of several aspects pertaining to the fulfilment of this vision and the design and implementation of the ENTRUST framework, which will provide the basis for the **research, development, implementation, and integration** activities to be carried out throughout the lifecycle of the project. In this regard, this deliverable serves as the basis for all subsequent WPs and deliverables, serving as a reference for the envisioned ENTRUST work plan.

Specifically, in Chapter 2, we outlined the core reasoning behind the overall focus of the approach followed in ENTRUST, aimed towards addressing the security requirements of **heterogeneous medical devices** operating in cloud network topologies in an interconnected manner, thus facing an increasingly **expanded attack surface** containing a wide variety of threats and vulnerabilities. ENTRUST aims to provide a holistic security framework that is able to address all relevant requirements faced by the targeted types of medical operations, while also employing the notion of **Zero Trust**. Based on this approach, no device or entity is considered trusted by default, and needs to be able to provide strong guarantees on the correctness of their identity and configuration state. Considering this approach, we provided a detailed overview of the current state-of-the-art with regard to existing regulations and standards related to the provision of cybersecurity assurance in the medical device domain. Next, we outlined the cybersecurity needs and challenges to be addressed by ENTRUST, as well as the gaps in the existing standards that ENTRUST aims to bridge through the provided solution.

Next, in Chapter 3, we identified the **core research pillars** of ENTRUST, corresponding to the **innovative technologies and components** to be integrated into the overall ENTRUST framework. In this regard, ENTRUST aims to push forward the state-of-the-art in the domain of medical device management, thus enhancing the posture of the EU within the research community and providing significant contributions to the literature, in order to enable other research or industrial organizations to build upon the produced results. Specifically, the scope of ENTRUST contains a wide variety of research domains, including **formal verification models, software verification techniques, threat modelling, trust assessment, Digital Twins, runtime attestation schemes, use of PUFs** and other Trusted components in the context of the medical domain, **AI-based Misbehaviour Detection**, and **issuance of Conformity Certificates**. For each of these domains, we provided the motivation behind the ENTRUST approach, as well as a state-of-the-art analysis considering the latest advancements documented in the literature.

The focus of Chapter 4 was on the documentation of the core **requirements to be fulfilled by the ENTRUST solution**. Specifically, we first conducted an extensive analysis of existing standards and regulations pertaining to the medical device domain, and we documented all identified requirements. Afterwards, we curated this list by considering the most relevant requirements in the context of ENTRUST, in order to provide operational assurance for medical devices in all phases of their operational lifecycle, including **manufacturing, deployment, normal operation, and end-of-life**. The result of this analysis was a set of requirements which were placed into four core categories, namely **Framework Requirements, Security Requirements, Operational Requirements, and Legal and Ethical Requirements**, covering the entire scope of the ENTRUST project.

Considering the previously outlined approach, Chapter 5 documents the **high-level conceptual architecture** of ENTRUST, which provides the basis for the development of the overall ENTRUST framework. Specifically, this process was split into three core phases: (i) the **design phase** of the CMD, which involves the actual design and development by the manufacturer and includes processes such as the conceptualization and requirements assessment, as well as any actions to be performed before the device is received by a medical organization. The **pre-deployment** phase includes all actions taken after the device leaves the manufacturing floor and is delivered to the end-user (before the actual operation of the device), such as the integration of the device into the network of the organization, the secure enrollment and bootstrapping, and the risk assessment. Finally, the **runtime phase** entails all actions to be performed during the normal operation of the device in order to provide runtime operational assurance, such as attestation operations, AI-based misbehavior detection (i.e., anomaly detection in network traffic data), the deployment of secure updates, and the secure sharing of threat intelligence data and Conformity Certificates.

Finally, Chapter 6 is dedicated to an overview of the envisioned use case demonstrators and the associated user stories for each, aiming to cover the entirety of the components and services provided by the ENTRUST Framework. Specifically, (i) the **Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring of Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting** aims to provide runtime assurance to devices related to cardiovascular health, (ii) the **Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living** use case entails the use of a gateway deployed to a patient's home in order to monitor their health through a set of medical sensors and monitors, (iii) the **Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carriers** aims to securely monitor the state of a patient during their transportation with an ambulance and to ensure trust across legacy systems in an emergency care unit, and (iv) the **Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data** use case employs wearable devices in order to provide and manage diagnostic data related to mental health.

Overall, this deliverable provides a detailed overview of all core aspects of the ENTRUST work plan for the design and implementation of the envisioned solution and serves as a comprehensive reference document for detailing the actions to be performed by the ENTRUST consortium throughout the lifecycle of the project. It follows from all the above that ENTRUST constitutes a significant step forward in the domain of cybersecurity for medical devices and will provide a diverse set of research and implementation artefacts that can provide significant added value to medical enterprises and research organizations.

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APPENDIX

Table 27: Comprehensive list of requirements for the medical domain

Category	Process Phase	Requirement #	Name	Description	Reasoning	KPIs	Means of verification	Attacks to counter	Mitigation Measure
		<i>Unique number for the requirements for cross-refs</i>	<i>A short name of the requirement</i>	<i>Description of the requirement</i>	<i>More elaborated reasoning why the requirement is needed; what is it good for</i>	<i>Possible Measurable Success criteria</i>	<i>How the KPIs could be validated</i>	<i>Against which attack(s) does this requirement protect</i>	<i>Which security countermeasures can protect against identified attacks and help achieve the identified requirement</i>
General Requirements	Expertise	SR_1	Role List Creation	Manufacturer creates a list of all roles involved with IT security	To ensure all roles related to IT security are identified and accounted for	Number of roles listed	Review of role list	Unauthorized access	Role-based Access Control
		SR_2	IT Security Expertise Evidence	Manufacturer provides evidence of IT-security expertise for each role	To ensure roles have necessary IT-security expertise	Verification of expertise evidence for each role	Review of expertise evidence	Incompetent security management	Continuous Training & Certification
		SR_3	Expertise Verification Records	Manufacturer maintains records demonstrating expertise	To ensure people in roles have the necessary expertise	Number of records, quality of training documents	Review of records and training documents	Incompetent security management	Regular Audits & Record Keeping
		SR_4	Product-specific Expertise	Development plans define product-specific expertise	To ensure understanding of product-specific security requirements	Number of plans including product-specific expertise	Review of development plans	Product specific attacks	Training in Product-specific security
Process Requirements Product development requirements	Intended purpose and stakeholder requirement	SR_5	Neighboring System Identification	Manufacturer identifies all neighboring systems that may connect to the product	To understand potential points of interaction	Number of neighboring systems identified	Review of system list	Cross-system attacks	Network Segmentation & Firewall
		SR_6	Interaction Role List	Manufacturer creates a list of roles that may interact with the product	To understand potential users and systems interacting with the product	Number of roles listed	Review of role list	Unauthorized access	Role-based Access Control

		SR_7	Regulatory Requirement Identification	Manufacturer identifies all relevant regulatory requirements in all markets	To ensure compliance with all relevant regulations	Number of identified regulatory requirements	Review of identified regulations	Non-compliance penalties	Regular Compliance Reviews
		SR_8	User Identification	Manufacturer identifies the intended primary and secondary users with their IT expertise	To understand the user base and their IT expertise	Number of users identified, level of IT expertise	Review of user list, IT expertise assessment	User-induced threats	User training, User Access Management
		SR_9	User Environment Definition	Manufacturer defines the intended user environment	To understand the operating environment and its potential vulnerabilities	Quality and detail of environment definition	Review of environment definition	Environment-based attacks	Environment specific security measures
		SR_10	Unspecified User Risk Analysis	Manufacturer analyzes risks if system is used by non-specified user in specified environment	To understand potential risks from unauthorized use	Number and severity of identified risks	Review of risk analysis	Unauthorized user attacks	User Access Management, Training
		SR_11	IT Security Threat Documentation	Manufacturer documents IT security threats and potential consequences	To understand and communicate potential threats and impacts	Quality and detail of threat documentation	Review of threat documentation	Various	Regular Risk Assessment
		SR_12	Risk Acceptance Criteria Generation	Manufacturer generates risk acceptance criteria based on product use and state-of-the-art	To define acceptable levels of risk	Quality and relevance of risk acceptance criteria	Review of risk acceptance criteria	Misjudgment of risk acceptance	Regular Risk Assessment
		SR_13	IT Security Risk Evaluation System	Manufacturer develops system for evaluating IT security-related risks	To regularly evaluate and manage IT security risks	Functionality and accuracy of risk evaluation system	Testing and review of risk evaluation system	Various	Regular Risk Assessment

Process Requirements Product development System and software Requirements	Authentication and authorization	SR_14	Data Interface Identification	Manufacturer identifies all data interfaces	To understand points of data transfer	Number of identified data interfaces	Review of identified data interfaces	Data breach	Encryption, Network Segmentation
		SR_15	Protocol and Standard Specification	Manufacturer specifies protocols and standards used for each data interface	To ensure secure and standardized data transfer	Number of specified protocols and standards	Review of specified protocols and standards	Protocol and standard attacks	Use of Secure Protocols and Standards
		SR_16	Interface Function Specification	Manufacturer specifies functions offered via each data interface	To understand potential vulnerabilities of each interface	Number of specified functions	Review of specified functions	Function-based attacks	Secure Coding Practices
		SR_17	Security Relevance Analysis	Manufacturer analyzes each function's security relevance	To understand the security impact of each function	Number and severity of identified security relevant functions	Review of security relevance analysis	Function-based attacks	Secure Coding Practices
		SR_18	Safety-Relevant Function Documentation	Manufacturer documents effects of safety-relevant functions in risk management documentation	To communicate potential safety impacts	Quality and detail of safety-relevant function documentation	Review of safety-relevant function documentation	Function-based attacks	Secure Coding Practices
		SR_19	Unspecified Information Display Risk Testing	Manufacturer tests scenarios where risks are generated due to unspecified information display	To understand and mitigate risks from incorrect or missing information display	Number of tested scenarios, number and severity of identified risks	Review of test results	Misinformation attacks	User Interface Design Best Practices
		SR_20	Accessible Function Definition	Manufacturer defines product functions accessible to each role and neighboring system	To manage access to functionalities	Number of defined accessible functions	Review of function access definitions	Unauthorized access	Role-based Access Control

Data, Communication	SR_21	Authentication Procedure Justification	Manufacturer justifies choice of authentication procedure for all roles and neighboring systems	To ensure secure and appropriate authentication	Number of justified authentication procedures	Review of authentication justifications	Authentication attacks	Multi-factor Authentication
	SR_22	Additional Access Mechanisms	Manufacturer requests additional mechanisms to minimize unauthorized access where necessary	To strengthen system security	Number of requested additional mechanisms	Review of additional mechanisms	Unauthorized access	Additional Security Mechanisms
	SR_23	Access Failure Risk Analysis	Manufacturer analyzes effects on patient safety if a person cannot access patient or device data and defines measures	To ensure patient safety in case of access failures	Number and quality of defined measures	Review of risk analysis and defined measures	Denial of access	Recovery Mechanisms, Training
	SR_24	Data Management List	Manufacturer creates a list of all data managed by the system	To understand and manage data	Number of listed data items	Review of data list	Data breach	Data Classification and Protection
	SR_25	Data Protection Worthiness Assessment	Manufacturer assesses worthiness of data protection in relation to confidentiality and patient safety	To ensure proper data protection	Number of assessed data items	Review of assessment	Data breach, Patient safety issues	Data Classification and Protection
	SR_26	Sensitive Data Protection Risk Evaluation	Manufacturer evaluates effect if particularly sensitive data is no longer protected	To ensure proper protection of sensitive data	Quality of evaluation	Review of risk evaluation	Data breach	Data Classification and Protection
	SR_27	Overloading System Risk Investigation	Manufacturer investigates consequences of overloading system with too many requests or large volumes and defines actions	To mitigate risks from system overload	Number and quality of defined actions	Review of risk investigation and actions	Denial of Service (DoS)	DoS protection measures

		SR_28	Network Availability Risk Analysis	Manufacturer analyzes consequences if network is no longer available or no longer in expected quality	To mitigate risks from network failures	Quality of risk analysis	Review of risk analysis	Network failure	Network Redundancy and Failover
		SR_29	Data Loss Risk Analysis and Actions	Manufacturer analyzes consequences of data loss and establishes actions, such as making a backup	To mitigate risks from data loss	Number and quality of established actions	Review of risk analysis and actions	Data loss	Regular Backups, RAID Systems
		SR_30	External Data Checking Criteria	Manufacturer establishes criteria for checking of external data before processing	To ensure data integrity	Quality of established criteria	Review of criteria	Data corruption	Data Validation Techniques
	Patches	SR_31	Patch Management Plan	Manufacturer documents plan of how patches are applied and removed, including development, distribution, installation, and review	To maintain system security and stability	Quality and detail of patch management plan	Review of patch management plan	Exploitation of known vulnerabilities	Regular Patching and Updates
		SR_32	SOUP/OTS Component List	Manufacturer has a list of all Software of Unknown Provenance/Off-The-Shelf (SOUP/OTS) components	To manage and track all external software components	Number of listed SOUP/OTS components	Review of SOUP/OTS component list	Exploitation of vulnerabilities in external components	Regular Updates of SOUP/OTS Components
		SR_33	Patch Frequency Assessment	Manufacturer assesses how often patches are required and how they should be installed	To maintain system security and stability	Frequency of required patches, quality of installation method	Review of patch frequency assessment	Exploitation of known vulnerabilities	Regular Patching and Updates
	Others	SR_34	Cybersecurity Compromise User Notification	Manufacturer establishes how the medical device informs users in the event of cybersecurity compromise	To alert users of potential threats	Quality of user notification method	Testing of user notification method	Various	User Notification System

		SR_35	Functionality Assurance Assessment	Manufacturer assesses functionality the medical device must guarantee in the event of cybersecurity compromise	To maintain essential functionality in the event of a breach	Quality of functionality assurance assessment	Review of functionality assurance assessment	Various	Backup Systems, Redundancy
Process Requirements Product Requirement Product development requirements System and Software Architecture		SR_36	SOUP/OTS Component Documentation	Manufacturer documents all SOUP/OTS components, including version, manufacturer, update information, release notes	To manage and track all external software components	Quality and detail of SOUP/OTS component documentation	Review of SOUP/OTS component documentation	Exploitation of vulnerabilities in external components	Regular Updates of SOUP/OTS Components
		SR_37	Technology Risk Analysis	Manufacturer analyzes specific risks resulting from the choice of technologies, including programming language, SOUP/OTS components	To understand and mitigate potential technology-related risks	Quality of technology risk analysis	Review of technology risk analysis	Technology-specific attacks	Secure Coding Practices, Regular Updates
		SR_38	Malicious Code Protection Measures	Manufacturer takes measures to ensure tools used, platforms, and SOUP/OTS components are free of malicious code	To prevent malicious code infiltration	Number and quality of malicious code protection measures	Testing of tools, platforms, and components	Malware attacks	Antivirus Software, Regular Scanning
		SR_39	External Service List	Manufacturer creates a list of all services that the product offers or uses externally, e.g., through its operating system	To manage and track all external services	Number of listed external services	Review of external service list	Exploitation of vulnerabilities in external services	Regular Updates of External Services
		SR_40	External Service Justification	Manufacturer justifies why each service has to be visible externally with no time limitation	To ensure necessary services are accessible externally	Number of justified external services	Review of service justifications	Unauthorized access, Data breach	Firewall, Network Segmentation
		SR_41	Interface Attack Control	Manufacturer describes how attacks via product interfaces are controlled in the context of risk management	To prevent and manage potential interface attacks	Quality of attack control description	Review of interface attack control plan	Interface attacks	Firewall, Intrusion Detection System

		SR_42	Externally Visible Service Process Identification	Manufacturer identifies the process offering/running each externally visible service	To manage and monitor externally visible services	Number of identified service processes	Review of service process identifications	Unauthorized process execution	Process Auditing, Monitoring
		SR_43	OS-Level User Identification and Justification	Manufacturer identifies the user at the operating system level for each process and justifies if user does not run with minimal rights	To manage user rights and prevent unauthorized actions	Number of identified and justified OS-level users	Review of OS-level user identifications and justifications	Privilege escalation	User Access Control, Principle of Least Privilege
		SR_44	IT Security Threat Modeling	Manufacturer systematically identifies risks caused by deficient IT security using threat modeling	To identify and manage potential IT security threats	Quality of threat modeling	Review of threat modeling	Various	Threat Modeling, Regular Security Audits
		SR_45	Anti-Malware Update Risk Analysis	Manufacturer analyzes risks resulting from the (auto-)update of anti-malware software	To manage risks from potential anti-malware update issues	Quality of risk analysis	Review of anti-malware update risk analysis	Malware attacks due to outdated software	Regular Updates, Anti-malware Software
		SR_46	Compromised IT Security Detection, Documentation, and Reaction	Manufacturer establishes how the product detects compromised IT security, documents this and reacts quickly	To detect and respond to IT security compromises	Quality of detection, documentation, and reaction plan	Testing of IT security compromise detection and reaction	Various	Intrusion Detection System, Incident Response Plan
		SR_47	Audit Log Protection and Analysis	Manufacturer determines where audit log data is stored, how it is protected and updated, and how it can be automatically analyzed	To protect and analyze audit logs effectively	Quality of audit log protection and analysis plan	Testing of audit log protection and automatic analysis	Unauthorized access to logs, Data tampering	Log Encryption, Automatic Log Analysis
		SR_48	IT Security Problem Risk Analysis	Manufacturer analyzes risks arising if software components, services, processes, and data do not behave in accordance with specifications due to IT	To manage risks from potential IT security problems	Quality of risk analysis	Review of IT security problem risk analysis	Various	Regular Security Audits, Secure Coding Practices

				security problems						
		SR_49	Software Requirement Consideration in Architecture	Manufacturer takes software requirements into account in the software architecture	To ensure software architecture meets requirements	Quality of software architecture	Review of software architecture	Various	Proper Software Design and Architecture	
Implementation and development of the software		SR_50	Coding Guidelines for IT Security	Manufacturer creates coding guidelines that establish specific requirements for IT security	To ensure secure coding practices	Quality of coding guidelines	Review of coding guidelines	Various	Secure Coding Practices	
		SR_51	Safe Code Deployment	Manufacturer only deploys code where reverse engineering and RAM readout cannot lead to unacceptable risks	To prevent reverse engineering and unauthorized data access	Quality of code deployment strategy	Testing of code deployment	Reverse Engineering, Unauthorized Data Access	Code Obfuscation, Memory Protection Techniques	
		SR_52	Pre-Delivery Malicious Code Testing	Manufacturer tests software (source code and binaries) for malicious code before delivery and/or protects all computers involved in software development and "production" against malware	To prevent malware infection	Quality of malware testing and protection measures	Testing of malware protection measures, review of testing records	Malware Attacks	Regular Malware Scanning, Antivirus Software	
		SR_53	Buffer Overflow Mitigation Measures	Manufacturer defines measures that can find and eliminate buffer overflows	To prevent buffer overflow attacks	Quality of buffer overflow mitigation measures	Testing of buffer overflow mitigation measures	Buffer Overflow Attacks	Secure Coding Practices, Buffer Overflow Protection Techniques	
	Evaluation of Software Units		SR_54	Coding Guideline Compliance Check Method	Manufacturer defines at least one method used to check compliance with the coding guidelines	To ensure adherence to secure coding practices	Quality of compliance check method	Review of compliance check method	Various	Code Review, Automated Code Analysis Tools

		SR_55	Security-Relevant Component Code Reviews	Manufacturer requires code reviews for all components that map (IT) security-relevant functions	To ensure secure coding practices for security-relevant components	Number of security-relevant components reviewed	Review of code review records	Various	Code Review
		SR_56	Code Review Test Criteria	Manufacturer has concrete test criteria in its specification documents for the code reviews	To ensure effective code reviews	Quality of test criteria	Review of test criteria	Various	Code Review
		SR_57	Four-Eye Principle Code Reviews	Code reviews are carried out according to the four-eye principle and only by people who have the necessary expertise, and the manufacturer has documented this expertise	To ensure thorough and knowledgeable code reviews	Number of code reviews conducted under the four-eye principle	Review of code review records and documented expertise	Various	Code Review
		SR_58	Required Unit Tests and Coverage	Manufacturer establishes which tests (e.g., unit tests) are necessary with which test cases and which degrees of coverage are necessary	To ensure thorough testing of software components	Quality of testing strategy, achieved test coverage	Review of testing strategy, test results	Various	Unit Testing, Code Coverage Analysis
		SR_59	SOUP and OTS Component Verification	Manufacturer describes how all Software of Unknown Provenance and Off-The-Shelf (SOUP/OTS) components have to be verified	To ensure the security and reliability of external components	Quality of SOUP/OTS component verification process	Review of SOUP/OTS component verification process	Exploitation of vulnerabilities in external components	Regular Updates of SOUP/OTS Components, Component Verification
		System and Software Tests	SR_60	Network Interface Port Scans	Manufacturer includes port scans at all relevant network interfaces in the test plan and performs them	To identify vulnerabilities and unauthorized services	Number of performed port scans	Review of test plan and test results	Various

		SR_61	Data Interface Penetration Tests	Manufacturer includes penetration tests at all relevant data interfaces and/or for all known vulnerabilities of the OTS components used in the test plan and performs them	To identify vulnerabilities and potential exploits	Number of performed penetration tests	Review of test plan and test results	Various	Regular Penetration Testing
		SR_62	Use of Vulnerability Scanners	Manufacturer includes the use of “vulnerability scanners” in the test plan	To identify vulnerabilities in the system	Number of performed vulnerability scans	Review of test plan and scan results	Various	Regular Vulnerability Scanning
		SR_63	Data Interface Fuzz Testing	Manufacturer includes fuzz tests at all relevant data interfaces with at least one tool in the test plan and performs them	To identify potential software bugs and vulnerabilities	Number of performed fuzz tests	Review of test plan and test results	Various	Regular Fuzz Testing
		SR_64	Usual Attack Vector Security Check	Manufacturer includes a security check against the usual attack vectors in the test plan	To prepare for and protect against common attacks	Number of attack vectors checked	Review of test plan and security check results	Various	Regular Security Checks
		SR_65	Robustness and Performance Testing	Manufacturer includes the testing of robustness and performance in the test plan	To ensure the system's ability to handle expected and peak loads	Quality of robustness and performance tests	Review of test plan and test results	DDoS Attacks, Performance-related Issues	Load Testing, Stress Testing
		SR_66	System/Software Requirements Testing	Manufacturer includes the testing of all system/software requirements (see above) in the test plan	To validate that all system/software requirements have been met	Quality of system/software requirements tests	Review of test plan and test results	Various	Thorough Testing of All Requirements

Product Release	SR_67	IT Security Expert Software Check	Manufacturer has its software checked by IT security experts with regard to the above measures	To validate the effectiveness of implemented security measures	Number of expert checks performed	Review of expert check reports	Various	Regular Security Reviews by Experts	
	SR_68	Inclusion of Third-Party Test Reports	Manufacturer includes third-party test reports (e.g. from SOUP manufacturers) in the system test (if available)	To leverage external expertise and additional resources in testing	Number of third-party test reports included	Review of test plan and third-party test reports	Various	Inclusion of Third-Party Test Reports	
	SR_69	Addressing Common Errors and Hazards	Manufacturer has addressed the most common errors and the resulting hazards in the risk analysis or can at least explain how these risks are controlled	To prepare for and mitigate common risks	Quality of risk analysis and control measures	Review of risk analysis and control measures	Various	Risk Analysis, Control Measures	
	SR_70	Attack Vector Risk Control	Manufacturer discusses the risks posed by all relevant attack vectors in the risk analysis and shows how these risks are controlled	To proactively manage and control potential attack risks	Quality of risk analysis and control measures	Review of risk analysis and control measures	Various	Risk Analysis, Control Measures	
	SR_71	Risk-Control Measures Effectiveness Check	Manufacturer has checked the effectiveness of all risk-control measures	To validate the effectiveness of implemented risk-control measures	Number of effective risk-control measures	Review of risk-control measures and their effectiveness check results	Various	Regular Effectiveness Checks	
	SR_72	IT Security Risk Traceability Matrix	Manufacturer has created a traceability matrix it uses to document that there are measures that control all risks related to IT security	To map and manage all risks related to IT security	Quality of traceability matrix	Review of the traceability matrix	Various	Traceability Matrix	
	SR_73	Risk Management and IT Security Report Preparation	Manufacturer has prepared the risk management report and the IT security report	To document and communicate risk management and IT security activities	Quality of risk management and IT security reports	Review of the reports	Various	Risk Management, IT Security Report	

		SR_74	Post-Development Phase Plans	Manufacturer has drawn up the necessary plans for the post-development phase (e.g. post-market surveillance and incident response plan)	To manage post-development activities effectively	Quality of post-development phase plans	Review of the plans	Various	Post-Development Phase Plans
		SR_75	Test Completeness Check	Manufacturer has tested the completeness of the tests using a traceability matrix that links the tests to the requirements	To ensure all requirements are tested	Quality of test completeness check	Review of the traceability matrix and test results	Various	Test Completeness Check
Process Requirements for the post-development phases	Production, Distribution, Installation	SR_76	Product Delivery Check	Manufacturer has described how it ensures that only the exact intended artifacts (files) in exactly the intended version are delivered in the product or as a product	To ensure the correct and intended version of the product is delivered	Consistency of delivered products and their versions	Review of product delivery procedure and actual deliveries	Various	Product Delivery Check
		SR_77	Installation Version Clarity	Manufacturer has described how the people responsible for the installation know which is the latest version and how confusion during installation can be prevented	To ensure the latest and correct version of the product is installed	Clarity and accuracy of installation instructions	Review of installation instructions and actual installations	Various	Clear Installation Instructions
		SR_78	Installation Requirement Check	Manufacturer has described how it ensures during the installation that the requirements specified in the support materials are actually met	To ensure all installation requirements are met	Consistency of installed products and their requirements	Review of installation procedure and actual installations	Various	Installation Requirement Check
		SR_79	Quick Communication Procedures	Manufacturer has established procedures that ensure that it can communicate quickly with operators and users of its products	To ensure quick and effective communication with users and operators	Quality and speed of communication	Review of communication procedures and actual communications	Various	Quick Communication Procedures

Post-Market Surveillance	SR_80	Post-market Surveillance Plan	Manufacturer has created a post-market surveillance plan	To keep track of the product's performance and issues after it has been released to the market	Quality of the post-market surveillance plan	Review of the post-market surveillance plan	Various	Post-market Surveillance Plan
	SR_81	Downstream Phase Information Collection	Manufacturer has described which information is collected from the downstream phase	To have a clear understanding of the product's performance in the downstream phase	Quality and relevance of collected information	Review of collected information from the downstream phase	Various	Data Collection Plan
	SR_82	Downstream Phase Information Channels	Manufacturer has described how and through which channels information is collected from the downstream phase	To ensure information is collected effectively from the downstream phase	Efficiency of information collection channels	Review of information collection channels and procedures	Various	Information Collection Channels
	SR_83	Downstream Phase Information Analysis	Manufacturer has described what information is analyzed and evaluated from the downstream phase	To gain insights from the collected downstream phase information	Quality and relevance of the analysis results	Review of the analysis results	Various	Data Analysis Plan
	SR_84	Downstream Phase Resulting Measures	Manufacturer has described the resulting measures	To respond appropriately to the insights gained from the downstream phase	Quality and relevance of the resulting measures	Review of the resulting measures	Various	Action Plan
	SR_85	OTS Component Security Problem Monitoring	For each OTS component, the manufacturer has defined at least one source through which it is informed of IT security problems and how often it is monitored and described the role this analysis performs with which tools	To keep track of IT security problems related to OTS components	Frequency and quality of IT security problem monitoring	Review of the monitoring results and procedures	IT security problems related to OTS components	OTS Component Security Problem Monitoring

Incident Response Plan	SR_86	Technology and Procedure Security Monitoring	Manufacturer has described how it monitors that the technologies and procedures used (e.g. cryptology) are still secure	To ensure the continued security of the used technologies and procedures	Quality and frequency of security monitoring	Review of the monitoring results and procedures	Various	Security Monitoring
	SR_87	Incident Response Plan	Manufacturer has created an incident response plan	To respond effectively to incidents	Quality of the incident response plan	Review of the incident response plan	Various	Incident Response Plan
	SR_88	Incident Response Plan Criteria	The incident response plan governs the criteria the manufacturer uses to evaluate information from the market and when it implements the emergency plan	To have clear guidelines for responding to incidents	Quality of the incident response plan criteria	Review of the incident response plan and its criteria	Various	Incident Response Plan Criteria
	SR_89	Patch Development and Release	Who develops and releases the patches and how and within what deadlines	To manage patches effectively	Speed and quality of patch development and release	Review of the patch development and release procedures and results	Various	Patch Management
	SR_90	Patch Acquisition	How the customer obtains the patches	To ensure patches are easily and promptly accessible to customers	Efficiency and effectiveness of patch acquisition process	Review of the patch acquisition process	Various	Patch Acquisition Procedure
	SR_91	Patch Installation Assurance	How the manufacturer ensures that the patches are also installed	To ensure patches are installed properly by the customers	Efficiency and effectiveness of patch installation assurance process	Review of the patch installation assurance process	Various	Patch Installation Assurance Procedure
	SR_92	Customer Notification	Who informs the customers, how and within what deadlines	To ensure customers are timely and accurately informed about any issues or updates	Efficiency and effectiveness of customer notification process	Review of the customer notification process	Various	Customer Notification Procedure

		SR_93	Decommissioning or Product Recall	In which cases decommissioning or other product recalls is ordered and how	To manage critical situations like product recalls efficiently	Quality of the decommissioning or product recall procedure	Review of the decommissioning or product recall procedure	Various	Decommissioning or Product Recall Procedure
Product Requirements System / Software requirements	Authentication	SR_94	User Authentication	The product only allows users to use it if they have authenticated themselves to the product	To prevent unauthorized access	Effectiveness of the user authentication mechanism	Test of the user authentication mechanism	Unauthorized access	User Authentication Mechanism
		SR_95	Neighboring System Authentication	The product allows the neighboring systems (e.g. other medical devices, IT systems) connected at each data interface to exchange data only if they have been authenticated by the product	To prevent unauthorized data exchange	Effectiveness of the neighboring system authentication mechanism	Test of the neighboring system authentication mechanism	Unauthorized data exchange	Neighboring System Authentication Mechanism
		SR_96	Password Complexity	The product allows password authentication only if this has a defined minimum length of which at least one is a non-alphanumeric character and it contains at least one uppercase and one lowercase character	To ensure the strength of passwords and hence security	Compliance with password complexity requirements	Test of password complexity requirements	Weak passwords	Password Complexity Requirements
		SR_97	Default Password Policy	The product does not have a default password or requires that a password be changed during the first use	To prevent unauthorized access using default passwords	Compliance with default password policy	Test of default password policy	Unauthorized access using default passwords	Default Password Policy
		SR_98	User Blocking	The product blocks users and neighboring systems for m minutes after n attempts, with the manufacturer able to define the n and m values or their lower limits	To prevent brute-force attacks	Effectiveness of user blocking mechanism	Test of user blocking mechanism	Brute-force attacks	User Blocking Mechanism

		SR_99	Risk Analysis of User Blocking	The manufacturer has analyzed the "safety-related" risks resulting from such a blocking and, if necessary, has implemented measures to minimize these risks	To ensure the user blocking mechanism doesn't lead to safety risks	Quality of the risk analysis and implemented measures	Review of the risk analysis and implemented measures	Safety risks due to user blocking	Risk Analysis and Measures
		SR_100	Login Failure Information	In the event of an unsuccessful login, the product only displays information that does not allow the user to identify the exact cause of the blocking	To protect system information	Quality of displayed information during login failure	Review of the information displayed on login failure	Information Disclosure	Limited Information Display
		SR_101	Session Termination	The product terminates user and neighboring system sessions after n minutes of inactivity	To prevent misuse of inactive sessions	Compliance with session termination policy	Test of session termination policy	Misuse of inactive sessions	Session Termination Policy
		SR_102	Role Assignment	The product assigns a role to each user and each neighboring system for authentication	To manage system access based on roles	Effectiveness of role assignment	Review of role assignment process	Unauthorized access	Role-Based Access Control
		SR_103	Access Control	The product allows each role to access only the functions it is authorized for	To manage system access based on roles	Compliance with access control policy	Test of access control policy	Unauthorized access	Access Control Policy
		SR_104	User Blocking	The product allows authorized users to block other users and neighboring systems	To manage system access	Efficiency of user blocking process	Test of user blocking process	Unauthorized access	User Blocking Procedure

Communication and Storage	SR_105	Authentication Reset	The product allows authorized users to reset the authentication of any required elements of other users and neighboring systems	To manage system access	Efficiency of authentication reset process	Test of authentication reset process	Unauthorized access	Authentication Reset Procedure
	SR_106	User Deletion	The product allows authorized users to delete other users and neighboring systems	To manage system access	Efficiency of user deletion process	Test of user deletion process	Unauthorized access	User Deletion Procedure
	SR_107	Permission Modification Restriction	The product does not allow users to change their own permissions	To prevent unauthorized access or escalation of privileges	Compliance with permission modification restriction policy	Test of permission modification restriction policy	Unauthorized access, Escalation of privileges	Permission Modification Restriction Policy
	SR_108	Permission Cancellation	The product allows permissions to be canceled (“breaking the glass”), and identifies/documents the person and the reasons	To manage emergencies or critical situations	Efficiency and effectiveness of permission cancellation process	Review of permission cancellation process	Various	Permission Cancellation Procedure
	SR_109	Server-side Cybersecurity	In a client-server architecture, all cybersecurity measures are determined and checked on the server side	To ensure system security	Compliance with server-side cybersecurity measures	Review of server-side cybersecurity measures	Various	Server-side Cybersecurity Measures
	SR_110	Client Input Check	In a client-server architecture, all client inputs are checked on the server side	To ensure data integrity	Compliance with input check policy	Test of input check policy	Data corruption	Input Check Policy
	SR_111	Patient Data Deletion	The product allows users to permanently delete all patient-specific data. - The product allows you to restrict permissions to do this	To manage patient data privacy	Efficiency of patient data deletion process	Test of patient data deletion process	Data Breach	Patient Data Deletion Procedure

		SR_112	Data Protection	The product protects data from accidental deletion	To ensure data integrity	Compliance with data protection measures	Review of data protection measures	Data loss	Data Protection Measures
		SR_113	Data Encryption	The product only transmits data via its data interfaces in encrypted form. This also applies to storage on external data carrier	To protect data during transmission and storage	Compliance with data encryption policy	Test of data encryption policy	Data interception, Data breach	Data Encryption Policy
		SR_114	Data Integrity	The product protects the integrity of the data against unwanted modification	To ensure data integrity	Compliance with data integrity measures	Review of data integrity measures	Data corruption, Data modification	Data Integrity Measures
		SR_115	Connection Rejection	By default, the product rejects all incoming connections	To protect the system from unauthorized access	Compliance with connection rejection policy	Test of connection rejection policy	Unauthorized access	Connection Rejection Policy
		SR_116	Data Verification	The product checks all user inputs and all incoming data on the basis of verification criteria defined by the manufacturer	To ensure data integrity	Compliance with data verification policy	Test of data verification policy	Data corruption	Data Verification Policy
		SR_117	No Wireless Critical Data	The product does not use wireless transmission for the transmission of time-critical data relevant to patient safety	To ensure timely and reliable data transmission	Compliance with wireless transmission policy	Review of wireless transmission policy	Data loss, Data delay	Wireless Transmission Policy
		SR_118	Password Storage	The product stores passwords as "salted hash" only	To protect password data	Compliance with password storage policy	Review of password storage policy	Password cracking	Password Storage Policy

Patches	SR_119	Encrypted Personal Data	The product stores characteristics that could be used to identify a person in encrypted form only	To protect personal data	Compliance with personal data encryption policy	Review of personal data encryption policy	Data breach	Personal Data Encryption Policy
	SR_120	Critical Data Protection	The product protects critical data against accidental change and loss	To ensure data integrity and availability	Compliance with critical data protection policy	Review of critical data protection measures	Data loss, Data corruption	Critical Data Protection Policy
	SR_121	Data Sync Check	Every time the program is restarted, it checks whether the mechanisms used to protect the data against loss and modification are in sync	To ensure data integrity and availability	Compliance with data sync check policy	Test of data sync check procedure	Data loss, Data corruption	Data Sync Check Policy
	SR_122	Interface Deactivation	The product allows users to deactivate data interfaces	To secure potential entry points into the system	Compliance with interface deactivation policy	Test of interface deactivation process	Unauthorized access	Interface Deactivation Policy
	SR_123	Code Integrity Check	The product checks the integrity of the program code every time it is restarted	To ensure the reliability and safety of the product	Compliance with code integrity check policy	Test of code integrity check procedure	Code corruption	Code Integrity Check Policy
	SR_124	Emergency Mode	In the event of that security is compromised, the product provides an emergency mode for functions that have an effect on patient safety	To ensure patient safety under compromised conditions	Efficiency of emergency mode	Test of emergency mode	Cybersecurity attacks	Emergency Mode Procedure
	SR_125	Patch Application	The product allows patches to be applied	To facilitate updates and fixes	Compliance with patch application policy	Test of patch application process	Software bugs, Vulnerabilities	Patch Application Policy

		SR_126	Patch Roll-back	The product allows you to remove defective patches again	To ensure system stability and safety	Compliance with patch roll-back policy	Test of patch roll-back process	Faulty patches	Patch Roll-back Policy
		SR_127	Patch Access Control	The product limits the ability to apply or remove patches to users with the corresponding permissions	To maintain system security	Compliance with patch access control policy	Review of patch access control process	Unauthorized access	Patch Access Control Policy
Other		SR_128	Patch Integrity Check	The product checks changed program code (patches) for integrity before first use and when restarted	To ensure system stability and safety	Compliance with patch integrity check policy	Test of patch integrity check process	Code corruption	Patch Integrity Check Policy
		SR_129	Audit Logging	The product logs all essential actions on/in the system in an audit log, including day and time and actor	To maintain a record of system activities for analysis and troubleshooting	Efficiency of audit logging	Review of audit logs	Unauthorized activities	Audit Logging Procedure
		SR_130	System Time	The product ensures that it has the correct system time	To maintain accurate timestamps for logging and other functions	Accuracy of system time	Review of system time mechanism	Time-related attacks	System Time Policy
		SR_131	Audit Log Protection	The product protects the audit log against change	To ensure the integrity of the audit logs	Compliance with audit log protection policy	Test of audit log protection measures	Unauthorized changes to audit logs	Audit Log Protection Policy
		SR_132	Attack Detection	The product implements mechanisms that can detect penetration or an attack and react to them	To ensure the product's resilience against attacks	Efficiency of attack detection mechanisms	Test of attack detection mechanisms	Various cyber attacks	Attack Detection and Response Policy

Product Requirements	System / Software Architecture	SR_133	Certificate Exchange	The product allows the exchange of certificates	To maintain secure communication channels	Compliance with certificate exchange policy	Test of certificate exchange process	Man-in-the-middle attacks	Certificate Exchange Policy
		SR_134	Cryptographic Libraries	The software only uses tried and tested libraries/components for all cryptographic functions	To ensure reliable and secure cryptography	Compliance with cryptographic library usage policy	Review of cryptographic library usage	Cryptographic attacks	Cryptographic Library Usage Policy
		SR_135	Cryptographic Separation	The software uses different technologies or keys for different functions	To ensure the security of different cryptographic functions	Compliance with cryptographic separation policy	Review of cryptographic separation	Cryptographic attacks	Cryptographic Separation Policy
		SR_136	Malware Protection	The software is protected against malware as far as is technically possible	To ensure the security and reliability of the software	Efficiency of malware protection measures	Test of malware protection measures	Malware attacks	Malware Protection Policy
		SR_137	Secure SOUP/OTS Components	The software is based on versions of the SOUP/OTS components that do not contain any security vulnerabilities	To ensure the security and reliability of the software	Compliance with secure SOUP/OTS components policy	Review of SOUP/OTS component versions	Various attacks exploiting vulnerabilities	Secure SOUP/OTS Components Policy
	Support Materials	SR_138	Intended IT Environment	The instructions for use establish the intended IT environment for operation	To ensure the product operates in a secure and appropriate environment	Compliance with intended IT environment policy	Review of instructions for use	Misconfiguration, Unintended usage	Intended IT Environment Policy
		SR_139	Operator Instructions	The instructions for use specify which activities the operator must perform, as well as how and how often they should be performed	To ensure proper operation and maintenance of the product	Compliance with operator instructions policy	Review of instructions for use	Misuse, Misconfiguration	Operator Instructions Policy

		SR_140	Roles and Responsibilities	The installation and service instructions establish which other roles are responsible for which activities and how often they have to be performed	To ensure clear distribution of responsibilities	Compliance with roles and responsibilities policy	Review of installation and service instructions	Misuse, Misconfiguration	Roles and Responsibilities Policy
		SR_141	Lost/Stolen Authentication Elements	The support materials describe how to deal with lost or stolen authentication elements and forgotten passwords	To ensure secure recovery in case of lost or stolen authentication elements	Compliance with lost/stolen authentication elements policy	Review of support materials	Unauthorized access	Lost/Stolen Authentication Elements Policy
		SR_142	IT Security Problem Recognition	The support materials describe how users can recognize an IT security problem with the product and what to do in this case	To ensure quick response to IT security problems	Compliance with IT security problem recognition policy	Review of support materials	Various cyber attacks	IT Security Problem Recognition Policy
		SR_143	Anti-Malware Software	The support materials describe which anti-malware software has been approved for the product and where it can be obtained and who is responsible for updating it	To ensure the use of approved anti-malware software	Compliance with anti-malware software policy	Review of support materials	Malware attacks	Anti-Malware Software Policy
		SR_144	Manufacturer Contact Details	The support materials contain the manufacturer's contact details, which can be used to contact the manufacturer, for example, in the event of problems with IT security	To ensure easy communication in case of IT security problems	Compliance with manufacturer contact details policy	Review of support materials	Various issues related to IT security	Manufacturer Contact Details Policy
		SR_145	Technical Description	The support materials also give a technical description of the product	To provide users with a comprehensive understanding of the product	Compliance with technical description policy	Review of support materials	Misuse, Misconfiguration	Technical Description Policy

